

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D3.1 - Part1: A literature review

Report on the limits and potential applications of current state-of-the-art OEF, EEW and RRE systems for European conditions

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GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description

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1 INTRODUCTION

The current report is part I of the deliverable 3.1 in the work package 3 of the European TURNkey project (H2020 – SC5 – 2018 – 2 call; action RIA – Research Innovation Action) entitled: “Towards more earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions”. Task 3.1 will survey the current situation of OEF, EEW and RRE systems operating in Europe with respect to the assessment of seismic hazard. Also, this task will assess quantitatively the limits and potentials of these types of systems with respect to the current science and technology and for the critical earthquake scenarios for Europe. These scenarios are often shallow moderate (M 5 to 6.5) earthquakes occurring close (<30 km) to urban centres, although the unusual context of Bucharest with a deep (90-180 km) strong earthquake source at about 150km will also be considered. This survey and assessment will determine a baseline at the beginning of the project that can be used at the end of the project to judge its effectiveness in improving OEF, EEW and RRE for European application. Collaboration with the non-European partners of the project is also planned in this task through learning from their experiences. This task is split into the following two subtasks as summarised in the TURNkey grant agreement:

Subtask 3.1.1: A survey of OEF, EEW and RRE systems operating in Europe (particularly for the TBs) with respect to their methods to assess seismic hazard based on available literature and interviews with the responsible organisations and end-users will be made. This subtask will be conducted in collaboration with WP1 on end-user needs and WP2 on the TBs. The use-case scenarios developed in WP1 will be used to identify the application requirements of the TURNkey EEW, OEF and RRE systems from the end-user perspective. ARU will assume the role of ‘proxy clients’ representing each stakeholder group and advising on system specification and review process. Note that task 1.1 reviews the use of these systems for community resilience, whereas this subtask is only on the assessment of seismic hazard by these systems.

Subtask 3.1.2: A quantitative assessment of the limits and potentials of OEF, EEW and RRE systems for European conditions. This subtask will be based on simulation exercises for typical earthquake and aftershocks scenarios for Europe based on seismic hazard results (e.g. from disaggregation analyses of the FP7 SHARE seismic hazard model and local information provided by the TBs). These simulations will include kinematic modelling of extended seismic sources and computation of broadband seismograms for different tectonic settings. Based on 3.1.1 and the literature, the sensitivity of the results to key parameters, e.g. changes in seismic activity rates, lead times for triggering actions and thresholds for damaging ground motions, will be assessed. SeisComp3 (including Virtual Seismologist) will be used as part of the assessment for EEW.

The deliverable 3.1 is divided into two reports consisting of: part I and part II respectively, on subtask 3.1.1. and subtask 3.1.2. The report Part I is subdivided into seven main sections: this section, section 2: an executive summary for the whole deliverable (Part I and Part II), section 3: a summary of findings from TURNkey work package 1, section 4 Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF), section 5: Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) systems, section 6: Rapidly Responding to Earthquake impacts (RRE). Section 7 provides a bibliography and Section 8 and 9 constitute two appendices.

2 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The end-user expectations and operational requirements of the Forecasting early Warning Consequence prediction and Response (FWCR) platform are discussed in section 3. This short section effectively represents the first stage of WP1's 'proxy-client' input into WP2. The rest of the report is organized in three major disciplines as below:

2.1 Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF)

The literature review and a report on the limits and potential applications of the current state-of-the-art in the Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF) discipline for European conditions are provided in Part I. The different OEF methodologies are introduced, and recent advances are discussed. The OEF is compared with other natural hazards, and the relationship between the short-term probability of a hazardous event occurring and the time-scale of forecasts is discussed. Additionally, a summary of warning systems for other hazards is introduced, and possible lessons for OEF are listed. Several experiences from different countries are briefly discussed, i.e. for Italy, Iceland, Japan, the USA and Romania (see Appendix B). In conclusion, the Epidemic Type Aftershock Sequence (ETAS) is chosen as a promising approach to be implemented within the TURNkey project.

In part II, a cost-benefit analysis approach has been introduced to assess the potential of OEF in Europe. The purpose of this section is to assess the potential of OEF for the mitigation of earthquake risk in Europe at a continental scale. The seismic hazard is combined with the loss and cost quantities to evaluate the benefit-to-cost ratio. This ratio has been considered to identify whether an action in a given site would be beneficial or not. As quantification of loss and cost is not a simple process, a comprehensive parametric analysis is carried out by considering a relatively wide range of values for each parameter. The results of the parametric study, in terms of feasibility of taking a given action, are shown on the continental scale for different ranges of input parameters. Furthermore, it is discussed how often an OEF system may trigger a potential action. The interval between potential triggers of actions by an OEF system found to be sufficiently short (simply the return period of the intensity of interest) such that the local population is aware of what to do and such that the system can be calibrated and tested during actual periods of heightened hazard. The map of the average interval between potential triggers is also provided for Europe. In the end, an easy-to-use graphical tool (anomogram) has been introduced to quickly estimate the benefit-to-cost ratio.

The obtained results revealed that areas of high seismic hazard (e.g. Iceland, Italy, Greece and Turkey) will benefit from OEF if there are low-cost (cost ratios $< 0.1\%$) short-term mitigation actions that can be performed even if the increase in the weekly probability of an earthquake is moderate. These triggers would also occur sufficiently often (more frequently than every 10 to 50 years) in these areas for the local population to have prior experience of what actions to take. Areas of moderate seismic hazard (e.g. Alps, Pyrenees, Rhine graben and south Spain) would only benefit from OEF in the case of very large increases in weekly probabilities and only if low-cost actions are possible (here, the triggers would occur infrequently, i.e. less often than once every 50 years). If the crisis period (heightened hazard) persists for a number of weeks, more expensive actions become cost-beneficial. If actions can mitigate losses that are caused by low-amplitude ground motions, then these actions are more cost-beneficial than actions related to losses caused by stronger earthquake shaking, because low-amplitude ground motions occur much more frequently.

It is possible that even if R is less than unity for a given action (i.e. it is not assessed as being cost-beneficial) that the action may be taken by some people if it was sufficiently cheap (low C) or easy to do. For example, there is a personal cost of risk mitigation actions in day-to-day life (e.g. keeping a well-stocked first aid cabinet) that may not be cost-beneficial given the chance that it is required, but the cost to most people is sufficiently low that this cost is not a barrier to choosing this action.

In conclusion, despite the considerable assumptions made, the results of the simple cost-benefit analyses presented here show that short-term OEF has the potential to trigger cost-beneficial actions over much of Europe, especially if low-cost actions (cost ratios $< 0.1\%$) are identified for an element at risk.

2.2 Earthquake Early Warning (EEW)

Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) is a relatively new strategy for reducing disaster risk and increasing resilience to seismic hazard in urban settings. EEW systems provide real-time information about ongoing earthquakes, enabling individuals, communities, governments, businesses and others located at a distance to take timely action to reduce the probability of harm or loss before the earthquake-induced ground shaking reaches them. Examples of potential losses mitigated by EEW systems include injuries and infrastructure downtime. Such systems are currently operating in nine countries, and are being or have been tested for implementation in 13 more. Deliverable D3.1 - Part 1 reviews state-of-the-art approaches to EEW around the world. We specifically focus on the various algorithms that have been developed for the rapid calculation of seismic source parameters, ground shaking, and potential consequences in the wake of an event. We also discuss limitations of the existing applied methodologies, with a particular emphasis on the lack of engineering-related (i.e., risk and resilience) metrics currently used to support decision-making related to the triggering of alerts by various end-users. Finally, we provide a number of suggestions for future end-user-orientated advances in the field of EEW. For example, we propose that next-generation EEW systems should incorporate engineering-based, application-specific models and tools for more effective risk communication. They should operate within robust probabilistic frameworks that explicitly quantify uncertainties at each stage of the analysis to enable more informed stakeholder decision-making. These types of advancements in EEW systems would represent an important paradigm shift in current approaches to issuing early warnings for natural hazards.

Deliverable D3.1 – Part 2 quantitatively assesses the limits and potentials of EEW for various rupture scenarios in Europe. Generally, these are shallow moderate (magnitudes 5 to 6.5) events that occur close (< 30 km) to urban centres, although we also consider the unusual context of the Vrancea region in Romania (see Appendix B), where deep earthquakes occur approximately 150 km from Bucharest. Findings from these analyses represent a baseline at the start of the project, which will be used to judge the effectiveness of TURNkey in improving EEW for European applications. The first part of the study is a simulation-based exercise that uses seismic hazard data, exposure models, event-dependent vulnerability proxies, and a sophisticated travel-time algorithm to probabilistically map EEW feasibility across Europe. We find that Turkey, Italy, and Greece contain the sites with the largest EEW feasibility. The results for Italy and Greece are particularly notable for TURNkey; while neither country has a currently operational EEW system, both contain a TURNkey testbed to be the focus of more detailed analyses for EEW and the target of end-user-orientated applications of the system. The second part of the study explores the performance of popular regional EEW algorithms for European conditions of seismicity and seismic network density, to identify the best context-specific algorithms for location and moment magnitude prediction. We specifically test Probabilistic

and Evolutionary early warning SysTem (*PRESTo*), Earthquake Alarms System (*ElarmS*), *Virtual Seismologist* (original version), and an implementation of the *Virtual Seismologist* magnitude component within *SeiscomP*, *VS(SC)*, which we use jointly with the *scanloc* module for locating events. We first investigate the operational performance of the *PRESTo* and *SeisComP* (using *scanloc* and *VS(SC)*) platforms, to evaluate the timeliness and accuracy of the provided estimates in real-time simulation mode. Then, we focus particularly on algorithmic accuracy, and separately assess the location and magnitude components of *PRESTo*, *ElarmS*, and *Virtual Seismologist*, along with the *scanloc* module for location. We finally illustrate the performance improvement that the best algorithmic combinations for location and magnitude estimation (i.e., *scanloc* + *PRESTo* magnitude component and *scanloc* + *ElarmS* magnitude component) can offer at the decision-making stage of EEW, relative to the original versions of the algorithms. These findings will be used to inform EEW implementation within the TURNkey platform.

2.3 Rapid Response to Earthquake (RRE)

In an RRE context, the main objective pertains to the accurate estimation of the extent and location of incurred losses, within the shortest time possible following the earthquake event. Therefore, many automated tools and systems for damage and loss estimation have been developed and implemented worldwide: Part I of this report conducts a critical review of the most prominent of them. Then, in Part II, some elements of the technical solution considered for the TURNkey platform are tested on real-life applications.

In Part I, the review of current RRE systems hinges on two distinct aspects, namely (i) the generation of shake-maps (i.e., updated spatial field of ground-motion parameters) and (ii) the estimation of damage or losses, based on the estimated level of shaking and the exposure and vulnerability models for the affected area. The algorithms behind the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) ShakeMap[®] procedure (both versions v3.5 and v4.0) are detailed and compared to another shake-map approach, which is based on correlated Gaussian fields that are assembled in a Bayesian Network (BN). The USGS ShakeMap[®] v4.0 and the Bayesian approach provide identical results: the ShakeMap[®] v4.0 procedure is much faster (i.e., quicker estimation of the level of shaking), however, it appears that the Bayesian approach is more flexible (i.e., possibility to additional variables, or evidence containing uncertainties). Therefore, the latter may be more suited to experimental purposes, in order to integrate diverse sources of field observations, for instance. From the inventory of shake-map systems currently operating worldwide, it appears that most of them are still based on the USGS ShakeMap[®] v3.5 procedure, while an upgrade to version 4.0 would be beneficial in order to obtain more accurate results. Moreover, some existing gaps are related to the soil amplification models used (i.e., most systems are based on first-order approximations, such as the topographic slope model for $V_{s,30}$) and the uneven use of macroseismic testimonies (i.e., the disparity between the *Did You Feel It?* forms used by the various systems).

Then, the review of loss estimation tools has led to the first distinction between systems that link the earthquake event directly to projected losses (usually through simplified empirical relations) and the tools that make use of previously-computed shake-maps. It appears that the systems that provide a fully integrated and automated chain of treatment (detection of the earthquake event -> generation of shake-map -> estimation of damage and losses) are still very sparse: the most notable ones include USGS PAGER, SeisDaRo in Romania, ELER in Istanbul, and SEISAID in France (currently in the project). Moreover, while most systems provide results at the scale of a region or a city (or even

aggregate over the whole event), damage estimations should be carried out at the building block or city district level, in order to guide emergency responders towards the precise areas where disaster relief is the most needed. Another noteworthy observation pertains to the type of exposed assets that are considered in the loss estimation: most systems focus on built areas (i.e., residential buildings), yet emergency responders would also greatly benefit from the knowledge of the performance loss of critical infrastructure systems (e.g., road networks, water and electricity supply systems). Finally, the coupling between shake-maps and loss assessment software (such as SELENA, developed by NORSAR and U. Alicante, or Armagedom, developed by BRGM), is recommended as the technical solution to be adopted by the TURNkey platform.

In Part II, the feasibility of the considered solution is investigated in two case-studies, i.e. the Luchon valley (Pyrenees, Test-Bed 2) and the town of Hveragerði (Iceland, Test-Bed 3):

- In the Pyrenees, shake-maps are coupled with the Armagedom damage assessment tools, in order to propagate uncertainties related to the hazard input (i.e., uncertain estimates from the shake-map) and to investigate the impact of the density of seismic stations on the estimated distribution of damage.

In Iceland, the sensitivity of shake-map outcomes with respect to various hypotheses and modelling assumptions is investigated: the influence of a dense seismic array, the influence of different GMPEs, the influence of different spatial correlation models, the influence of considering the additional uncertainty on observations (i.e., uncertainty on the site terms of the stations). Further developments of GMPEs accounting for area-specific near-fault terms, along with a posterior estimation of site terms for seismic stations, appear to be crucial for the successful implementation of a robust and accurate shake-map system in this area.

3 END-USER EXPECTATIONS AND OPERATIONAL REQUIREMENTS OF THE FWCR PLATFORM: SUMMARY OF FINDINGS FROM TURNKEY WORK PACKAGE 1

The following provides initial input from Work Package 1 (WP1) of the end-user stakeholder expectations and operational considerations of the TURNkey Forecasting - Early Warning - Consequence Prediction and Response (FWCR) Platform that will need to be considered by those developing the technical aspects of the platform. This short section effectively represents the first stage of WP1's 'proxy-client' input into WP2.

3.1 Overview of Work Package 1

The aim of WP1 was to explore the potential socio-economic benefits of OEF, EEW and RRE systems on community resilience to earthquake events across Europe.

To this end, WP1 conducted a critical review of the literature to identify strengths and weaknesses of existing (international) systems which informed a series of interviews and focus groups with international experts and representative end-user stakeholder groups (citizens, emergency responders, critical infrastructure providers and private/public sector business organisations) from the TURNkey project Test Beds (TBs) to identify a series of Europe-focused use-cases. The use-cases highlighted how each of the different stakeholder groups could apply the FWCR Platform to their particular sector. An analysis of the use-cases across sectors identified common expectations of the FWCR Platform along with key operational issues that the FWCR Platform would need to address before the FWCR Platform would find wide acceptance by each of the end-user stakeholder groups. This section summarises these issues to provide guidance on the end-user format that will be required of the technical outputs from the FWCR Platform. Full details of the results from WP1 can be found in Deliverables D1.2-D1.6.

3.2 Potential uses of the FWCR Platform

The initial operational specification of the FWCR Platform (as presented in the TURNkey Grant Agreement) was used as the basis to examine the different end-user stakeholder group's reactions to the FWCR Platform's outputs and to develop a series of high-level use-cases to describe how the stakeholder groups would use the Platform to improve their resilience to an earthquake event. Although there were some differences in detail between the stakeholder groups, their potential use of the FWCR Platform fell into two areas:

1. improved health and safety;
2. improved speed of recovery.

With regards to improved health and safety, there was a clear expectation that the primary role of the FWCR Platform should be to reduce mortality and morbidity as a consequence of an earthquake event and, whilst there were differences between the stakeholder groups on how this could be achieved, there was general agreement of what the FWCR Platform should deliver:

- EEW alerts and action-guidance that an individual (employee or citizen) can use to reduce their risk of injury or death.
- OEF's and actionable guidance that stakeholders can use to better prepare for a potential earthquake event.

- RRE that can capture and interrogate information received from those responding to an earthquake event to improve their post-event critical response planning to reflect the real situation on the ground. This would include greater awareness of the specific danger to first responders, including early notification of aftershocks.

With regards to improved speed of recovery there was a clear expectation that the primary role of the FWCR Platform should be to minimise disruption to critical systems/components and enable rapid and effective enaction of disaster management and resilience plans:

- EEW alerts that support autonomous or semiautonomous control of critical systems switching them to a fail-safe mode where possible or suspending critical operations until ground shaking ceases.
- OEF integrated into disaster management and resilience plans to allow pre-event actions that minimise damage to critical systems and post-earthquake repair (recovery) time. These actions would not only apply to the primary stakeholders but also to their upstream and downstream supply chains/communication channels.
- RRE information to allow faster mobilisation of first responders and disaster management resources, including better interaction between all those involved in post-disaster recovery and full integration with existing command and control systems.

3.3 End-user performance requirements the FWCR Platform

In addition to identifying potential uses of the FWCR Platform, end-users also identified the performance requirements they would have of the FWCR Platform. The performance requirements fell into three categories:

- Technical requirements
 - metrics and models must be complete, transparent (including uncertainties) and timely;
 - outputs must include guidance on how the metrics and models can be integrated into decision-making models.
- Functional requirements
 - systems must be robust and reliable and continue to operate during an earthquake event;
 - must contain output metrics that can be customised to reflect the different needs of the end-user, including attitudes towards risk and upstream and downstream supply chains;
 - contain applications and guidance that directly relate to critical stakeholder processes and systems including implications of false-positive and false-negative forecasts and warnings on the stakeholders critical success factors;
 - compatible with existing disaster management and resilience planning systems and not be an additional channel of information.
- Governance requirements
 - operate within a fair and equitable governance framework and be compliant with local legal, statutory and regulatory requirements;
 - be supported by a business model that guarantees the long term operation and maintenance of the FWCR Platform;

- must be secure with all personal data protected and confidentiality guaranteed;
- be free at the point of use to all stakeholders.

The functional requirements need to be addressed alongside the development of the technical solutions in WP3, WP4 and WP5 as part of the process of operationalising the FWCR conceptual model to be tested with end-user stakeholders in WP2. The governance requirements need to be addressed alongside the development of the FWCR user-interface in WP6 and business models in WP7.

3.4 Operational considerations for the FWCR Platform from an end-user perspective

From an end-user stakeholder perspective the outputs from the FWCR Platform need to be in the form of data, metrics and models that support better stakeholder decision making to improve resilience (both stakeholder and community) to an earthquake event. Table 1 presents an analysis of the key operational issues identified in WP1 that need to be considered by WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 when developing their technical solutions to operationalise the FWCR Platform.

Table 1: Key operational considerations for the FWCR Platform.

Key operational issues with OEF	
Level of forecast	Need clarity on the level of the forecast, e.g. in terms of thresholds and timescales that can be achieved in the forecasts.
The granularity of forecast (geographical scales)	Need clarity on how geolocation-sensitive the forecasts are. Need to define the level of detail that can be provided by the Platform, e.g. -can a range of forecasts be issued at different levels of certainty/reliability? - can a range of ground shaking forecasts be issued at different levels of certainty?
Transmission of warning (push, pull, both)	Need clarity on transmission protocols for end-users, e.g. - can the FWRC Platform push data to stakeholders/organisations so as to allow them to translate the ground shaking forecasts into critical actions (e.g. for specific locations or assets)? - does the FWRC Platform know the location of stakeholder/organisation critical assets (built or human) and as such can 'push' critical asset-specific risks to the stakeholder/organisation? - can end-users pull detailed forecasts from the FWRC Platform against their specific risk requirements* *Example: "show me all of my assets that have a greater than X% likelihood of being affected by a Y intensity earthquake in the next 48 hours" (X and Y would be derived from stakeholder/organisation risk assessments of the vulnerability and resilience of individual critical systems/assets)
All clear	How will the end-user know the forecast has returned to the lowest risk state?

Reliability	How reliable will the forecasts be and how will this reliability be translated into a language that non-technical users can understand?
Impact OEF on operational models	How are forecasts integrated into disaster management and business continuity plans? How and where will impacts on critical processes/actions be modelled?
Link ground shaking to stakeholder/organisation and community impact	How are forecasts translated into ground shaking and then into impact on stakeholder systems? How are impacts on individual stakeholder systems integrated into community resilience models?
Cost	Will the system be free like the weather forecast or will end-users be charged for it?
Integration with existing systems	How will alerts integrate with existing warning and security systems, e.g. - for push / pull notifications how does FWRC Platform interface with the stakeholders/organisation's IT systems? - how does it affect security issues (e.g. firewalls, fire alarms)?
Transmission of warning (direct or via the third party)	Does the FWRC Platform work through third-party providers to supply OEFs? If so, what would the business model look like for such a system?
Technical support	What technical support would the FWRC Platform provide to organisations/third-party providers to technically integrate the FWRC Platform OEFs into their disaster management plans?
Key operational issues with EEW	
Granularity of warning	Need to define the level of detail that can be provided by the alerts, e.g. - strength of ground shaking - can a range of times to a given location be given with associated measures of reliability?
Transmission of warning (push, pull, both)	Need clarity on transmission protocols for end-users, e.g. - can FWRC Platform push data to stakeholders/organisations so as to allow them to interpolate the timescale for each critical asset or process? - does the FWRC Platform know the location of a stakeholder/organisation's critical assets (built or human) and as such, can 'push' critical asset-specific risks to the stakeholder/organisation?
Transmission of warning (direct or via the third party)	How would direct warnings - and those delivered via third parties - affect the end-user's operational models? - would the FWRC Platform provide a series of end-user alarms linked directly to the FWRC Platform? If so, what would the business model look like for such a system? - would the FWRC Platform work through third-party providers to supply end-user alarms linked to the FWRC Platform? If so, what would the business model look like for such a system? Would this model reduce the time aspect of the alert?

Technical support	What technical support would the FWRC Platform provide to organisations/third-party providers to technically integrate the FWRC Platform EEW alerts into their disaster management plans?
All clear alerts	How will the end-user know ground shaking has passed?
Integration with existing systems	How will alerts integrate with existing warning and security systems, e.g. - for push notifications, how does the FWRC Platform interface with the organisation's IT systems? - how does it affect security issues (e.g. firewalls, fire alarms)?
Impact EEW on operational models	How are alerts integrated into disaster management, business continuity and recovery plans? How and where will impacts on operational processes be modelled?
Cost	Will the system be free like the weather forecast or will customers be charged for it?
How reliable will the warnings be?	
How much warning can be given? Is this location specific?	
Key operational issues with RRE	
Communication to first responders	Need a user-friendly dashboard (Earthquake Cockpit Situation Report) to present a range of information from multiple sources to first responder command and control, e.g. - what specific information will the dashboard present? - will the end-user be able to drill down through the dashboard? - will the end-user be able to write their own reports in the dashboard? - will there be the facility for two-way communication between headquarters and field units?
Updating with real-time post-earthquake data	How will real-time updating of data be managed within the FWRC Platform, e.g. - how will data be validated? - how will data be maintained (e.g. if conditions change due to after-shocks etc.)? - who will be permitted to upload data? - who will be legally responsible for the accuracy of the data?

The issues identified in Table 1 will be addressed as part of the participatory action research methodology where researchers from WP1 will act as 'proxy-clients' to present the operational needs of the different end-user stakeholders to researchers from WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 as the FWCR Platform is planned, developed, tested and reviewed over the remainder of the TURNkey project.

4 CURRENT SITUATION OF OEF SYSTEMS OPERATING IN EUROPE

4.1 Summary

The concept of Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF) is illustrated in this section. OEF includes the dissemination of authoritative information about time-dependent earthquake probabilities over time scales of hours to decades to inform the decisions that people, organizations and stakeholders make to mitigate or manage seismic risk (Field et al. 2016). The term “operational” is used to emphasise the importance of providing scientific information about the well-formatted hazard time-span that is authoritative and timely (Marzocchi et al. 2014). First, the concept of OEF is described. Subsequently, different algorithms are discussed, and finally, experiences from different countries are presented.

4.2 OEF at a glance among other natural hazards

Natural hazards are physical events that are usually (rapid or slow) time-dependent phenomena, and they can be illustrated by geophysical, hydrological, climatological, meteorological, or biological understandings. Earthquakes are one of the natural hazards and are placed in the top ten deadliest natural disasters in history. Humans are now capable of triggering warnings to stakeholders and the public for most natural hazards. However, as seen in Figure 1, for some of the natural hazards, this warning is quite close to the event origin time and for other cases, it is hours or days before the event. Weather and climate forecasting is one tangible example that may produce warnings days or weeks before the event; however, in the case of an earthquake, early warning systems can provide at best only a few seconds up to minutes before the strong ground motions arrive at a site of interest.

The relationship between the short-term probability of a hazardous event occurring and the time-scale of forecasts is shown in Figure 1 in order to illustrate how OEF, EEW and RRE perform compared to other perils. OEF is dealing with lower probabilities than warnings for floods etc. and EEW and RRE are dealing with shorter time-scales either side of the event. On the other hand, OEF is able to provide warnings hours or days before an earthquake, but with a higher level of uncertainty. This large OEF uncertainty results in a trade-off between triggering a decision and the level of uncertainty. Therefore, most of the experts in this field are of the opinion that OEF results should be part of an advisory framework for the relevant civil protection authorities and decisions should not be taken by seismologists.

Figure 1: The relationship between the short-term probability of a hazardous event and the time-scale of forecasts.

4.2.1 Short-term OEF

On short time scales of days and weeks, earthquake sequences show clustering in space and time, as indicated by the aftershocks triggered by large events. Statistical descriptions of clustering explain many features observed in seismicity catalogues, and they can be used to construct forecasts that indicate how earthquake probabilities change over the short term.

The short-term earthquake probability (STEP) model by Gerstenberger et al. (2005) added spatial information and hazard to the Reasenber and Jones (1989, 1994) model. In 2005, the USGS produced a STEP aftershock forecasting web service for California but discontinued these postings in 2010 due to maintenance issues (Field et al. 2016). STEP uses aftershock statistics to make hourly revisions of the probabilities of strong ground motions (Modified Mercalli Intensity \geq VI) on a 10-km, state-wide grid (Jordan and Jones, 2010). In the first version of the STEP model, the probability changes that resulted from a particular earthquake did not depend on the proximity of that earthquake to major faults (Gerstenberger et al., 2005). The new version incorporates the short-term fault-based earthquake forecasting into the Uniform California Earthquake Rupture Forecast (UCERF3). Improving OEF capabilities is an identified strategic goal of the USGS (Holmes et al. 2012) with two current foci. The first effort is to automate the Reasenber and Jones process for regions outside of California. The second effort involves combining the epidemic type aftershock sequence (ETAS) model (Ogata 1988), which takes into account secondary aftershock sequences, with long-term earthquake probabilities (Field et al. 2016).

A combination of the short- and long-term forecasts was firstly done with the foreshock model of Agnew and Jones (1991), but that model was limited to forecasting only the largest events (Michael

2012). These efforts have been endorsed by the National Earthquake Prediction Evaluation Council (NEPEC), which advises the USGS on earthquake prediction research priorities (Field et al. 2016).

The recent experiences and current capabilities of OEF in Italy, see Marzocchi et al. (2014), developed following the 2009 L'Aquila earthquake, and in New Zealand, deployed during the 2010–2011 Canterbury sequence (Gerstenberger et al. 2014) have revealed interesting observations. The Italian system forecasts both event probabilities and ground-motion hazard for various time intervals, based on an ensemble of two ETAS models and a version of the STEP model. OEF in New Zealand has been developed for end-users ranging from the public to government decision-makers. The system combines short-term, medium-term, and long-term models to forecast both event probabilities and ground-motion hazard for time frames of 1 day to 50 years. This hybrid model has been used to inform rebuilding decisions in Christchurch, which was severely damaged during the Darfield/Christchurch aftershock sequences in 2010/2011 and subsequently it has led to an upgrade in New Zealand's building design standards (Field et al. 2016). For more recent events, aftershock scenario earthquakes also have been provided to help end-users interpret the forecasts (Christophersen et al. 2016).

4.2.2 Long-term OEF

Long-term forecasts, which are applicable from decades to centuries, represent OEF's first line of defence for mitigating earthquake risk, primarily by informing building codes (Field et al. 2016). Also, Omori–Utsu based statistical clustering models have demonstrable reliability and predictability concerning short-term triggering and therefore provide a rational basis for short-term and long-term OEFs (Field et al. 2016). However, the primary challenge to usefulness is that triggering models usually estimate a low probability for damaging earthquakes (Jordan et al. 2011). Probability gains may be as high as factors of 1000, but the overall likelihood of triggering damaging events will typically be less than a few per cent. The exceptions are during aftershock sequences of large ($M > 7$) events, when this probability can climb above 10%. Such low-to-moderate probabilities will constitute useful information if the potential consequences of large triggered events are high (Marzocchi et al. 2015). About half of all large damaging earthquakes lack any detectable foreshocks, meaning they will occur without potential warning (Agnew and Jones 1991). OEF can also produce high-probability forecasts for smaller aftershocks that are felt but cause little damage; understanding that such events are to be expected can be reassuring in the aftermath of a massive earthquake (Wein and Becker 2013).

4.2.3 Decision-making in OEF

Decisions to undertake mitigation actions based on OEF information depend on the balance between costs and benefits, which are specific to the risk at hand (Field et al. 2016). Because these decisions are contingent on a host of economic, political and psychological considerations that lie beyond the science of hazard analysis, scientific information about future earthquake activity should be developed independently of any specific risk assessment or mitigation effort (Field et al. 2016). Moreover, all validated OEF information should be made available to all potential end-users in an appropriate well-formatted and timely manner. These principles of hazard-risk separation and transparency imply that seismologists should provide potential end-users with complete, probabilistic forecasts, including the epistemic uncertainties (Jordan et al. 2014). The OEF systems should be policy-neutral. In other words, OEF systems should not involve decisions to withhold information until some activity or probability threshold is exceeded, or until a “significant” mainshock has occurred, since doing so would not only imply that we know how to define these things for all

potential users, but would also effectively put scientists in the inappropriate role of making policy decisions (Field et al. 2016). Recent events have revealed the public's hunger for OEF information during active earthquake sequences. It is well known that information vacuums invite unfounded predictions and misinformation (Mileti and Peek 2000), such as the rumours on Twitter that "experts are holding back on a prediction to avoid panic" within hours of the 2010 El Mayor–Cucapah earthquake (Jordan and Jones 2010). The level of apparent certainty provided by amateur predictors can also be particularly attractive and therefore distracting (Marzocchi 2012). The infamous L'Aquila trial, in which seven Italian officials were charged with involuntary manslaughter, was at least partly a consequence of miscommunications about earthquake risk by the Italian Department of Civil Protection (Field et al. 2016). That agency convened its Grand Risk Commission before the L'Aquila earthquake to address ill-founded earthquake predictions that were worrying the public during the active seismic sequence preceding the L'Aquila mainshock. Still, it lacked the operational capabilities to accurately assess and report the evolving seismic hazard (Marzocchi 2012). The best solution in such predicaments is to have an OEF system that produces authoritative and scientific information (Jordan 2013; Jordan et al. 2011).

The probability from a time-dependent forecast relative to the time-independent probability, produced by short-term forecasting models, can be quite high (>100). In these situations, the forecasting intervals are typically much shorter than the recurrence intervals of large earthquakes (days compared to hundreds of years), and the probability of potentially damaging earthquake remains much less than unity ($< 1\%$ per day). As a result, although the value of long-term forecasts for ensuring seismic safety is clear, the interpretation of short-term forecasts is problematic, because earthquake probabilities may vary over orders of magnitude. Still, short-term OEF cannot provide high probability earthquake predictions. Translating such low-probability forecasts into effective decision-making is a difficult challenge. Therefore, it is necessary to establish an earthquake probability threshold with respect to mitigation actions by means of a cost-benefit analysis, as well as to take psychological preparedness and resilience into consideration. Alert procedures should be standardized to facilitate decisions at different levels of government and among the public if necessary. Moreover, the principles of effective public communication established by social science research should be applied to the delivery of seismic hazard information (Jordan et al., 2011). It is worth emphasising that due to high uncertainty in the probability gains, the quality of all operational models should be evaluated for reliability and skill by retrospective testing. They should also be under continuous prospective testing against established long-term forecasts and alternative time-dependent models (Jordan et al., 2011).

4.2.4 Summary of warning systems for other hazards and lessons learnt for OEF

The purpose of this section is, firstly, to briefly summarise the choices made in early warning systems for natural hazards other than earthquakes and, secondly, to learn lessons from these systems for the development of operational earthquake forecasting and earthquake early warning. In the future, the system being developed in TURNkey should be compatible with early warning systems for other hazards. Therefore, any similarities or differences among the TURNkey system for earthquakes and those systems need to be identified and addressed to ensure compatibility.

If hazards such as crime and diseases are excluded (as these are too different from earthquakes for there to be potential similarities and often they would not be considered as a "natural hazard"), then the number of different types of natural hazards equals about twenty, e.g. Gill and Malamud (2014).

The authors summarise the spatial and temporal scales as shown in Figure 2. The figure demonstrates that major earthquakes have short temporal scales (seconds or a few minutes), but can have a large spatial extent (many thousands of km²). Excluding hazards that occur over temporal scales over many months (local subsidence and heave, regional subsidence and uplift, drought and long-term climatic change) as well as ground collapses that have very small spatial scales still leaves a number of hazards that could be considered within a comparison of early warning systems. Because of their analogous spatial and temporal scales, the most similar hazards are: tsunami, snow avalanche, landslide, volcanic eruption (all associated perils) and wildfire. Hence, these are first priority for this summary and comparison. A second priority is constituted by flood (particularly local flash floods), hail/snow/lightning/thunder-storm, tropical cyclone and short-term climate change. Terrorism is also briefly considered here as there are clear warning levels.

Group	Hazard	References
Geophysical	Earthquake	Dixon [1991]; Ilk et al. [2005]; Minster [2013]
	Tsunami	Chelton [2001]; Ilk et al. [2005]
	Volcanic Eruption	Dixon [1991]; Ilk et al. [2005]
	Landslide	Waugh [2000]; Malamud et al. [2004]; Winter et al. [2005]
	Snow Avalanche	Waugh [2000]; Winter et al. [2005]; Lemke et al. [2007]
Hydrological	Flood	Hirschboeck [1988]
	Drought	Edwards [1999]
Shallow Earth Processes	Regional Subsidence and Uplift	---
	Local Subsidence and Heave	---
Atmospheric	Ground Collapse	Cooper [1998]
	Tropical Cyclone	Edwards [1999]; Greci and Nese [2006]; Laing and Evans [2011]; Hirschboeck [1988]
	Tornado	Grenci and Nese [2006]; Laing and Evans [2011]
	Hail, Snow, Lightning, Thunder Storm	Edwards [1999]; Greci and Nese [2006]; Laing and Evans [2011]; Hirschboeck [1988]
	Long-Term Climatic Change	Edwards [1999]; Chelton [2001]; Laing and Evans [2011]
Biophysical	Short-Term Climatic Change	Chelton [2001]; Laing and Evans [2011]; Hirschboeck [1988]
	Wildfire	Malamud et al. [1998]; Hincks et al. [2013]

Figure 2: A summary of the spatial and temporal scales for different types of natural hazards (Gill and Malamud 2014).

This section is divided into a number of subsections covering different choices that need to be made when developing a warning system. In each subsection, we summarise the choices made for systems for alternative hazards. Because of the ready availability of public information in English and because

warning systems are well developed and publicly available for some of the considered hazards, the examples are mostly taken from the UK and the USA. Some specific elements are collected from other countries, including France. Following these subsections, there is a subsection listing the suggestions for the design of the TURNkey OEF and EEW systems derived from the knowledge of existing systems for other hazards. In Appendix A, a summary of each of the systems studied is provided.

4.2.4.1 *How many warning levels are considered?*

All of the warning systems considered have either four or five levels of alerts, including a base level which means there is no warning in operation. Sometimes (e.g. French hurricane warnings for the Caribbean) there is a further alert level that indicates that the threat has passed its peak and is decreasing, but people should still be aware.

4.2.4.2 *What words are used to describe the different warning levels?*

The names used to describe the different levels are simple and comprise only one or two words. Some systems try to convey the action within the names used, e.g., “watch” used by the US’s volcano and tsunami systems. For the UK’s flood hazard, there is a difference between an “alert”, where only preparation is recommended and a “warning”, where immediate action is recommended.

4.2.4.3 *What colours/symbols are used to identify the different warning levels?*

The colours used for the different levels are typically: green or grey for no warning, yellow for low warning level, orange for moderate warning level and red for high warning level. Sometimes (e.g. UK’s immediate risk of flooding service) use symbols like road traffic signs to illustrate the potential

effects graphically, e.g. = severe flood warning.

4.2.4.4 *How are warning levels defined?*

From the publicly available information, the warning levels and the probabilities of the effects, forecasts appear to be based on expert judgement rather than precise definitions. It is possible, however, that there are technical documents that provide more information, but these do not seem to have been published. The impacts of the event are defined using qualitative terms such as “moderate impact” (UK’s weather warnings) and “significant risk to life” (UK’s 5-day flood risk), which also shows that they are often expressed in terms of risk rather than a hazard. An exception is the US tsunami warnings that use the forecasted and observed wave height (a hazard measure rather than a risk measure) to define the advisory and warning levels. The likelihood of the event is also always defined in qualitative terms, at least to the public, through phrases such as “is possible” (UK’s 5-day flood risk) and “very likely” (UK’s weather warnings). It is possible that an estimate of the probability of an event is converted by the providers of the warning to a qualitative statement to avoid the appearance of over-precision (e.g. if the probability is greater than X, this means “very likely”, whereas a probability of less than Y means “is possible”). The most sophisticated approach surveyed is the UK’s weather warnings that are defined using a risk-impact matrix accounting for both the impact and likelihood of occurrence.

4.2.4.5 Are the warnings used to trigger actions and if so, how?

Most of the systems provide a link to a small set of recommended actions for the public (e.g. UK's immediate flood warnings). The warnings in some cases are explicitly used by the public authorities to initiate actions (e.g. the UK's fire severity index level 5 that is used to prevent access to some land). Other actions are probably triggered by different stakeholders when higher warning levels occur, for example, high bridges may be shut when weather warnings are in place (e.g. <https://trafficscotland.org/bridgerestrictions/>).

4.2.4.6 Who is the audience for the warnings?

All the systems investigated have a version that the public can use, and some of the systems (e.g. UK's weather and flood systems) are particularly easy to use and visually attractive. It is likely that public authorities have access to more detailed information.

4.2.4.7 Who is responsible for the warnings?

Public authorities (e.g. the UK's Environment Agency or the Met Office) are responsible for the warnings in all cases.

4.2.4.8 How is the warning calculated?

For some hazards (e.g. short-term flooding) observations (e.g. of river levels) are extrapolated to estimate the chance of an event whereas for others (e.g. weather) the warnings are based on modelling. This depends on the available lead-time and predictability of the hazard. Warnings are often given for rather broad geographical areas (e.g. at county scale) rather than very specific locations. More geographically-specific warnings may give a false impression of precision and also are more likely to prove incorrect.

4.2.4.9 How are the warnings provided?

The warnings are available on the websites of the issuing authority. The warning systems often allow users to subscribe to alerts via email, text or phone. Some provide alerts by an app (e.g. UK's weather warnings) or RSS and other means (e.g. audible alarm in the case of the US's tsunami system). In the case of UK weather warnings, these are broadcast by television and radio and reissued on news providers websites (e.g. on the BBC weather pages).

4.2.4.10 How long before the potentially damaging event are warnings issued?

Some systems provide a long-term hazard level (e.g. UK's terrorism system) with warnings in place for an indefinite period. The warning times provided for some hazards are not precisely defined due to the nature of the phenomenon (e.g. the US's volcano system). Other systems generally provide warnings for the coming hours (e.g. UK's immediate flooding) up to a week (e.g. UK's weather warnings), although they are regularly updated.

4.2.4.11 Lessons learned for OEF and EEW

Designing future OEF and EEW systems as similarly as possible to existing well-established warning systems for other hazards would be advantageous as targeted audiences will be familiar with those systems and hence, they will be more readily accepted. Therefore, lessons that can be learned from these existing systems are summarised in this concluding section. This will help to justify the choices

made for the proposed OEF and EEW systems of TURNkey. These design choices will be considered in the following tasks within TURNkey, particularly task 3.5.

Suggestions for the design of the TURNkey OEF and EEW systems include the following:

- use a maximum of five warning levels;
- use simple vocabulary to describe the warning levels;
- use standard colours (e.g. green, yellow, orange and red) for the warning levels (although care should be taken so that the colours are distinguishable for colourblind people);
- consider both impact and likelihood when defining the warning levels;
- do not associate precise numbers to the impact or the likelihood, but use easier to understand general terms;
- do not provide warnings for small geographical areas (e.g. a town) but for larger regions (e.g. counties);
- provide a short list of actions that the public is recommended to take at each level;
- provide warnings up to a week before the potential event (for OEF);
- a respected and approved public authority should issue the warnings;
- provide many means for the public to obtain the warnings;
- consider having a category for “warning no longer in force”, once the seismic hazard has reduced to its background level; and
- use historical events to calibrate the warning levels and make sure that the highest warning level is triggered for the largest historical event.

4.3 OEF Algorithms

Most of the OEF algorithms have been introduced to provide a platform for seismicity-based earthquake forecasting. A wide variety of techniques are now available that use physical assumptions or statistical approaches; however, all of them try to re-produce the statistics and characteristics of both the historical and instrumental seismic records. Comparison of the methods suggests that while smoothed seismicity models provide improved forecast capabilities over longer time periods, higher probability gain over shorter time periods is achieved with methods that integrate statistical techniques including the knowledge on the physical process, such as ETAS models or those related to changes in b-value. The available algorithms are divided into two general categories, i.e. physical process models (Table 2) and smoothed seismicity models (Table 3) (Tiampo and Shcherbakov 2012). The classification in section 2.3 as well as Tables 1 and 2 are mainly based on the work by Tiampo and Shcherbakov (2012).

4.3.1 Physical process models

Physical models are “those in which the precursory process relies on one or more physical mechanisms or phenomena associated with the generation of large events”; this is a direct quotation from Tiampo and Shcherbakov (2012). A detailed analysis, often but not always statistical, is performed on the instrumental or historical seismicity or both in order to isolate those precursors. These techniques are based on the assumption that the seismicity is acting as a sensor for the underlying physical process and can provide information about the spatial and temporal nature of that process. It should be noted that, while the classification of a physical, and potentially verifiable,

source for the earthquake generation process is an attractive feature of these methodologies, differentiating between both the source and the subtly varying seismic phenomena is difficult. As a result, many of these techniques rely on pattern recognition or statistical methodologies to isolate the spatio-temporal signal. A comprehensive understanding of their relative successes and failures is often obscured by the complicated nature of the analyses, the simplifying assumptions of the physical models, and the heterogeneities that exist in the real earth. Here we discuss those physical process models that have had the most significant impact on the field and are part of ongoing forecasting research that employs high-quality catalogues from active seismic regions (Tiampo and Shcherbakov 2012).

Table 2: Physical process models. These descriptions are generally abbreviated direct quotations from Tiampo and Shcherbakov (2012).

Model Name	Brief description
Acceleration Moment Release (AMR)	Precursory seismic activation, or foreshock activity, has been observed before a number of large events around the world (Bakun et al. 2005; Jones and Molnar 1979; Sykes and Jaumé 1990; Jordan and Jones 2010). The most widely applied method for analyzing these precursory increases in seismicity has been known as time-to-failure analysis, accelerating seismic moment release (ASMR), or accelerating moment release (AMR) (Ben-Zion and Lyakhovsky 2002; Bowman and King 2001; Bowman et al. 1998; Brehm and Braile 1998; Gross 1998; Jaumé and Sykes 1999; Mignan 2008; Robinson 2000; Turcotte, Newman, and Shcherbakov 2003). It uses only a relatively small fraction of the instrumental catalogue in its analysis, and its forecast time periods are poorly defined and often long-term. A more complete discussion of the history and theory of AMR can be found in Mignan (2011).
Characteristic earthquakes	Elastic rebound theory hypothesizes that a large earthquake releases most of its accumulated stress on a given fault segment and that the next earthquake occurs after the stress builds up until it is restored to a level that results in rupture again. Here, the characteristic earthquake model assumes that faults tend to generate earthquakes of the same size over a very narrow range of magnitudes on rupture zones or segments that are similar in location and spatial extent (Parsons and Geist 2009; Wesnousky 1994; Schwartz and Coppersmith 1984). The hypothesis leads to forecasts of specific events on the size of the rupture dimension of the largest earthquakes (~M6.5–9). The model is appealing because it fits historical and empirical observations at the most basic level, i.e. large earthquakes tend to occur where they have occurred in the past (Allen 1968; Davison and Scholz 1986; Petersen et al. 2010; Kafka 2002; Petersen et al. 2007).
Variation in b-value	Variations in the b-value, or slope of the GR frequency–magnitude distribution relation for earthquakes, have been studied intensively over the past thirty years (Cao et al. 1996; Frohlich and Davis 1993; Gerstenberger et al. 2001; Gutenberg et al. 1945; Imoto 1991; Ogata and Katsura 1993; Schorlemmer et al. 2004; Wiemer and Benoit 1996; Wiemer and Schorlemmer 2007; Wiemer and Wyss 1997; Wiemer et al. 1998; Wyss and Wiemer 2000). The b-value is highly heterogeneous in both space and time and on a wide variety of scales (Schorlemmer et al. 2004; Wiemer and Schorlemmer 2007; Wiemer and Wyss 2002). These variations have important implications for earthquake hazard, because local and regional probabilistic seismic hazard assessment is commonly

	<p>performed using the Gutenberg-Richter frequency–magnitude distribution, particularly in areas of dispersed seismicity (Field 2007; Wiemer and Schorlemmer 2007; Wiemer et al. 2009). Recent work on regional b-values has resulted in two crucial conclusions. First, the b-value varies with fault mechanism. The b-value for thrust events is the smallest (~0.7), while that of strike-slip events is intermediate (~0.9), and it is greatest for normal events (~1.1). This relationship is inversely proportional to the mean stress in each regime (Schorlemmer et al. 2005). Gulia and Wiemer (2010) confirmed this result for regional seismicity in Italy. Second, related research suggests that locked patches on faults, or asperities, are characterized by low b-values, while creeping faults have higher b-values (Schorlemmer et al. 2004; Wiemer and Wyss 1994; Wiemer and Wyss 1997; 2002). Taken together, this suggests that the change in b-value can be used as a stress sensor, locating areas of high or low-stress accumulation, particularly toward the end of the seismic cycle, and quantify it in a regional earthquake forecasting model (Gulia and Wiemer 2010; Latchman et al. 2008; Schorlemmer et al. 2005). This hypothesis is supported by laboratory results for acoustic emissions. Stress intensity is proportional to effective stress (Sammonds et al. 1992) and the square root of the length of the nucleating fracture, such that heterogeneous materials tend to be tougher, confirming the relationship between stress, heterogeneity and b-value. Many of the above references discuss increased seismic hazard associated with lower b-values (Westerhaus et al. 2002) and formulate postdicted maps of b-value variations for large events. However, recent work has focused on formulating prospective probabilistic forecasts using b-value variations. Schorlemmer et al. (2005) studied b-value variations along the Parkfield segment of the San Andreas fault, and produced retrospective five-year periods by extrapolating the GR distribution with spatially varying b-values over small volumes. Wiemer and Schorlemmer (2007) developed the Asperity-based Likelihood Model (ALM) for California and provided it to the RELM forecast testing site. In this version, they analyse the seismic catalogue for California for the minimum magnitude of completeness and a depth of 30 km. Gulia et al. (2010) provided an ALM forecast for Italy to the Collaboratory for the Study of Earthquake Predictability (CSEP).</p>
<p>The M8 family of algorithms</p>	<p>The M8 algorithm (Keilis-Borok and Kossobokov 1990; Keilis-Borok et al. 1990; Kossobokov 2006; Kossobokov et al. 1999; 2000; Latoussakis and Kossobokov 1990; Peresan et al. 2005) was developed approximately thirty years ago to locate regions of heightened earthquake occurrence probability in both space and time. The current algorithm calculates sevendime series from smaller earthquakes, ~M4, for a specified region of investigation that is a function of the size of the earthquake that is to be forecast. The values from these time series are used to make a decision on whether to invoke a “Time of Increased Probability”, or TIP, for a larger event of approximately M6.5–8 (Kossobokov et al. 1999). The M8 algorithm generally involves a forecast for relatively large areas of approximately five times the rupture dimension, or from hundreds to more than one thousand kilometres, and from six months to five years into the future (Kossobokov 2006). Predictions are calculated for earthquakes of magnitude M0 and above in interval steps of 0.5. The region is scanned using overlapping circles with a diameter</p>

	<p>directly related to seismic moment(384 km, 560 km, 854 km and 1333 km for M6.5, M7.0, M7.5 and M8, respectively). Time series for earthquake sequences within each circle are calculated and then normalized by the lower magnitude cut-off. Several running averages are computed for the sequence in sliding time windows, typically six months, which characterize earthquake intensity and its deviation from the average as well as seismicity clustering.</p>
Region–Time–Length (RTL)	<p>The RTL is a statistical method in which three earthquake-related parameters (time, place and magnitude) are included in a weighted coefficient (Sobolev and Tyupkin 1997; 1999). The algorithm combines the distance, time and rupture length of clustered seismicity into a combined measure. The designation of RTL arises from Region (epicentral distance), Time interval, and Length (rupture size or magnitude). The RTL algorithm is a statistical method for investigating seismicity changes prior to large events. These changes occur over regions on the order of 100 km, and a few years prior to a large event (Mignan and Giovambattista 2008).</p>
Load–Unload Response Ratio (LURR)	<p>The LURR originally was proposed to measure the seismic energy change in the months and years prior to a large event so that it might be used as an earthquake predictor (Yin et al. 1995). The physical idea is that when the crust is close to instability, more energy is released in the tides' loading period than in the unloading period. If one could measure the ratio between known periods of loading and unloading, then a measure could be derived that pinpointed times and locations of high energy release as a potential precursor. Although the earthquake triggering capability of tidal forces remains controversial, studies have suggested that it is a measurable effect, at least in certain regions. Certainly, tidal strains are expected to affect large areas of Earth's crust (Cochran et al. 2004; Lockner and Beeler 1999; Rydelek et al. 1992; Smith and Sammis 2004; Tanaka 2010; Tanaka et al. 2002; Vidale et al. 1998). In the case of LURR, the cyclic nature of the tidal stresses are hypothesized, to impose loading and unloading on the crust that corresponds to positive and negative tidal Coulomb Failure Stresses (CFS). In LURR, loading and unloading periods are identified based on earth tide-induced perturbations in the CFS on optimally oriented faults (Feng et al. 2008; Mora et al. 2002; Peng et al. 2006; Wang et al. 2004; Yin and Mora 2006; Yin et al. 1995; 2000; 2006; 2008; Yin et al. 2010; Yu and Zhu 2010; Yu et al. 2006; Zhang et al. 2004; Zhang et al. 2006; Zhang, et al. 2010).</p>
Pattern Information (PI) index	<p>The PI index is an analytical method for quantifying the spatio-temporal seismicity rate changes in historic seismicity (Holliday et al. 2006; Rundle et al. 2002; Tiampo et al. 2002). Practically, the method is an objective measure of the local change in seismicity relative to the long-term background seismicity that has been used to forecast large earthquakes. The method identifies spatio-temporal patterns of anomalous activation or quiescence that serve as proxies for changes in the underlying stress that may precede large earthquakes. As a result, these anomalies can be related to the location of large earthquakes that occur in the years following their formation (Tiampo et al. 2002; 2006). Again, the theory suggests that these seismicity structures are related to changes in the underlying stress level (Dieterich 1994; Tiampo et al. 2006; Stein, and Sagiya 2002). The PI index is calculated using instrumental catalogue data from seismically active areas.</p>

4.3.2 Smoothed seismicity models

Smoothed seismicity models are “a more general class of seismicity-based forecasting models which define the essential physical spatio-temporal features of earthquake processes, characterize these features in a mathematical and/or probabilistic manner, and then calibrate the model based on data available from seismic catalogues for particular tectonic regions”; this is a direct quotation from Tiampo and Shcherbakov (2012). The smoothed seismicity approach, originally developed by Frankel (1995), has been extended to many different algorithms and regions around the world (Helmstetter et al. 2006; 2007; Kafka 2002; Kagan and Jackson 2000; Kagan et al. 2007; Nanjo 2010; Rhoades and Evison 2004; Stirling et al. 2002). Smoothed models can be formulated to account for the clustering that exists in natural seismicity as a result of the spatial and temporal correlations between events that arise because of stress transfer interactions (Stein et al. 1994). Also, while actual earthquake catalogue data are often limited by the short time periods available for recorded data, particularly at smaller magnitudes, spatial smoothing can compensate for this lack of data as well as for errors in the data, such as those in magnitude or location (Nanjo 2010; Werner and Sornette 2008).

Over the past ten years, significant progress has been made in developing methods to characterize the physical processes related to seismicity generation in this class of models. Note that a number of techniques have been adapted to short-term forecasting on the order of days, either in addition to or in place of intermediate-term forecasting. Smoothed seismicity models are intuitively attractive because they concentrate seismic hazard in areas that have had earthquakes in the past, a property of seismicity that has been substantiated by several researchers (Allen 1968; Davison and Scholz 1986; Petersen et al. 2010; Kafka 2002). While many versions can be quite complicated, the basic formulation is relatively straightforward, and the results can be easily checked against instrumental catalogue statistics. Virtually all methods can be compared with both random and clustered null hypotheses in a relatively straightforward manner. Many also can evolve in time, potentially monitoring the dynamics of the fault system. Proportional hazard model (PHM) forecasts, for example, currently are recalculated both at regular intervals and as large events occur that modify the ongoing spatio-temporal nature of the seismicity in the region (Faenza and Marzocchi 2010). However, errors or lack of information in the instrumental catalogues can result in significant errors in the resulting forecasts, particularly for large events which have sparse statistics and those areas that have been quiescent in recent memory (Werner and Sornette 2008). Several pattern recognition methodologies, although they may show significant promise, are omitted because they are challenging to implement or are not widely applied to date. These include neural network techniques (Adeli and Panakkat 2009; Alves 2006; Lakshmi and Tiwari 2009), pattern recognition algorithms such as K-means clustering (Morales-Esteban et al. 2010), hidden Markov model methods (Ebel et al. 2007), and cellular automata simulations (Jiménez et al. 2008). The following methodologies are used for ongoing forecasting research in active seismic regions and with high-quality catalogues (Tiampo and Shcherbakov 2012).

Table 3: Smoothed seismicity models. These descriptions are generally abbreviated direct quotations from Tiampo and Shcherbakov (2012).

Model Name	Brief description
Every Earthquake is a Precursor According to Scale (EEPAS)	The EEPAS is based on the precursory scale increase phenomenon, where minor seismicity increases occur before and in the same region as large events in much the same manner as aftershocks. As a result, it is both a physically-based and a smoothed seismicity model but is classified here as the second, because the generated forecasts are intrinsically linked to the distributions associated with each modelled parameter. Originally formulated based upon observations of precursory swarms (Evison and Rhoades 1997; 1999), the idea was extended to the general class of foreshocks to identify localized precursors (Evison and Rhoades 1999; Evison and Rhoades 2002; Evison and Rhoades 2004). The EEPAS stochastic model was formulated based upon the simple idea that every earthquake is a precursor, and that its input into the model is scaled with its magnitude (Rhoades 2010; Rhoades and Evison 2004). The EEPAS model sums contributions to the rate density from past earthquakes based on predictive scaling relations derived from the precursory scale increase phenomenon. The EEPAS model is found to be more informative than a quasi-static baseline model based on proximity to past earthquakes and much more informative than the stationary uniform Poisson model (Rhoades 2011).
Time-independent smoothed seismicity	In 1994, Kagan and Jackson first described a method for developing smoothed seismicity models by extrapolating seismic catalogue information into probabilistic forecasts (Kagan and Jackson 2000). Effectively, this is a time-independent forecast in which rates from historical and instrumental seismic catalogues are spatially smoothed and prorated for particular periods. In the intervening years, this particular method has been applied in the northwest and southwest Pacific (Kagan and Jackson 2000), California (Helmstetter et al. 2006; Kagan et al. 2007), and Italy (Werner et al. 2010).
Epidemic-Type Aftershock Sequence (ETAS)	The original ETAS hypothesis was formulated by Ogata (Ogata 1988; Ogata 1989). Not simply a model of aftershock sequences, ETAS is fundamentally a model of triggered interacting seismicity in which all events have identical roles in the triggering process. Again, it is both a physically-based and a smoothed seismicity model but is classified here as the second, because forecasts are intrinsically linked to the distributions associated with each parameter. In this process every earthquake is regarded as both triggered by earlier events and a potential trigger for subsequent earthquakes, i.e. every event is a potential aftershock, mainshock or foreshock, with its own aftershock sequence. For general seismicity, a background term with a random component is added to the formulation. In the intervening years, the model has been used in many studies to describe the spatio-temporal distribution and features of actual seismicity (Console et al. 2003; Ogata 1998; Helmstetter and Sornette 2002; 2003a; 2003b; Ma and Zhuang 2001; Ogata 1988; Console and Murru 2001; Ogata 1999; 2005; Ogata and Katsura 2006; Saichev and Sornette 2006; Vere-Jones 2006; Zhuang et al. 2004; Zhuang et al. 2005). In general, the ETAS algorithm is used in a branching model, where the parent event of a given magnitude and location produces a series of child events that occur within some specified region and time.

	<p>The average number of children produced for every parent event is the branching ratio (Helmstetter and Sornette 2003). The ETAS model includes the contribution of every previous event based upon the magnitude of the triggering earthquake, the spatial distance from the triggering event, and the time interval between the triggering event and the time of the forecast.</p>
Relative Intensity (RI) method	<p>The RI forecast model was first proposed by Holliday et al. (2005), primarily as a better null hypothesis for forecast testing than a random, nonclustered seismicity model. The idea is to use the rate of occurrence of earthquakes in the past in order to forecast the locations of future large earthquakes, in which future large earthquakes are considered more likely where the higher seismic activity occurred in the past. The RI algorithm is the simplest of smoothed seismicity models and was originally formulated as a binary forecast, although it has been modified in several ways since then.</p>
Simple Smoothed Seismicity model (TripleS)	<p>The TripleS model was developed as a test of a very simple model for earthquake forecasting, with a minimal number of parameters. At its most basic, it applies a Gaussian smoothing filter to a catalogue data set and optimizes a single parameter, σ, which controls the spatial extent of smoothing, against retrospective forecasts (Zechar and Jordan 2010). The simplest smoothed seismicity method is the RI forecast technique. In that model, the smoothing is anisotropic and uniform. TripleS instead applies a two-dimensional isotropic Gaussian smoothing that used a continuous kernel function that allowed for a wider region of influence.</p>
Non-Poissonian earthquake clustering	<p>Most smoothed seismicity models are founded on the idea that earthquakes will tend to occur in the future where they have occurred in the past (Allen 1968; Davison and Scholz 1986; Petersen et al. 2010; Kafka 2002; Petersen et al. 2007). In the case of the short-term non-Poissonian earthquake clustering model, a daily forecasting model submitted to the RELM project by Ebel et al. (2007) was extended on the assumption that the average statistical properties of the spatial and temporal occurrences of earthquakes with $M \geq 4.0$ during the forecast period will be the same as those of the past ~ 70 years, including aftershocks and foreshocks. The initial spatial formulation is based on this premise. Because this is primarily an aftershock forecasting algorithm, the average occurrence rate of aftershocks is modelled using Omori's law (Utsu and Ogata 1995), forming the basis for forecasting activity near the epicentre of a large earthquake immediately following that event. If an earthquake of $M \geq 4.0$ occurs anywhere in the region, a circle of radius R is drawn around the epicentre, as defined by Gardner and Knopoff (1974). In the case of California, the Reasenber and Jones (1989) relation for the Omori law was chosen to calculate the expected rate of earthquakes of $M \geq 4.0$. In addition, the Poisson distribution of inter-event times is the statistical distribution from which short-term forecasts of new mainshocks are derived. The forecast assumes that all events of magnitude smaller than the mainshock are aftershocks. If a new event has a magnitude greater than the first event, the forecast assumes that the first earthquake was a foreshock. When the forecast aftershock/foreshock rate drops below the background mainshock rate for any given location, then the background mainshock rate is substituted. Finally, for those locations that are outside the aftershock zones, the average rate of $M \geq 4$ events for a regional de-clustered earthquake catalogue is calculated, and this mean mainshock rate is</p>

	distributed throughout the entire area proportional to its past distribution (Ebel et al. 2007). Ebel et al. (2007) detail the various forecast choices for any given day and how they are combined into short-term forecasts.
Short-Term Earthquake Probability (STEP)	In 2005, the STEP model was inaugurated by the USGS (Gerstenberger et al. 2005). STEP is a modular approach that uses parameters of Reasenberg and Jones (1989, 1994). It modifies the parameters spatially depending on the real-time seismicity, updating whenever sufficient sequence-specific data are available, thus using the most recent data to update model forecasts. Because the STEP model is based on the Omori law, it is a short-term forecast that produces forecasts on a time scale of days and whose primary signal is related to aftershock sequences, much like the non-Poisson clustering model of Ebel et al. (2007). The STEP model combines a time-independent occurrence model from tectonic fault data with stochastic clustering models whose parameters are derived from long-term and recent catalogue data. The time-independent model is drawn from the 1996 USGS long-term hazard map (Helmstetter et al. 2006). Three stochastic models are calculated for incorporation into the background model: a generic clustering model, a sequence-specific model, and a spatially heterogeneous model (Gerstenberger et al. 2005).
HAZGRIDX	HAZGRIDX, as proposed by Akinici (2010), is another version of a smoothed seismicity model where the Gutenberg-Richter magnitude–frequency relationship governs smoothing. Starting with a seismicity catalogue for Italy that is de-clustered, the minimum magnitude of completeness is determined. Then the seismicity is smoothed using the spatially smoothed seismicity method (Frankel 1995) and the smoothed rate of events in each cell is calculated using the corresponding equation and normalized by the total regional seismicity.
Proportional Hazard Model (PHM)	The Proportional Hazard Model (PHM) is a multivariate nonparametric statistical method that characterizes the temporal dependence of a hazard function that represents the instantaneous conditional probability of an occurrence (Hawkes 1971; Faenza et al. 2003). The model does not assume any a priori statistical distribution of the events and can be used to integrate different kinds of information simultaneously. In this case, it allows for analysis of the earthquake occurrence process without the requirement to assume a model such as the characteristic earthquake distribution. In addition, it allows for testing the impact of the integration of individual pieces of physical information on the event distribution as they are integrated into the model, and test their relative importance (Faenza and Marzocchi 2010). The PHM was applied in studies of the spatio-temporal distribution of destructive earthquakes in Italy (Cinti et al. 2004; Faenza and Pierdominici 2007; Faenza et al. 2003), medium-sized central European earthquakes (Faenza et al. 2009), and large earthquakes worldwide (Faenza et al. 2008), which showed that temporal clustering of events on the order of a few years occurs as a precursory signal prior to large events. Their spatial scale ranges from tens to hundreds of kilometres. Two types of random variables (RV) are considered in this version of PHM, the inter-event time (IET), the time interval between two consecutive events, and the censoring time (CT), the time between the most recent event in the catalogue and the end of the catalogue itself (Faenza and Marzocchi 2010).

4.4 ETAS as a promising OEF system for TURNkey

Among the few spatio-temporal models that have been proposed, only the spatio-temporal ETAS model has been extensively studied in the context of short-term earthquake clustering. Even though its formulation is based on empirical statistics, studies by Console et al. (2007) and Iwata (2013) suggest that the ETAS model is the best model for describing short-term seismicity. According to several studies, e.g. Nandan et al. (2017), the ETAS model ranks among the best models of earthquake forecasting developed to date relative to other models, and it outperforms the physics-based models of seismicity (Nandan et al., 2017). Nonetheless, it fails to account for several key properties of seismicity such as magnitude-dependent exponent of Omori law (Ouillon and Sornette 2011), the existence of stress shadow regions where seismicity following an earthquake is suppressed (Nandan et al. 2016; Meier et al. 2014), and multifractal nature of the spatial distribution of earthquakes (Nandan et al. 2017).

Several researchers have been investigating various aspects of ETAS forecasting models to improve its applicability. For instance, estimation of ETAS model parameters through point process approaches such as the one by Lombardi (2015) based on simulated annealing algorithm for the maximum-likelihood estimation or the expectation-maximization method by Veen and Schoenberg (2008), or using Bayesian statistics which allow parameter uncertainty to be explicitly represented and fed into the forecast distribution (Ross, 2016; Ebrahimian and Jalayer, 2017). Here is a summary of the recent work toward improving ETAS-based models:

- The parameters of the ETAS model have been generally assumed to be spatially invariant in most of the literature on the ETAS model, primarily for computational simplicity. Considering that these parameters are possibly the manifestations of the local physical properties of the crust, they exhibit spatial variability. Nandan et al. (2017) proposed an objective framework for the estimation of spatially varying parameters of the ETAS model, using the expectation-maximization (EM) algorithm and spatial Voronoi tessellation ensembles. They used the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) to rank inverted models given their likelihood and complexity and selected the best models to compute an ensemble model at any location. Nandan et al. (2019) presented a class of smoothed seismicity models (SSM) based on ETAS principles and performed numerous pseudo-prospective experiments to find the best performing model. According to their results, the ETAS model with spatially variable parameters indeed outperformed other smoothed seismicity-based models and was followed by the ETAS model with a global (spatially homogenous) set of parameters in most of the experiments. Indeed, their findings highlighted the importance of forecasting the rates of future aftershocks of all generations, contrary to the often-used hypothesis that the background seismicity alone can lead to a superior smoothed seismicity forecast (Nandan et al. 2019).
- Lombardi (2015) proposed an innovative method based on Simulated Annealing (SA) for the Maximum Likelihood Estimation of an ETAS model, as described in Lombardi (2017a). SA is a stochastic method to solve problems of multidimensional global optimization. Unlike the Newton methods (Ogata 2006; Zhuang, Ogata, and Vere-Jones 2002), the SA method allows a proper evaluation of the model uncertainties, utilizing multiple runs. These provide a probability distribution for each parameter and the background spatial distribution. Moreover, the comparison of parameter values found in different runs helps to detect possible correlations among them. Therefore, this is of prominent importance to detect the multimodal

- distribution of the maximum log-likelihood to attribute a physical significance to parameters and to discuss possible spatio-temporal variations. Finally, the SA method produces a systematic set of models, without any dependence on the starting values of parameters, thereby avoiding the risk of finding a local maximum of the log-likelihood (Lombardi, 2017a).
- Lombardi (2017b) made an effort to separate epistemic (parametric) uncertainty, which is due to lack of knowledge, from aleatory uncertainty, which is due to randomness, in the narrow context of short-term modelling of earthquakes by means of an application of a specific version of the ETAS model to the seismicity of Central Italy, recently struck by a sequence with a main event of Mw 6.5 (October 30, 2016). The parametric uncertainty of the ETAS-type model is much lower than the aleatory variability of the process. This result points out two main aspects: an analyst has a good chance to fix the ETAS-type models, but he may retrospectively describe and forecast the earthquake occurrences with still limited precision and accuracy (Lombardi, 2017b). To explain more, the large aleatory uncertainty means that it is difficult to fit observations soon after the strongest events, since the main short-term features of seismicity have high uncertainty. The ETAS-type models do not consider specific characteristics of the ongoing seismicity, such as the possible activation of close major faults, during a sequence. The background rate, constant in time and variable in space, is inadequate to represent the complexity of long-term physical processes, particularly at the start of significant sequences. For these reasons, the ETAS-type models can provide plausible, even if highly uncertain, forecasts of aftershocks, but they do not usefully predict the occurrence of large shocks, both before and during a sequence. All these results show that a great effort needs to be done to improve this type of models (Lombardi, 2017b).
 - It should be emphasized that Lombardi (2017b) did not discuss the impact of data uncertainty and highly temporary incompleteness, soon after the Mw 6.5 event occurrence. The assessment of data incompleteness, and its impact on ETAS-type models, can help to provide new, more efficient, real-time forecasting procedures, comprised in OEF (Marzocchi et al. 2014). The impact of incomplete data sets has been studied by Omi et al. (2013, 2015) who proposed a Bayesian estimation method to apply to incomplete early aftershock data soon after the occurrence of large events. Omi et al. (2013) employ the detection rate of an aftershock, which is modelled by the cumulative normal distribution (the error function) of the magnitude M at an elapsed time t after the mainshock to statistically characterize the data incompleteness (Ogata and Katsura 1993).
 - Recently, Bayesian approaches are becoming more common in seismology. Researchers made an effort to present a robust estimate of earthquake forecast using Bayesian approaches to take into account the uncertainty in the ETAS short-term forecasting model (Omi et al., 2014; Ebrahimian et al., 2014; Ebrahimian and Jalayer, 2017). The Bayesian framework is difficult due to the highly complex nature of the posterior distribution in the ETAS model. Even the above-mentioned studies that attempt Bayesian earthquake forecasting have had to resort to using frequentist-style plug-in point estimates of parameters which reduces the benefits of the Bayesian framework (Ross 2016). Ross (2016) introduced a new posterior sampling scheme for estimating the ETAS model in a fully Bayesian manner, which can be efficiently scaled up to large catalogues containing thousands of earthquakes and Ross (2016) demonstrated its efficiency.
 - Kolev and Ross (2019) introduced the concept of temporally variable ground intensity based on stress release modelling. They specified two families of (stress release) SR-ETAS models that depend on either the occurrence time of the previous event in the sequence (Full-SR-ETAS), or the elapsed time from the last immigrant main event (Branched-SR-ETAS). Their

experimental results suggest that these models capture observed features of real earthquake catalogues that the standard ETAS model does not. It should be noted that for simplicity and ease of both simulation and computation, Kolev and Ross (2019) only considered the original temporal ETAS model rather than its spatio-temporal extension, emphasizing that their model could be extended to the spatial version without difficulty. Kolev and Ross (2019) examined a single fault, a nonspatial occurrence that is typically used by seismologists for the analysis of seismic fault activity. All concepts are directly applicable to the spatial extension of ETAS. There are many alternatives to the spatial component(s) of the standard ETAS that provide a great differentiation amongst them, which makes a direct comparison of the introduced family of model impractical. Overall, the nonspatial alternative introduced by Kolev and Ross (2019) provided excellent results as long as there are no strong nonlinear or nonuniform patterns in the spatial distribution of the earthquakes along the fault of interest.

4.5 OEF experiences from Italy

4.5.1 Systems and organizations

Following the 6th April 2009 L'Aquila earthquake (Mw 6.2), the International Commission on Earthquake Forecasting for Civil Protection (ICEFCP) was convened by the Italian government to provide a comprehensive report on OEF and its deployment (Jordan et al., 2011). The commission had two main duties: (1) to report on the current state of knowledge of short-term prediction and forecasting of tectonic earthquakes and (2) to indicate guidelines for utilization of possible forerunners of large earthquakes to drive civil protection actions, including the use of probabilistic seismic-hazard analysis in the wake of a large earthquake.

The Department of Civil Protection in Italy (Dipartimento della Protezione Civile, DPC) is responsible for risk forecasting, loss prevention, emergency management and response, at the national scale. According to Law #225/1992, the level at which decisions are made after an event depends on the event's severity rated from natural events (scale A) to natural disasters and catastrophes (scale C). Events A and B are dealt with by the affected municipality or region at the local level. Events C are dealt with by the National Civil Protection Service under the coordination of the Prime Minister through DPC (Jordan et al., 2011). The DPC's responsibilities include activities devoted to the causes of disasters, identification of risks and areas at risk, reducing damage due to disasters including information based on forecasts, and interventions for the rehabilitation of communities and the recovery of normal life conditions (Jordan et al., 2011).

The National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology (Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, or INGV) is the DPC competence centre for seismic and volcanic risk and provides long-term seismic hazard maps for the entire country. Centro di Pericolosità Sismica (CPS, the Seismic Hazard Centre) at the INGV is an authoritative source of information on the seismic hazard for the Italian Civil Protection that is the body in charge of managing the seismic risk in Italy. The main goals of CPS are the establishment of (a) a procedure that produces authoritative scientific information and (b) a transparent decision-making protocol that clarifies how scientific information will be used for risk reduction strategies. The distinction of roles between CPS-INGV and DPC establishes the duties of the scientists and engineers who must estimate the hazard and risk and of decision-makers who must plan and put in place risk-reduction strategies.

The INGV introduced the first official OEF system in Italy (OEF-Italy, Marzocchi et al. 2014) developed by CPS, which fully satisfies the ICEF guideline (Jordan et al., 2011). The OEF-Italy is continuously delivered by INGV to the Department of Civil Protection, and INGV are presently working with communication experts on how to shape effective public messages (Field et al. 2016). It is also regularly delivered to the Commissione Nazionale per la Prevenzione e Previsione dei Grandi Rischi (the Grand Risk Commission), which provides the Italian government with expert advice about natural hazards and their associated risks.

The authoritative information should be only based on earthquake forecasting or prediction models that are under evaluation by independent experts, for example in CSEP, and tested against future observations to evaluate their forecasting power (Zechar et al. 2010; Schorlemmer et al. 2018; Taroni et al. 2018).

To make OEF information potentially useful to a wider group of stakeholders, Marzocchi et al. (2014) activated a collaboration with REte dei Laboratori Universitari di Ingegneria Sismica (RELUIS), a consortium of Italian universities involved in seismic engineering research, in order to move from short-term hazard to short-term risk assessment which produces loss metrics, such as the expected number of collapsed buildings, displaced residents, injuries, and fatalities. Iervolino et al. (2015) investigated the feasibility of short-term operational earthquake loss forecasting (OELF) in Italy. Their proposed procedure was implemented in an experimental OELF system that continuously processes OEF-Italy information to produce nationwide risk maps applying to the week after the OEF data release.

4.5.2 OEF-ITALY operating system

CPS at INGV established a pilot OEF system for Italy during the REAKT project and with additional funding from the Italian Civil Protection (Marzocchi et al. 2014). To our knowledge, no other European nation has a similar national OEF programme. The philosophy of the OEF-Italy system rests on three concepts: (a) it is fully transparent such that the results are reproducible by anyone; (b) the system is open to any modellers who want to contribute, provided the model is under test in at least one CSEP experiment; and finally (c) it minimizes scientific controversies because the use of ensemble models based on objective statistical evaluation of the model's performance significantly reduces the subjectivity that is implicit when choosing the model to be used. For a detailed discussion, please refer to Marzocchi et al. (2014).

4.5.2.1 Forecasting models

Seismicity rates from the OEF-Italy system of INGV cover the whole national area and some parts of the sea. The system uses an almost-real-time earthquake catalogue from recordings of the National Seismic Network, operated by INGV (<http://iside.rm.ingv.it>), which are available and updated 20–30 minutes after each event.

In the OEF-Italy system, the forecasts are the product of an ensemble model by Marzocchi et al. (2012) that combines three clustering models that all had been submitted to the CSEP forecast experiment in Italy:

- 1) *The version of the ETAS model proposed by Lombardi and Marzocchi (2010b)*: the ETAS model calibrated using the Italian instrumental catalogue (2005-2009), both for the background and the triggering part (Taroni et al. 2018).

- 2) *The ETAS model implemented by Falcone et al. (2010)*: the ETAS model with a spatial decay of the triggering activity independent from the magnitude of the shock, and with the aftershock productivity parameter α fixed to 1. The model was calibrated on a merged Italian instrumental catalogue from 1987 to 2009, known as ETES (Taroni et al. 2018).
- 3) *The version of the STEP model proposed by Woessner et al. (2010)*: the STEP model with specific parametrization for Italy and original global parameters. For the triggering part, these models use a spatial extension of the Reasenberg and Jones (1989) aftershock model. The model was calibrated on a merged Italian instrumental catalogue, covering the period from 1981 to 2007 (Taroni et al. 2018).

The ensemble procedure of score model averaging (SMA), introduced by Marzocchi et al. (2012), is usually obtained through a weighted average of all models, and the weights are related to the past forecasting model's performance. An ensemble model has several advantages: prospectively, it usually outperforms any single model; it allows for a proper estimation of the epistemic uncertainty that is represented by the variability of forecasts among the models and that is of paramount importance for testing (Marzocchi and Jordan 2014) and for communicating uncertainties to the decision-makers (Marzocchi et al. 2017), and it accounts for the different features of all forecasting models (Zechar et al. 2016).

4.5.2.2 System outputs

Two main outputs of the OEF-Italy are (Marzocchi et al. 2014): 1) the weekly earthquake forecast of different magnitudes (i.e. 4+, 5.5+) representing the system forecasts that at least one earthquake with local magnitude no smaller than 4 or 5.5 will happen within the next week and 2) the weekly probability of ground shaking for modified Mercalli intensities (MMIs) VI, VII, and VIII.

The weekly earthquake forecasts and seismic hazard are updated every day or just after an earthquake with M3.5 (local magnitude) or larger. The time window of one week has been agreed upon with DPC considering the time scale of hazard variability and short-term internal emergency actions. Note that the OEF-Italy system incorporates ground-motion prediction equations and site-effect models that already have been used for operational purposes in order to maintain consistency with different seismic-hazard models such as the Italian ShakeMaps (Michelini et al. 2008; Lauciani et al. 2012). In order to predict potential earthquakes with $ML \leq 5.5$, regionalized GMPEs developed by Malagnini et al. (2000), Malagnini et al. (2002) and Morasca et al. (2006) were adopted, and for larger events, a predictive model developed by Akkar and Bommer (2010) was utilized. The ground motions for rock sites were corrected by the amplification factors proposed by Michelini et al. (2008) depending on VS30 (average shear-wave velocity to a depth of 30m), to account for potential site effects. To this end, the VS30 map derived from topography using the approach of Wald and Allen (2007) was used.

In the present version of the OEF-Italy system, the ground shaking parameter is MMI. The intensity maps are derived from instrumental ground motions by using the regression relationships of Wald et al. (1999). The OEF-Italy system issued statistically reliable space-time-magnitude forecasts of the largest earthquakes during the complex 2016–2017 Amatrice-Norcia sequence, which is characterized by several bursts of seismicity and a significant deviation from the Omori law (Marzocchi et al. 2017). No increase in seismic activity was anticipated before the Amatrice earthquake on 24 August 2016 (M6). M5.9 (on October 26) and M6.5 (on October 30) earthquakes happened in the northern portion of the sequence, and M5+ earthquakes occurred in January in the

southern part of the sequence (Marzocchi et al. 2017). In the last revision of the OEF-Italy system, Sardinia and the Etna region are not included in the system due to their peculiar seismic activity.

4.5.3 Prospective CSEP evaluation of 1-day, 3-month, and 5-year earthquake forecasts

The European CSEP test centre at ETH Zurich conducted three CSEP-Italy experiments beginning on the 1st August 2009 to solicit forecasts for seismicity tomorrow, in the next three months, and for the five years in Italy. During these five years, the INGV recorded 83 target earthquakes with $3.95 \leq ML < 4.95$, and 14 larger shocks (Taroni et al. 2018). The results were:

1. The 1-day forecasts were consistent with the number and magnitudes of the target earthquakes, and one version of the ETAS model by Lombardi and Marzocchi (2010a) was also consistent with their spatial distribution. Taroni et al. (2018) used three different types of ensembles proposed by Marzocchi et al. (2012) to forecast the distribution of earthquakes in Italy for the purpose of the 1-day experiment. The ensemble approaches were: 1) Bayesian model averaging (BMA), 2) score model averaging (SMA), and 3) generalized score model averaging (gSMA). The ensemble forecasts (BMA, gSMA and SMA) were consistent with the number, locations, and magnitudes of the target earthquakes and performed as well as the best model.
2. None of the 3-month time-independent models produced consistent forecasts.
3. The best 5-year models accounted for the fault distribution and the historical seismicity. The 5-year models based on instrumental seismicity and b-value spatial variation showed poor forecasting performance (Taroni et al. 2018).

Besides CSEP experiments, the ETAS model has been experimentally used to forecast the space-time earthquake occurrence rate for several earthquake sequences that occurred in Italy. For instance, Marzocchi and Lombardi (2009) performed a prospective real-time earthquake forecast experiment during the sequence that followed the L'Aquila earthquake and Marzocchi et al. (2012) did a similar exercise for the Emilia earthquake sequence. Recent studies by Ebrahimian and Jalayer (2017) presented a robust estimate of earthquake forecasts using Bayesian parameter estimation and a Markov Chain Monte Carlo simulation scheme and taking into account the uncertainty in the ETAS short-term forecasting model. They demonstrated the methodology by retrospective early forecasting of seismicity associated with the 2016 Amatrice seismic sequence activities in central Italy.

4.6 OEF experiences from Iceland

Iceland currently has no national OEF system. Nevertheless, a prototype OEF system is operated by the Icelandic Meteorological Office (IMO) since December 2014. The short-term forecasting model runs automatically through the MATLAB-based program, MapSeis software, written by Eberhard (2014), and it was funded by the EC FP7- Real-time Earthquake Risk Reduction (REAKT) project. The seismic forecasts cover the seismic region of southwest Iceland including the South Iceland Seismic Zone, the Hengill Triple Junction and the Reykjanes Peninsula.

The prototype OEF system for south Iceland (OEF-SI) runs on a seismic catalogue reported by the Icelandic seismic network (SIL) and revised by Panzera et al. (2016) to overcome the deficiency that the local magnitude scale in Iceland effectively saturates at larger magnitudes. For instance, the SIL catalogue reported the 29-May-2008 Olfus earthquake with ML 5.3, while international agencies reported Mw 6.3 (Zechar et al. 2016). The catalogue comprises data from 1991 to 2013, including the damaging earthquakes of 17 and 21 June 2000 (Mw 6.4, 6.5). It should be noted that the SIL catalogue is capable of detecting events with magnitudes down to zero as well as of automatically evaluating the data to a high level.

The OEF-SI system issues new forecasts daily (every 24 hrs) and also immediately after an earthquake with ML 3 or larger. Such models are defined as “real-time” models by Eberhard (2014), because they will not issue forecasts at a fix predefined time interval that might cause missing aftershocks occurring after a larger earthquake, which might occur shortly after an issued forecast.

To evaluate the consistency of the forecast with the observations, Eberhard (2014) produced one-day forecasts daily and pseudo-real time updates where additional new forecasts were produced after every event with magnitude ML 3 or larger from 2007 to 2010. For this purpose, he used three models: 1) STEP (Gerstenberger et al. 2005), 2) ETAS (Zhuang 2011), and 3) TripleS (Zechar and Jordan 2010b). Note that STEP and ETAS are common space-time clustering models following the CSEP experiments (Zechar et al. 2013), whereas TripleS is a spatially heterogeneous but time-invariant model built as a long-term reference model (Eberhard 2012; Taroni et al. 2013). To work on a catalogue that is close to real-time, a sparsely processed catalogue release by IMO was used to generate the forecasts.

As indicated in Figure 3, Eberhard (2014) reported the predictive performance of the three above-mentioned models, their negative binomial implementations, their real-time implementations, and the ensembles. He built ensemble models using the generalized score model averaging method proposed by Marzocchi et al. (2012) and evaluated whether a time-invariant contribution could enhance the forecasting performance. The ensemble model of two space-time clustering models, STEP and ETAS, was named “duo” and the ensemble duo with the added TripleS model was named “trio”. The performance metric is information gain per target earthquake (Rhoades et al. 2011) relative to a spatially uniform Poisson model. Positive (negative) information gain shows that a forecasting model is better (worse) than the reference model with a uniform forecast. The red line represents the expected information gain of the perfect Poisson model (equal to 15).

Figure 3: Total information gain relative to the spatially uniform forecast per target earthquake for all models. n. bin and RT stand for negative binomial and real-time, respectively. Originally published as Fig. 4.9 by Eberhard (2014).

In brief, the results of the comparison are as follows:

1. the best performing model is the ensemble trio real-time model;
2. ensemble models outperform single models, as expected. However, the difference to the best non-ensemble model (i.e. real-time ETAS) is not significant;
3. ensemble trio models perform better than ensemble duo models;
4. negative binomial implementations have negative information gains because negative binomial models are super-Poisson in each cell and each cell has a low expectation, so the models inherently forecast smaller probabilities (than Poisson) for a small number of events, and in this experiment, no cell has more than one event (Zechar et al. 2016);
5. real-time models are better than regularly updated (24 hrs) models because they are more likely to be able to forecast the evolution of seismic sequences more accurately.

Regarding the computational demand, Eberhard (2014) reported that the best performing model, the real-time ensemble trio, required about 15 minutes of CPU time on a modern desktop computer. Indeed, this number depends on the size of the study region, the size of the grid, the seismicity rate, and the selected models, but it nonetheless suggests that OEF is computationally practical (Zechar et al. 2016).

Note that the OEF-SI system issues daily earthquake forecasts using only the ETAS model (Ogata 2011). Other models such as STEP were not implemented on the IMO website at this time. The access to the OEF-SI is limited to the seismic monitoring group at IMO and the end-users of REAKT, Landsvirkjun and Landsnet. The forecasts are based on all recorded earthquakes from 1991 up to midnight the day before. The catalogue is assembled from two parts, a static catalogue from 1991 until August 2014 and a catalogue updated every day from August 2014 until midnight before the forecasting day. An illustrative example of the OEF-SI system is shown in Figure 4. It indicates the spatiotemporal forecasted seismicity rates issued for 02-Dec-2019 for two ML scenarios of 3.5 and 6.5.

Figure 4: The spatiotemporal forecasted seismicity for two ML scenarios of 3.5 and 6.5 on 02-Dec-2019, depicted from the OEF-SI system.

Zechar et al. (2016) believed that advances in Iceland demonstrate that we have models that are superior to time-invariant, spatially uniform estimates of seismic hazard. The multifaceted geology of Iceland containing volcanoes, active tectonics and geothermal systems as well as the availability of a dense seismic network and an earthquake catalogue that is complete down to small magnitudes make this country an ideal benchmark to explore the OEF limits and feasibility as a testbed in the TURNkey project.

4.7 OEF experiences from the USA

The United States Geological Survey (USGS) initiated OEF efforts in the 1980s, with foreshock alerts as part of the Parkfield Earthquake Prediction Experiment (Bakun and McEvilly 1984). The first generation of OEF models was based on the statistical evaluation of seismicity over time. For example, the model of Reasenberg and Jones (1989) has been used widely for aftershock forecasting since the 1989 Loma Prieta earthquake. This model estimates earthquake probability based on the empirical Omori-Utsu and Gutenberg-Richter laws. Reasenberg and Jones (1989) assume that all aftershocks are triggered by a single mainshock, which is not commonly demonstrated in practice. The model also does not account for spatial information, which may lead to poor performance for complex seismic sequences (e.g. 2016-2017 Amatrice-Norcia) or swarms of multiple similar-sized earthquakes not taking into consideration the secondary aftershock sequence (Marzocchi et al. 2017). The Reasenberg and Jones (1989) model has been used to generate automated alerts following moderate earthquakes in California and for advisories issued by an ad-hoc process after the 2010 Haiti earthquake, the 2010 Maule, Chile, earthquake, the 2010 El Mayor-Cucapah, Mexico, earthquake, the 2011 Mineral Springs, Virginia, earthquake, and the 2015 Gorkha, Nepal, earthquake (Field et al. 2016). There are three different types of parameter values: (1) “generic” parameter values derived from previous sequences in similar tectonic settings, (2) “sequence-specific” parameter values fitted to the aftershock sequence as of the time of the forecast, and (3) “Bayesian” parameter values, which combine the generic parameter values with sequence-specific information (USGS 2020). It is not currently calculating spatial forecasts or providing maps to show areas with the highest likelihood of aftershocks. As a rule of thumb, aftershocks are most likely to occur near the mainshock fault plane and in areas already experiencing numerous aftershocks. This platform provides “the probability of at least one aftershock of at least magnitude, ‘M’, and the likely number of aftershocks of at least magnitude, ‘M’, within the given time frame, i.e. one day, one week, one month and one

year (USGS 2020). The recent space-time-magnitude forecasting models are based on the same empirical laws used by Reasenber and Jones (1989, 1994), however taking into account two significant improvements: the spatial component of the forecasts and the triggering effects of every earthquake of a sequence.

Almost all forecasting studies are based on windowing methods in which earthquake occurrence rates are predicted using data within either fixed or variable time and space windows. However, in recent work, Gupta and Baker (2017) developed a Bayesian change-point model to estimate spatially-varying seismicity rates for any non-homogenous spatiotemporal Poisson process and examined its performance by applying their proposed method to the induced seismicity observed in Oklahoma. The inter-event times are used to identify a change in event rates. The occurrence of a change in the seismicity rate is calculated using Bayesian updating. To estimate temporal changes in spatially varying event rates, they presented a smoothing radius. In order to specify the optimum smoothing radius, a probability-gain methodology is suggested. The approach is based on comparing likelihoods and also exploring the proposed model's performance in forecasting future seismicity. If a change in rates is detected, the probability of change happening at any given time and the probability distributions of event rates before and after the change occurrence are determined (Gupta and Baker, 2017). To compare the performance of the spatiotemporal change-point model with the common existing models (e.g. windowing approaches), it is suggested that the predicted event rates obtained from former model are tested against the CSEP experiments. As an extension to the presented model, Gupta and Baker (2017) suggested a combination of their proposed model with the ETAS declustering method (Ogata and Zhuang 2006) to avoid the independent earthquake catalogue declustering required prior to the change-point model implementation.

4.8 OEF Experiences from Japan

In Japan, two government organizations have responsibility for operational earthquake forecasting, namely: 1) the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA), which is responsible aftershock forecasting, earthquake early warning as well as tsunami warning and predicting the hypothetical Tokai earthquake; and 2) the Headquarters for Earthquake Research Promotion (HERP) in the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology established after the 17 January 1995 Hyogo-ken-Nanbu (Kobe) earthquake (Mw 6.9, 6434 deaths) following the 'Earthquake Disaster Management Special Act' which was enacted in July 1995. HERP is responsible for the public announcements based on comprehensive surveys and observational plans and planning relevant policies as well as possessing the operational responsibility for monthly reports on the evaluation of seismic activity in Japan, long-term evaluation of inland and off-shore earthquakes, and national seismic hazard maps for Japan (Jordan et al. 2011). For instance, HERP provided essential information towards seismic risk mitigation and the long-term (10 and 30 years) earthquake potential of active crustal and subduction-zone faults.

4.8.1 Earthquake Forecasting before 2016

In Japan, since 1998 and following a report entitled "Probabilistic evaluation of aftershocks" published by HERP, the Earthquake Research Committee (ERC, 1998) of the HERP established a formal operational procedure for aftershock forecasting. In order to calculate aftershock probabilities, two universal relationships, namely the Omori-Utsu law (Utsu and Ogata 1995) for presenting the aftershock decay and the Gutenberg-Richter law (Gutenberg et al. 1945) for the magnitude-frequency relation, are used. The sequence-specific parameters are employed only if they are reliably estimated.

Otherwise, the generic parameters, the average parameter values obtained from the past aftershock sequences in Japan, are used. Thereby, the JMA has conducted aftershock forecasting following 15 earthquakes with a maximum seismic intensity equal to or greater than six-lower (JMA scale) during 1998-2016 (ERC 2016; Omi et al. 2019; Jordan et al. 2011).

Zhuang (2011) employed the spatiotemporal ETAS model as an “off-line optimization, and online forecasting” scheme for short-term (daily) earthquake forecasts for the whole of Japan in the SCEC CSEP project which is maintained by the Earthquake Research Institute at the University of Tokyo (Nanjo et al. 2011). The proposed scheme consists of the following main components:

- (1) The off-line optimization in which the optimal model parameters were computed for delivering the forecasts. For this purpose, the ETAS model was fitted to earthquakes occurring before the forecasting time interval to derive the forecasts.
- (2) A simulation procedure to simulate several earthquakes in the forecasting time interval using the last updated parameters and most recent earthquake records.
- (3) A smoothing procedure to smooth the simulated events (from step 2) to obtain stable and smoothed spatiotemporal occurrence rates.
- (4) A forecast calculation procedure based on the CSEP common evaluation framework. The number of simulations of at least one event occurrence relative to the total number of simulations was defined as the probability of earthquake occurrence (Zhuang 2011).

In addition, Rhoades (2011) employed the EEPAS model to forecast long-term seismicity in Japan. EEPAS is a spatiotemporal point-process model based on the precursory scale increase phenomenon and its associated predictive scaling relations. Rhoades and Evison (2006) applied EEPAS to the depth-restricted NIED catalogue (real-time catalogue of National Research Institute for Earth Science and Disaster Resilience, NIED) including events with magnitudes greater than 4.75 to investigate the lower magnitude range applicability of the precursory scaling relations in the Kanto area located in central Japan. The EEPAS model was tested in the CSEP forecasting test centre in Japan, and its outcomes were compared with the existing models. According to the results, the scaling relationship between magnitude and precursor time indicates that the EEPAS model performs reliably for three-month forecasting for $M \geq 4$ and one-year forecasting for $M \geq 5$. The magnitude of completeness of the required earthquake catalogue should be approximately two orders of magnitude below the target magnitude threshold.

4.8.2 Earthquake Forecasting after 2016

After the 2016 Kumamoto earthquake, in which the M6.5 foreshock preceded the M7.3 mainshock by approximately 28 hrs, the ERC revised the aftershock forecasting procedure significantly (ERC 2016). In the revised procedure (ERC 2016), the aftershock probability computation was improved by exploiting the ETAS in addition to the previously employed Omori–Utsu law. According to the new procedure, the forecasted earthquakes equal to or larger than a mainshock will be announced to the public; however, it does not provide aftershock probabilities during the first week after a large earthquake. The reason is the incompleteness of data at the early stage of an earthquake sequence. According to the ERC (2016) document, the probability gain (i.e. the ratio of the aftershock probability relative to the background probability) is to be announced to the public instead of the aftershock probability (Omi et al., 2019).

4.8.3 A prototype real-time aftershock forecasting system

Forecasting aftershock probabilities, as early as possible after a mainshock, is required to mitigate seismic risks in a disaster area. However, it is challenging owing to the numerous unobserved aftershocks immediately after the mainshock caused by dense overlapping of seismic waves (Omi et al. 2014). Omi et al. (2019) presented a prototype of a real-time system for automatic aftershock forecasting in Japan using real-time seismicity data. The designed prototype issues the first forecast about 3 hrs after a mainshock and continues hourly forecasting until two days after a mainshock. This is a complementary system to the existing operational procedure (ERC 2016) in Japan with a primary goal of generating forecasts at the early stage of a sequence by employing statistical techniques introduced and tested by Omi et al. (2013, 2014, 2015).

The system started operation of its first version at the NIED in April 2017. Forecasts generated by the system can be viewed through a web browser, but access to the forecasts is restricted to limited users at present (Omi et al. 2019). The system runs every 15 min to detect the occurrence of a new mainshock (i.e. earthquake of $M \geq 5.0$ located sufficiently far from the last mainshock) and to generate the estimated occurrence probabilities of earthquakes with magnitudes equal to or greater than a mainshock ($M \geq 5.0$) at the scheduled timings. Omi et al. (2019) plan to report the resultant forecasts of the system to the ERC when a damaging earthquake happens.

In other words, a space-time window around each mainshock is considered. More precisely, the time window is one week after a mainshock, and the space window is the aftershock zone of a mainshock magnitude M_0 which is defined as a square with the side length $4 * 0.01 * 10^{(0.5M_0 - 1.8)}$ degrees. According to Omi et al. (2019), in case of large uncertainty in the real-time earthquake location, the relatively large aftershock zone is necessary to make the best use of the aftershock data.

The system does not calculate forecasts if the number of observed aftershocks in an estimation period is less than 30 because parameter estimation is difficult for small sample-size data. It should be noted that a smaller number of identified aftershocks in a very short learning period of one or two hours after the mainshock might be the actual practical case, which makes the forecasts unstable. Lippiello et al. (2019) presented a method for aftershock forecasting where the parameters of the Omori-Utsu law were extracted from the ground velocity recorded during the first 30 minutes after a mainshock and did not require that signals were transferred and elaborated by operational units. Refinements of the Lippiello et al. (2019) method can be obtained by incorporating higher-order generation aftershocks which should contribute to improving the agreement for learning periods larger than 1 hour. Also, it is worth mentioning that the forecasting method proposed by Omi et al. (2019) requires a ground motion prediction equation to determine the probability of ground shaking at a given site from the estimated aftershock forecast rates. However, Lippiello et al. (2019)'s method, which is based on a fitting procedure applied to the ground velocity recorded at a site of interest, does not require the identification of aftershocks and provides the probability of strong ground shaking without ground motion prediction equations. The idea is similar to the proposal of extrapolating the long-term probability of ground shaking directly from the frequency distribution of the maximum amplitude of seismograms. Also, in the method, it is not necessary to locate earthquakes and to rely on assumptions of seismicity.

Omi et al. (2019) investigated the system's performance for the cases of three inland earthquakes that occurred after the establishment of the system in April 2017. Moreover, they investigated the potential usefulness of their introduced prototype for forecasting large earthquakes by conducting a

retrospective forecast test for the 2016 Kumamoto earthquake sequence, including foreshocks, mainshock and aftershocks, based on the real-time seismicity data.

4.8.3.1 Real-time data

It should be noted that Japan's monitoring system is useful for providing continuous, timely information on time-dependent aftershock probabilities. For the purpose of real-time operation, the prototype system uses the High Sensitivity Seismograph Network automatic hypocentre catalogue (Hi-net catalogue) of the National Research Institute for Earth Science and Disaster Resilience (NIED). For the Hi-net catalogue, earthquakes occurring in Japan are automatically detected in real-time and assembled at the NIED (Okada et al. 2004). Omi et al. (2016) provided a comparison between the aftershock forecasting performances based on real-time seismicity data (Hi-net catalogue) and using the JMA unified catalogue. Note that in the JMA catalogue, all events are inspected manually within a few days after a large earthquake. According to Omi et al. (2016), the forecasting capability between the Hi-net and JMA catalogues are comparable when forecasting large aftershocks and the Hi-net catalogue is useful for real-time aftershock forecasting in Japan.

4.8.3.2 Forecasting model and its parameter estimation

The forecast method employed in the system is based on the simple Omori–Utsu and Gutenberg–Richter laws to generate robust forecasts using insufficient early aftershock data. Please refer to Omi et al. (2016) for detailed information. The model parameters are sequence-specific to account for the variability in aftershock activities, and they are updated every time a forecast is issued. To account for the deficit of new events due to the lowered detection ability of seismic networks after a large earthquake, Omi et al. (2016) employed the detection rate of aftershocks as a function of time and magnitude (Ogata and Katsura 2006; 1993; Omi et al. 2014; 2013). A Bayesian forecasting approach is employed to consider epistemic uncertainty. To clarify, they first calculate the probability distribution of the parameter values given the observed catalogue (i.e. the posterior distribution), which is proportional to the likelihood function and the prior distribution, according to Bayes' theorem. In this system, instead of the best point estimation from the posterior distribution (namely, the maximum a posteriori estimate) introduced by Reasenber and Jones (1989), the Bayesian forecasting method discussed by Akaike (1978), Nomura et al. (2011), and Omi et al. (2015) is used in which many sets of likely parameter values are sampled from the posterior distribution. In other words, Omi et al. (2019) made an ensemble forecast by combining individual forecasts, each of which is based on the Omori–Utsu and Gutenberg–Richter models with different parameter values. The system's output forecast value is the mean of these individual forecasts. The distribution of the individual forecasts represents the epistemic uncertainty of the aftershock probability. For further information on the forecast distribution, please refer to Marzocchi et al. (2015). The system uses the 25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles of the forecast distribution as a measure of the forecast uncertainty. Due to the better forecasting performance of Hi-net catalogue than the generic model, which is based on the JMA catalogue, the sequence-specific forecast is effective with the incomplete real-time data even though the real-time automatic data are inferior to the manually revised data, especially for the early stage of aftershocks of the M 7 class mainshocks (Omi et al. 2016).

5 CURRENT SITUATION OF EEW SYSTEMS OPERATING IN EUROPE

5.1 Summary

Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) is a relatively new strategy for reducing disaster risk and increasing resilience to seismic hazard in urban settings. EEW systems provide real-time information about ongoing earthquakes, enabling individuals, communities, governments, businesses and others located at distance to take timely action to reduce the probability of harm or loss before the earthquake-induced ground shaking reaches them. Examples of potential losses mitigated by EEW systems include injuries and infrastructure downtime. Such systems are currently operating in nine countries, and are being or have been tested for implementation in 13 more. This section reviews state-of-the-art approaches to EEW around the world. We specifically focus on the various algorithms that have been developed for the rapid calculation of seismic source parameters, ground shaking, and potential consequences in the wake of an event. We also discuss limitations of the existing applied methodologies, with a particular emphasis on the lack of engineering-related (i.e., risk and resilience) metrics currently used to support decision-making related to the triggering of alerts by various end users. Finally, we provide a number of suggestions for future end-user-orientated advances in the field of EEW.

5.2 Introduction

Early warning consists of a set of procedures and tools for disseminating actionable information in advance of a threatening circumstance to reduce the potential risks involved (Basher et al. 2006). Early warning systems are increasingly considered an important and effective way to mitigate the effects of natural hazards (Stein 1975). It is therefore not surprising that they are frequently used to send alerts related to floods (e.g., Krzysztofowicz et al. 1994), tornados (e.g., Simmons and Sutter 2009), avalanches (e.g., Rheinberger 2013), glacier lake outbursts (e.g., Bründl and Sturny 2014), landslides (e.g., Medina-Cetina and Nadim 2008), debris flows (e.g., Sättele et al. 2015) and tsunamis (e.g., Blaser et al. 2011). In this section, we focus specifically on their application to earthquakes.

Earthquake early warning (EEW) systems are primarily based on two concepts that enable alerts to be sent ahead of the occurrence of earthquake-induced ground shaking at target locations (on the order of seconds to minutes): (1) information travels faster than seismic (i.e., mechanical) waves; and (2) most of the energy of an earthquake is carried by the S- and surface waves, which arrive after the faster, lower amplitude P-waves. This warning time, although short, can reduce the impacts of an earthquake on many sectors of society (Strauss and Allen 2016). Individuals can “drop, cover and hold on” or (if there is sufficient time) evacuate hazardous buildings or move to safer locations within a building, mitigating injuries or fatalities. Automated actions can be taken, including the stopping of elevators at the nearest floor and opening the doors to avoid injuries, the slowing of high-speed trains to reduce accidents, the shutting down of gas pipelines to prevent fires, and the switching of signals to stop vehicles from entering vulnerable structures such as bridges and tunnels. This is not an exhaustive list but rather a snapshot of critical applications that could benefit from EEW.

The idea of using early warning for earthquakes was first considered by J.D. Cooper in November 1868 (Nakamura and Tucker 1988); he proposed the installation of seismic sensors near Hollister, California, that would send an electric signal via telegraph to San Francisco once an earthquake was detected. EEW was not practically implemented until the 1960's, however, when the Japanese National Railways authority developed an EEW system to avoid derailments of high-speed trains (Nakamura and Saita 2007). The concept was further enhanced by members of the U.S. Geological

Survey (USGS) in the 1960's and 1970's, when they developed a seismic monitoring system for central California that facilitated rapid estimation of earthquake location and magnitude (Kanamori 2005; Stewart 1977). Today, EEW systems are operating in the USA (Given et al. 2014), Japan (Hoshiba et al. 2008), Mexico (Cuéllar et al. 2017), Romania (Mârmureanu et al. 2011), Turkey (Alcik et al. 2009), Taiwan (Hsiao et al. 2009), South Korea (Sheen et al. 2017), China (Ji et al. 2019), and India (Kumar et al. 2014). They are also being tested for use in Italy (Zollo et al. 2014), Switzerland (Cua et al. 2009), Chile (Crowell et al. 2018), Israel (Nof and Allen 2016), Nicaragua (Strauch et al. 2018), Spain (Pazos et al. 2015), Slovenia and Austria (Picozzi et al. 2015), Greece, New Zealand and Iceland (Behr et al. 2016), as well as in Costa Rica and El Salvador (Allen and Melgar 2019). It is encouraging for developers of EEW systems to note that they are generally viewed as positive measures by relevant stakeholders (Suárez et al. 2009; Hoshiba 2014).

This section is written in the format of a “traditional or narrative literature review” e.g., Cronin et al. (2008). Using Satriano et al. (2011), Zollo et al. (2014), and Allen and Melgar (2019) as a basis, we first discuss state-of-the-art approaches and recent developments in EEW. We specifically focus on the algorithms that have been developed for various components of the real-time calculations of source parameters, ground shaking at a target site, and potential consequences. We then identify some limitations to current approaches; for example, although it is clear from Figure 5 that EEW presents a significant opportunity to reduce seismic risk in regions where it is applied, few (if any) implemented EEW systems make decisions to trigger alarms based on explicit engineering-related damage and loss predictions or resilience metrics, eventually accounting for end-user preferences in an explicit fashion. Finally, we discuss a number of suggestions for mitigating these limitations through the development of next-generation, end-user-orientated EEW systems.

Figure 5: Earthquake early warning system development across the world, overlaying a global seismic risk map that is expressed in terms of annual average losses normalized by construction costs (Silva et al. 2018). It can be seen that EEW systems are typically applied to regions that have significant seismic risk.

5.3 Current approaches and recent developments in EEW

5.3.1 Background

EEW involves four main steps (Figure 6):

- (1) detecting an event and estimating its location;
- (2) estimating the event magnitude;
- (3) estimating ground shaking at various distances conditional on the specific event occurrence and features (i.e., its location and magnitude); and
- (4) using all of the gathered information to determine whether or not to trigger an alarm, which may involve further processing of the available data. Alerts are then communicated to relevant stakeholders through various technological means, including radio, television, emails, websites, SMS messages, and smartphone applications.

Each step involves a degree of uncertainty, due to the rapid real-time calculations involved in EEW models and methods and the traditional uncertainties associated with probabilistic seismic hazard analysis (PSHA). EEW systems can be broadly divided into “regional”, “on-site”, and “hybrid” categories, based on their approach to the first three steps above and the complex EEW trade-off between warning time and prediction accuracy. Note that this section focuses on “conventional” EEW systems, which make use of data measured with traditional seismic instruments (e.g., high-quality seismometers). It is important to mention that alternative approaches to EEW are beginning to be developed, which harness the ever-increasing density of mobile computing and instead use smartphone sensors as a seismic network (Kong et al. 2016; Bossu et al. 2019; Finazzi 2016). However, there are currently many challenges to overcome before these types of systems become a realistic viable replacement to conventional approaches, including sensor quality issues and notification latency (Allen et al. 2019). Regional EEW systems consist of a network of seismic sensors located within the expected epicentral area or area of high seismicity in a region, for estimating the source parameters of steps 1 and 2. These estimates are used to predict ground shaking (step 3) at sites located further away from the event (Satriano et al. 2011). This type of EEW system can be further categorised as either “point-source” (which simplistically represents the source as a concentrated volume) or “finite-fault” (which involves a more complete characterisation of the source). While finite-fault approaches are more accurate than point-source approaches, they require observations from many sites and are therefore slower (e.g., Allen and Melgar 2019).

On-site EEW systems consist of a limited set of seismic stations located at (for site-specific systems) or near (for front-detection systems) particular target sites or infrastructure of interest. They estimate both source parameters and ground shaking directly based on characteristics of the seismograms recorded within the system (Zollo et al. 2014). Regional EEW systems yield more accurate estimates of the source parameters, but on-site EEW systems result in faster warning times for near-source targets (Kanamori 2005). Hybrid EEW systems (Zollo et al. 2010; Colombelli et al. 2012) combine the capabilities of regional and on-site systems, by incorporating evolving information on the source parameters from a regional network (steps 1 and 2), with ground motion estimates at the target site (step 3). We now summarise and discuss the various state-of-the-art methodologies that underpin EEW systems across the world, specifically discussing whether and how they deal with the uncertainty involved in each step. Analyses of real-time algorithm performance with respect to physical EEW network constraints (such as station location and density) is outside the scope of the current review. However, interested readers should note that many previous studies have already focused on this issue (Kuyuk and Allen 2013; Auclair et al. 2015; Ogweno 2018).

Figure 6: Conceptual outline of an EEW process. Information from an EEW system sensor network is input to an EEW algorithm to detect events and compute estimates of earthquake location, magnitude, and ground shaking amplitude. Selected outputs of the calculations are then provided to a decision module for potentially further processing to determine whether or not a warning should be triggered for end users.

5.3.2 Event Detection and Location Estimation

Table 4 to Table 8 summarise the most popular current methods for event detection and EEW estimation of event locations. The procedures outlined in Table 4 and Table 5 are used in point-source regional EEW systems. The method in Table 4 is conceptually straightforward and computationally efficient to implement, but it only uses information from triggered stations, which leads to higher location uncertainties than those obtained from the procedure in Table 5. However, it is significantly challenging to implement the method in Table 5 for realistic seismic networks that have non-uniform station telemetry delays (Cua et al. 2009).

Table 6 and Table 7 outline procedures used in finite-fault algorithms for constraining locations. While the outputs of these methods may be more accurate than those of the point source approaches in Table 4 and Table 5, they typically take longer to compute. The on-site method of Table 8 is very rapid and thus useful for near-source target sites, but is significantly less accurate than the aforementioned procedures described since it relies on data from only one seismic station.

Uncertainties in the calculations are accounted for in two of the point-source algorithms included in Table 4 and Table 5. PRESTo produces a normal probability density function (PDF) for hypocentre location, which is parameterised by a mean estimate and a covariance matrix that explicitly captures spatial uncertainty. *Virtual Seismologist* makes use of a Bayesian framework, in which location and magnitude are jointly conditioned on the available set of ground motions and the prior PDF represents an existing state of knowledge on relative earthquake probability.

Recent work has focused on improving the event detection capabilities of EEW systems, such that they are less likely to cause a false alert by misinterpreting local impulsive noise from natural or anthropogenic sources (Li et al. 2018). Hsu et al. (2016) and Meier et al. (2019) demonstrate that various machine learning algorithms (e.g., support vector classification, general adversarial network, random forest, convolutional neural network) may effectively reduce the probability of false alarms caused by non-earthquake vibration events.

Table 4: Estimating location, using only information from triggered stations.

Description of method		
Seismic arrivals at a station are detected using a picker method, such as the short-term-average/long-term-average (STA/LTA) procedure (Allen 1978). Once a sufficient number of stations have triggered (in accordance with the underlying EEW algorithm), the location is estimated using a grid search routine to minimise the residuals between observed seismic phases and those predicted from a velocity model.		
Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
P-wave arrival times at triggered stations; velocity model; seismic station locations	Epicentre/hypocentre location estimate	ElarmS (USA, Chile, Israel); eBEAR (Taiwan); Beijing EEW system (China)
Output uncertainty considered?	Key references	
No	Allen et al. (2009); Chen et al. (2015); Chung and Allen (2019); Hsiao et al. (2009); Kuyuk et al. (2014); Peng et al. (2011); Wu and Teng (2002); Wurman et al. (2007)	

Table 5: Estimating location, using information from both triggered and non-triggered stations.

Description of method		
When a seismic arrival is detected at the first station, the location is initially constrained either by the geometric surface that represents the set of all locations closer to the station than any other station in the network or characteristics of the early waveform envelope. Once two stations have triggered, location uncertainty is reduced to a conditional surface based on the time between the P-wave detections. The location can be estimated directly when the third station is triggered. Alternatively, grid search routines are used to increasingly constrain the location after the second or third trigger.		
Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
P-wave arrival times at triggered stations; Velocity model; Seismic station locations	Epicentre/hypocentre location estimate	JMA (Japan); Virtual Seismologist (USA, Switzerland, Costa Rica, El Salvador, Nicaragua); PRESTo (Italy, Austria, Slovenia, Spain)
Output uncertainty considered?	Key references	
Yes, in (1) Virtual Seismologist and (2) PRESTo	Cua et al. (2009); Cua (2005); Cua and Heaton (2007); Font et al. (2004); Horiuchi et al. (2005); Kamigaichi (2004); Rosenberger (2009); Rydelek and Pujol (2004); Satriano et al. (2008); Satriano, Elia, et al. (2011); Odaka et al. (2003)	

Table 6: Estimating earthquake depth, using geodetic observations.

Description of method		
Initial estimates of earthquake depth are obtained from grid searches based on peak ground displacement (PGD) scaling relationships, using information on magnitude and pre-computed epicentral distance estimates. Final depth estimates are computed from a centroid moment tensor calculation, using static offsets from Global Positioning Systems (GPS) data.		
Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
Epicentral distance estimates (from another EEW algorithm); GPS displacement waveforms; Green's functions	Depth estimate	G-FAST (USA, Chile)
Output uncertainty considered?	Key references	
No	Crowell et al. (2013, 2016, 2018); Hashima et al. (2008); Melgar et al. (2012, 2015)	

Table 7: Estimating earthquake centroid, using ground motion image-recognition techniques.

Description of method		
An image (I) of the observed spatial peak ground motion amplitude distribution is compared to theoretical templates (T), which are calculated from a ground-motion model (GMM, also known as an attenuation relationship or a ground-motion prediction equation) for line sources of varying length. The optimum T is then found by minimising the misfit between T and I , and the centroid of the corresponding line source is equivalent to the centroid of the earthquake.		
Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
Theoretical ground motion templates, modelled from GMMs; Observed (high frequency) ground motion amplitudes; Seismic station locations	Centroid estimate	FinDER (USA, Switzerland, Chile, Costa Rica, El Salvador, Nicaragua)
Output uncertainty considered?	Key references	
No	Böse et al. (2015, 2018); Böse et al. (2012)	

Table 8: Estimating location from a single seismic station.

Description of Method		
The distance is estimated from empirical equations, which include variables such as the peak P-wave amplitude and an estimate of the magnitude.		
Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
Required parameters for empirical equations (e.g. peak P-wave amplitude);	Epicentre/Hypocentre estimate	UrEDAS (Japan); EDAS-MAS (China)

Output uncertainty considered?	Key references
No	Nakamura and Saita (2007); Peng et al. (2013); Nakamura (1988)

5.3.3 Magnitude Estimation

Table 9 to Table 13 summarise common procedures for estimating magnitude. The method in Table 9 is used in point-source approaches and takes advantage of regression (empirical) relationships between the magnitude of an event and characteristics of its initial P-waves (and S-waves close to the rupture in some cases). However, these relationships are found to saturate at larger magnitudes (Kanamori 2005; Rydelek and Horiuchi 2006; Rydelek et al. 2007; Zollo et al. 2007). The method in Table 10 is a point-source approach that makes use of longer waveform windows, in which the aforementioned relationships do not saturate.

The methods of Table 11 and Table 12 are finite-fault approaches for estimating magnitude. They provide a more realistic estimate of the size of an ongoing event than the point-source approaches previously described, since they consider measurements from the entire fault plane (Zollo et al. 2014). The on-site method in Table 13 enables rapid estimations of magnitude at sites close to the epicentre, but is less reliable than other procedures due to its dependence on measurements from a single seismic station.

Uncertainties in magnitude estimates are accounted for in a number of algorithms included in the aforementioned tables. Both *PRESTo* and *Virtual Seismologist* make use of Bayesian frameworks. In *PRESTo*, magnitude is represented by a normal PDF; the average value is calculated from an empirical relationship between magnitude and initial characteristics of the P-wave/hypocentral distance, and the standard deviation depends on errors in the coefficients of the empirical relationship as well as uncertainty in the distance estimate. Magnitude distributions for each station and time window are combined through a likelihood product, and the prior PDF is the distribution obtained at the previous time step. In *Virtual Seismologist*, the joint distribution of magnitude and location is conditioned on the available set of observed ground motions as discussed above. *Southern Iberia EEW system*, *G-FAST*, *OnSite*, and *EDAS-MAS* account for confidence intervals on the median magnitude estimate, which are equal in width to two standard deviations of the relevant regression relationship used to derive magnitude.

Table 9: Estimating magnitude from information in the very initial portion of seismic waveforms.

Description of method			
The magnitude is estimated from the amplitude (e.g. peak displacement) and the frequency content (e.g. characteristic period) or both of the initial few seconds of the incoming P-wave train, using empirical relationships. Estimates are typically averaged over a number of seismic stations.			
Inputs		Outputs	Relevant algorithms
Initial seismic waveform; Magnitude-ground		Magnitude estimate	ElarmS (USA, Chile, Israel); Virtual Seismologist (USA, Switzerland, Costa Rica, El Salvador, Nicaragua); REWS (Romania); eBEAR (Taiwan); KEEWS (South Korea);

motion relationship	empirical	Beijing EEW system (China); EEW system for Southern Iberia (Spain)
Output considered?	uncertainty	Key references
Yes, in (1) Virtual Seismologist and (2) Southern Iberia EEW system		Allen and Kanamori (2001); Böse et al. (2007); Carranza et al. (2013); Chen et al. (2015); Cua et al. (2009); Cua (2005); Cua and Heaton (2007); Dong-Hoon et al. (2017); Festa et al. 2008; Hsiao et al. (2009); Ionescu et al. (2007); Mărmureanu et al. (2011); H. Peng et al. (2011); Sheen et al. (2014); Tsang et al. (2007); Wu and Kanamori (2008a, 2008b); Wu and Zhao (2006); Wurman et al. (2007)

Table 10: Estimating magnitude from information in increasing time windows of initial seismic waveforms.

Description of method				
The method is similar to the procedure outlined above, except that the amplitude and frequency content parameters of the empirical relationships are measured over larger and increasingly expanding time windows (up to the order of minutes in some cases), and thus may also incorporate information from S-waves.				
Inputs		Outputs		Relevant algorithms
Initial seismic Magnitude-ground empirical relationship	waveform; motion	Magnitude estimate	PRESTo (Italy, Austria, Slovenia, Spain); SASMEX (Mexico); JMA (Japan)	
Output uncertainty considered?		Key references		
Yes, in (1) PRESTo		Colombelli et al. (2014); Colombelli, Zollo, et al. (2012); Colombelli and Zollo (2015); Cuéllar et al. (2017); Kamigaichi (2004); Lancieri and Zollo (2008); Satriano, Elia, et al. (2011b); Suárez et al. (2009); Zollo et al. (2006)		

Table 11: Estimating magnitude from geodetic observations.

Description of method				
Static offsets are obtained from displacement time series that are measured using a geodetic data collection system, such as GPS or Global Navigational Satellite System (GNSS). An inversion technique recovers slip estimates from the static offsets, which are then used to calculate the magnitude.				
Inputs		Outputs		Relevant algorithms
Fault geometry estimates; displacement waveforms; station locations; Remaining parameters of the inversion method used (e.g. Green's functions, station seismograms)	GPS/GNSS	Magnitude estimate	G-larmS (USA); G-FAST (USA, Chile); BEFORES (USA); REGARD (Japan)	

Output uncertainty considered?	Key references
Yes, in (1) G-FAST	Allen and Ziv (2011); Colombelli et al. (2013); Crowell et al. (2009, 2012, 2016, 2018); Grapenthin et al. (2014); Grapenthin et al. (2014); Kawamoto et al. (2016, 2017); Minson et al. (2014); Ohta et al. (2012); Wright et al. (2012); Zhang et al. (2014)

Table 12: Estimating magnitude from rupture length.

Description of method		
The magnitude is estimated from an empirical magnitude-rupture length equation (e.g., Wells and Coppersmith 1994).		
Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
Rupture length estimate	Magnitude estimate	FinDER (USA, Switzerland, Chile, Costa Rica, El Salvador, Nicaragua)
Output Considered?	Uncertainty	Key References
No		Böse et al. (2012)

Table 13: Estimating magnitude from initial characteristics of a single seismic waveform.

Description of method		
The magnitude is estimated from the amplitude (e.g. peak displacement) and the frequency content (e.g. the predominant period) of the initial few seconds of the incoming P-wave train, using empirical relationships.		
Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
Required amplitude and frequency parameters	Magnitude estimate	OnSite (USA); UrEDAS (Japan); EDAS-MAS (China)
Output uncertainty considered?	Key references	
Yes, in (1) OnSite and (2) EDAS-MAS	Böse et al. (2009); Kanamori (2005); Nakamura and Saita (2007); Peng et al. (2013); Nakamura (1988)	

5.3.4 Ground-Shaking Estimation

Regional EEW systems generally estimate ground shaking in terms of ground-motion intensity measures (IMs) from an empirical attenuation relationship (e.g. an existing GMM), using estimates of the earthquake location and magnitude obtained from the procedures outlined previously (Table 14). IMs quantify the damage potential of an earthquake-induced ground motion with respect to a specific engineering system (e.g., a structure), and can be used to predict the associated seismic response of the system (Baker and Cornell 2005). Typical IMs predicted by EEW systems include peak ground acceleration (PGA) and peak ground velocity (PGV). In less common cases, regional systems instead estimate IMs by interpolating spatially distributed maps of recorded ground shaking

(Table 15 and Table 16). On-site and hybrid systems typically obtain rapid (and less accurate) PGV estimates, using only information on the characteristics of P-waves recorded at one seismic station (Table 17).

Ground-shaking estimation explicitly accounts for most of the uncertainty involved in the first three steps of EEW (Iervolino 2011). Uncertainties in ground shaking estimates are considered in a number of algorithms. The majority of these algorithms (i.e. *PRESTo*, *G-FAST*, *OnSite*, and *EDAS-MAS*) account for uncertainty by considering a confidence interval on the estimate with width equivalent to two standard deviations of the empirical relationship used to derive ground shaking, assuming most likely (or measured) values for the source-related variables. Virtual Seismologist accounts for the full lognormal PDF of ground shaking from the relevant attenuation equation, which also incorporates the propagated source parameter uncertainty quantified above. It is also worth mentioning that several methods of reducing ground-shaking estimation uncertainty for EEW have been proposed in the literature. For example, de Matteis and Convertito (2015) developed a procedure for updating the PGA parameters of a GMM (and hence reducing its associated standard deviation) to account for the specific features of a seismic source and propagation medium, which uses real-time maximum acceleration amplitudes recorded during an event at one-second intervals. Wang et al. (2017) proposed a technique for replacing initial PGV estimates from a GMM with more certain real-time amplitude predictions calculated using recorded seismogram envelopes and wave propagation (i.e., radiative transfer) modelling.

Table 14: Estimating ground shaking from attenuation equations.

Description of method		
Source distances to target sites of interest are first computed based on earthquake location estimates. Empirical attenuation relations (e.g. GMMs) are then used in combination with these distances and the magnitude estimate to calculate spatial estimates of ground shaking.		
Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
Magnitude estimate; Location estimate; Remaining parameters of the attenuation relationship used (e.g. site condition)	Ground motion amplitude estimates	ElarmS (USA, Chile, Israel); PRESTo (Italy, Austria, Slovenia, Spain); Virtual Seismologist (USA, Switzerland, Costa Rica, El Salvador, Nicaragua); JMA (Japan)
Output uncertainty considered?	Key references	
Yes, in (1) Virtual Seismologist and (2) PRESTo	Allen et al. (2009); Cua (2005); Kamigaichi (2004); Satriano et al. (2011a)	

Table 15: Estimating spatially distributed ground shaking from ground motion recordings.

Description of method		
Recorded ground motion estimates are translated into spatially distributed maps of ground shaking, using interpolation procedures or information on ground motion spatial correlation.		
Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms

Ground motion recordings; Seismic station locations	Ground motion amplitude estimates	FinDER (USA, Switzerland, Chile, Costa Rica, El Salvador, Nicaragua), ElarmS (USA, Chile, Israel)
Output considered?	uncertainty	Key references
No		Allen et al. (2009); Böse et al. (2018); Böse et al. (2012); Iervolino (2011)

Table 16: Estimating ground shaking from initial characteristics of multiple seismic waveforms.

Description of Method		
A first image of the seismic wavefield is obtained from the initial seismic waveforms recorded, using interpolation (i.e. data assimilation) techniques. This image is input to a physics-based wave propagation model to forecast final ground motion amplitudes.		
Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
Spatially distributed seismic waveforms; Remaining parameters of the wave propagation model (e.g. Green's functions)	Ground motion amplitude estimates	PLUM (Japan)
Output uncertainty considered?	Key references	
No	Hoshiba and Aoki (2015); Kodera et al. (2016, 2018)	

Table 17: Estimating ground shaking from initial characteristics of a single seismic waveform.

Description of method		
PGV is estimated from the amplitude (e.g. peak displacement) of the initial few seconds of the incoming P-wave train, using empirical relationships.		
Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
Initial seismic waveform	PGV estimate	OnSite (USA); PRESTo ^{Plus} (Italy); EEW system for Southern Iberia (Spain)
Output considered?	uncertainty	Key references
Yes, in (1) OnSite and (2) EEW System for Southern Iberia		Böse et al. (2009); Carranza et al. (2013); Colombelli et al. (2015); Wu and Kanamori (2008b); Wu and Kanamori (2005); Zollo et al. (2010, 2016)

5.3.5 Decision Module for Alert Notification

Decisions to trigger alerts in current EEW systems may be based on estimates of magnitude only (Table 18), magnitude and epicentral distance of target sites (Table 19), or ground motion amplitude estimates (Table 20). The most common decision variable used is seismic intensity (Table 21). It measures the observed effects of ground shaking, such as the degree to which it is felt or the extent

of damage experienced by household contents and is measured using a scale (e.g., Wood and Neumann 1931).

Damage- and loss-orientated approaches to EEW decision-making have also been proposed in the literature, but have not been implemented in any of the existing EEW systems around the world. For example, Le Guenan et al. (2016) developed a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methodology to select a trigger threshold for a bridge that was derived from a critical probability of bridge damage. Wu et al. (2016) used the framework of Wu et al. (2013) to investigate an EEW system that triggers an alert based on losses quantified as casualties due to people trapped in elevators. Further examples of damage-driven EEW studies include Fabozzi et al. (2018); Mitrani-Resier et al. (2016); and Salzano et al. (2009), while additional examples of loss-driven EEW studies are Wang et al. (2012), Picozzi et al. (2013), as well as the performance-based EEW (PBEEW) approach proposed in Manfredi and Zollo (2006), Iervolino et al. (2007), and Iervolino (2011).

Table 18: Triggering alerts based on magnitude.

Description of method		
A warning is triggered if the magnitude estimate exceeds a certain threshold.		
Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
Magnitude estimate	Warning trigger (yes/no)	SASMEX (Mexico); KEEWS (Korea); EDAS-MAS (China); Beijing EEW system (China)
Key references		
Cuéllar et al. (2017); Dong-Hoon et al. (2017); Peng et al. (2013); Peng et al. (2011); Sheen et al. (2014); Suárez et al. (2009)		

Table 19: Triggering alerts based on magnitude and epicentral distance.

Description of method		
Epicentral distances to target sites of interest are first computed based on earthquake location estimates. The magnitude and distance estimates are compared with magnitude-epicentral distance maps of predicted damage; if they lie within the portion of the map where damage is predicted, a warning is triggered.		
Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
Magnitude estimate; Location estimate	Warning trigger (yes/no)	UrEDAS (Japan)
Key References		
Nakamura and Saita (2007); Nakamura (1988)		

Table 20: Triggering alerts based on ground motion amplitude.

Description of method

Warnings are triggered based on potentially damaging levels of ground motion amplitude, which can be measured in various ways, e.g. PGA or cumulative absolute velocity (i.e. the time integral of the absolute acceleration over the duration of the earthquake record).

Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
Ground motion amplitude estimate (e.g. PGA)	Warning trigger (yes/no)	OnSite (USA); PRESTo (USA/Switzerland); IEEWS (Turkey); Virtual Seismologist (Japan); Compact UrEDAS

Key references

Alcik et al. (2009); Böse et al. (2009); Cua (2005); Cua and Heaton (2007); Erdik et al. (2003); Nakamura and Saita (2007); Oth et al. (2010); Satriano et al. (2011a)

Table 21: Triggering alerts based on calculated seismic intensity.

Description of method

Seismic intensity is calculated from characteristics of the event waveform (e.g. peak ground motion amplitude) observed at seismic stations using empirical equations. Warnings are triggered in a region if the estimated seismic intensity exceeds a certain value on the corresponding seismic intensity scale.

Inputs	Outputs	Relevant algorithms
Ground motion/seismic waveform information (e.g. PGV)	Seismic intensity estimate; Warning trigger (yes/no)	ElarmS (USA, Chile, Israel); PRESTo ^{Plus} (Italy); JMA (Japan); PLUM (Japan); eBEAR (Taiwan); REWS (Romania)

Key references

Zollo et al. (2010); Colombelli and Zollo (2016); Minson et al. (2018); Allen and Melgar (2019); Liu and Yamada (2014); Hoshiha et al. 2008; Wald et al. (1999); Meier (2017); Auclair et al. (2015); Allen et al. (2009); Picozzi et al. (2015); Colombelli et al. (2012); Ruhl et al. (2019); Colombelli et al. (2013); Kubo et al. (2011); Wurman et al. (2007); Kamigaichi (2004); Chen et al. (2015); Böse et al. (2007)

5.4 Limitations of the State-of-the-Art

It should be clear from the summary tables above that the most cutting-edge innovations in current EEW applications concern the seismological aspects of the system (i.e. steps 1-3 of the EEW process). For this reason, we concentrate on the decision-making component of EEW systems in this section, specifically through an end-user lens. While definitions of early warning explicitly refer to its potential to mitigate damage and loss (Table 22), it is obvious from the above that decisions to trigger EEW alerts are not currently made with risk-related metrics. The closest proxies for risk used are the ground-motion amplitude and macroseismic intensity measures, which both capture the effects of ground shaking. However, the considered threshold values are not calibrated based on explicit damage or loss analysis. More generally, there are a number of limitations associated with end-user-decision-making based on this type of metric.

Table 22: Risk-related terms included in definitions of early warning for natural hazards.

Words included	Key references
“risk”	Heaton (1985); Zollo, et al. (2015); Emolo et al. (2016); Bründl and Sturny (2014); Medina-Cetina and Nadim (2008); de Leon et al. (2013); Pate-Cornell (1986); Sättele et al. (2016); Iervolino et al. (2007)
“damage”	Satriano et al. (2011); Sättele et al. (2015); Krzysztofowicz et al. (1994); Minson et al. (2019); Zollo et al. (2014); Colombelli and Zollo (2016); Goltz (2002); Kong et al. (2016); Allen and Melgar (2019)
“loss”	UNISDR (2009); Satriano et al. (2011); Sättele et al. (2015); Wang et al. (2012); Convertito et al. (2008)
“harm”	UNISDR (2009); Strauss and Allen (2016); Pittore et al. (2014)
“vulnerability”	Emolo et al. (2016); Manfredi and Zollo (2006)

Firstly, there is an explicit assumption that a given level of ground shaking will result in a specific degree of damage. In reality, however, the relationship between ground shaking and damage at a target site is highly uncertain (e.g., Cremen and Baker 2019). In addition, regional EEW-system decision-making (e.g., by a highway authority) based on ground shaking does not account for varying levels of fragility across the affected area, i.e. the fact that damage probability and severity for a given level of ground motion is not the same across different types of structures, infrastructures and systems. Failure to account for uncertainty in damage may lead to a miscalculation in false (or missed) alarm potential.

To illustrate this, we take Figure 1A in Minson et al. (2019), which depicts the performance of an EEW system that triggers alerts for ground motions exceeding $10\%g$ when the expected ground motion is $20\%g$. In keeping with convention (Porter et al. 2007), the fragility function (i.e. the probability of damage conditioned on ground motion amplitude) associated with a target structure is assumed to be a lognormal cumulative distribution function. We assume that the median of the function is the expected ground motion of $20\%g$. The dispersion is taken as 0.6, which is in line with values used for real-life structural fragility functions (FEMA 2012). We have superimposed this fragility function on the probability distribution of ground shaking values from Minson et al. (2019) in Figure 7. The red shading refers to potentially observed ground motion values that would lead to a false alert according to Minson et al. (2019) (i.e. that are below the $10\%g$ threshold), and the green shading indicates ground motion values that would lead to a correct alert. Hatched areas in the figure identify values that may result in an opposite alert to that determined in Minson et al. (2019), when uncertainty in damage is also considered. It is particularly interesting to note that the red hatched area, which refers to the probability of no damage (i.e. false alert) across ground motion values that were originally labelled as returning a correct alert, is significant. For this hypothetical case, it is clear that the probability of false alarm is notably higher than that obtained from ground motion predictions alone, when uncertainty in damage is also considered. Failure to accurately predict false alert probability is an important limitation of ground motion-based decision metrics, as false alarms can have substantial economic impacts (e.g. due to business interruption) and affect large communities (e.g. due to an emergency lifeline stoppage), and their frequent occurrence can significantly decrease the value of warning information (Fritz et al. 2008).

Figure 7: Illustration of potential false alarms, when ground shaking amplitude is used as an EEW decision metric, using data from Figure 1A of (Minson et al. 2019). Red and green shaded areas, respectively, indicate false and correct alerts identified by Minson et al. (2019). Red and green hatched areas refer to the case in which a hypothetical fragility function for the target site is also accounted for.

Another notable limitation of ground shaking-related decision metrics is their failure to explicitly consider losses, which are additionally uncertain with respect to damage e.g., Martins et al. (2016). Accounting for losses as well as damage would therefore further amplify the potential miscalculation of false alarms from ground shaking found in Figure 7. Distinction between losses is also important for optimal decision-making. For example, a business owner may be more interested in measuring the value of an alert based on its ability to mitigate building downtime (business interruption) than the cost of repair after an event; ground shaking decision-based metrics are not useful in this instance. Finally, descriptions of an event in terms of magnitude, ground motion or macroseismic intensity are difficult to understand for the public (Allen and Melgar 2019). Confusion in the meaning of an alert makes the public less likely to take preventative action (Goltz 2002), which decreases the value of a warning. To maximise the benefits of alerts, they should be paired with robust messaging (Cochran and Husker 2019), which is best achieved using risk-orientated decision metrics (e.g., consequences).

5.5 Suggested Future End-User-Orientated Advances

The discussion above suggests that there is a strong need to develop next-generation end-user-orientated EEW systems that significantly advance the state-of-the-art in EEW decision support. These systems should trigger alerts based on interpretable probabilistic risk-based estimates that are optimised for the needs of – and are understandable to – a given end user, so that clear preventative actions can be taken to mitigate the impact of the event. Using earthquake engineering expertise, fragility and vulnerability or damage-to-loss models for target structures and infrastructure components should be combined with ground motion amplitude predictions from the scientific entity responsible for EEW to determine end-user-focused estimates of damage and loss (Figure 8). Since the engineering models represent a static piece of information (with respect to the EEW-based seismic hazard estimates), these combinations can be conveniently pre-computed offline for all possible ground motion amplitude estimates and then simply retrieved in real-time for rapid decision-making, following Iervolino (2011).

For well-informed decision-making on EEW triggering, we suggest that next-generation EEW systems should be developed based on a robust end-to-end theoretical framework that explicitly tracks uncertainties at each stage of the EEW process, such as the PBEEW approach mentioned above. This framework utilizes the concept of real-time PSHA (RTPSHA), where the probability density function of an intensity measure is conditioned on real-time seismic measurements that are related to the probability distributions of the source parameters. (Note that RTPSHA could easily be adapted to include additional conditional information, such as updated estimates of source parameters from operational earthquake forecasting calculations). This type of probabilistic approach is rarely used in current EEW applications. From the summary given above, Virtual Seismologist is the only existing algorithm that propagates uncertainties in the source parameters through to ground shaking estimation (although its estimations may be too slow for real-time applications; Chung and Allen 2019). RTPSHA is mathematically extended to a performance-based framework, to also quantify expected dollar losses in terms of the source-dependent real-time seismic measurements.

Figure 8: Conceptual overview of a suggested next-generation EEW system for a given end user (e.g., highway operator). Leveraging earthquake engineering expertise, this type of system translates ground motion amplitudes predicted by the scientific entity responsible for EEW (i.e. the current state-of-the-art) to damage and various loss

metrics using application-specific fragility functions and vulnerability functions or damage-to-loss models. This facilitates risk-orientated decision-making that satisfies the needs of the end-user and results in robust messaging that enables clear preventative actions to be taken. These systems are underpinned by a probabilistic end-to-end theoretical framework that explicitly tracks uncertainties at each stage of the EEW process. For EEW applications to network-based components (e.g., roads), system-level consequences and resilience metrics are captured by accounting for interdependencies in losses across individual target sites.

We suggest combining PBEEW with an EEW-adapted version of the MCDM methodology presented in Caterino et al. (2008; 2009). This methodology evaluates a group of alternative actions ($\{A_i\}$) for seismic structural retrofitting, based on a set of criteria ($\{I_j\}$) that are weighted ($\{w_j\}$) in importance according to end-user preferences. The explicit consideration of such preferences would improve the current dollar loss-based decision-making procedure of PBEEW. The proposed approach would also remove the requirement for criteria to be exclusively expressed in monetary terms. We now demonstrate integration of both PBEEW and MCDM for the case of a hypothetical school. Potential end users in this case include children, their parents, the headteacher, and local public officials.

The alternative set of actions for EEW-focused MCDM are: A_1 : "Trigger an EEW Alarm" and A_2 : "on't Trigger an EEW Alarm". The school-specific criteria for assessing the feasibility of each action can be measured using the indicators shown in the last column of the decision framework presented in Figure 9. Note that since this is a hypothetical framework, the criteria included are not exhaustive. For example, the cost of installing and maintaining the EEW is neglected for simplicity; however, this may be an important consideration for school stakeholders in a realistic scenario. We can represent the values of the indicators (for each criterion) associated with each action in the form of a consequence matrix as demonstrated in Table 23.

Table 23: Example consequence matrix for decision-making on EEW triggering in a hypothetical school.

	I_1 Injuries (number)	I_2 Downtime (days)	I_3 Direct Cost (\$)
A_1	Expected injuries due to estimated earthquake that cannot be reduced with EEW	Expected disruption due to potential false alarm + expected downtime due to estimated earthquake that cannot be reduced with EEW	Expected restoration cost due to potential false alarm + expected repair cost due to estimated earthquake that cannot be reduced with EEW
A_2	Estimated injuries due to estimated earthquake	Expected downtime due to estimated earthquake	Expected repair cost due to estimated earthquake

The quantification of the indicators for a given action A_i is conditioned on time-dependent physical measurements of the seismic network (\mathbf{d}), which comprise the vectors of information used to estimate magnitude (i.e., τ) and location (i.e., s) defined in Iervolino et al. (2007), i.e.:

$$E^{A_i}(I_j^{A_i}|\mathbf{d}) = \int_{I_j^{A_i}} \int_{DM} \int_{IM} i_j^{A_i} f(i_j^{A_i}|dm)f(dm|im)f(im|\mathbf{d}) dI_j^{A_i} dDM dIM \quad (5-1)$$

This equation can be computed offline for all possible estimates of \mathbf{d} ; thus, the only real-time activity involved is the selection of an appropriate value based on event-specific information. $E^{A_i}(I_j^{A_i}|\mathbf{d})$ is the expected value of the j th indicator for action A_i and the seismic measurements at a given time,

$f(a|b)$ is the conditional probability density function of a given b , dm is the damage state of the school, im is the considered intensity measure and $f(dm|im)$ is derived from an appropriate fragility model. $f(i_j^{A_i}|dm)$ is derived from a damage-to-loss (or consequence) model, where losses and consequences are broadly defined to include non-monetary considerations such as injuries and downtime. Note that models for $f(i_j^{A_1}|dm)$ (i.e., when the EEW alarm is triggered) are case-specific, and may be obtained from consultations with stakeholders or from expert engineering judgement for most practical applications. They may also be equivalent to $f(i_j^{A_2}|dm)$ in certain situations. This is foreseeable in the case of direct cost (I_3) for example, since EEW may not be able to reduce any dollar losses associated with a given level of damage. More advanced resilience-orientated decision-making could be facilitated by deriving indicator values directly from IMs following the limit-state approach of Burton et al. (2016), who developed fragility functions that enable ground motion intensity to be translated straight to post-earthquake functionality and recovery consequences. These resilience-based metrics have been successfully applied to support post-earthquake decision-making in previous studies (Burton et al. 2018; Burton et al. 2019).

Figure 9: A suggested decision framework for determining end-user criteria of interest to the application of EEW systems in schools.

The consequence matrix of Table 23 is translated to a decision matrix (Table 24) by accounting for importance weights $\{w_j\}$ (i.e., end-user preferences) and normalising indicator values. The values of each weight can be obtained, for instance, through an end-user pairwise comparison analysis across all criteria, according to the analytic hierarchy process (Saaty 2002). Finally, the optimal decision can be determined based on the TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) method (Yoon and Hwang 1995), in which the best action to take (at a given time) is deemed to be the one that minimises the highest number of weighted normalised values (in Table 24) across all criteria. The proposed decision-making approach results in a probabilistic dynamic decision-support system for real-time seismic risk management.

Table 24: Example consequence matrix for decision-making on EEW triggering in a hypothetical school.

	I_1 Injuries (Number)	I_2 Downtime (days)	I_3 Direct Cost (\$)
A_1	$\frac{E^{A_1}(I_1^{A_1} \mathbf{d})}{\sqrt{E^{A_1}(I_1^{A_1} \mathbf{d})^2 + E^{A_2}(I_1^{A_2} \mathbf{d})^2}} * w_1$	$\frac{E^{A_1}(I_2^{A_1} \mathbf{d})}{\sqrt{E^{A_1}(I_2^{A_1} \mathbf{d})^2 + E^{A_2}(I_2^{A_2} \mathbf{d})^2}} * w_2$	$\frac{E^{A_1}(I_3^{A_1} \mathbf{d})}{\sqrt{E^{A_1}(I_3^{A_1} \mathbf{d})^2 + E^{A_2}(I_3^{A_2} \mathbf{d})^2}} * w_3$

$$A_2 \frac{E^{A_2}(I_1^{A_2}|\mathbf{d})}{\sqrt{E^{A_1}(I_1^{A_1}|\mathbf{d})^2 + E^{A_2}(I_1^{A_2}|\mathbf{d})^2}} * w_1 \quad \frac{E^{A_2}(I_2^{A_2}|\mathbf{d})}{\sqrt{E^{A_1}(I_2^{A_1}|\mathbf{d})^2 + E^{A_2}(I_2^{A_2}|\mathbf{d})^2}} * w_2 \quad \frac{E^{A_2}(I_3^{A_2}|\mathbf{d})}{\sqrt{E^{A_1}(I_3^{A_1}|\mathbf{d})^2 + E^{A_2}(I_3^{A_2}|\mathbf{d})^2}} * w_3$$

A key limitation of existing damage- and loss-focused studies related to EEW is their narrow focus on one target site (and generally one target structure) of interest. However, system-level consequences are also important to consider for EEW applications to network-based components. For example, the threshold for triggering an alert to shut down a vehicular bridge should explicitly account for an indicator that measures the resulting decrease in functionality across the entire road network. Thus (where relevant), next-generation EEW systems should incorporate decision-making tools that capture interdependencies in losses. This could be achieved using mathematical tools developed for seismic engineering-related network analyses (e.g., Argyroudis et al. 2015; Lam et al. 2018).

As a significant advancement over current EEW approaches, next-generation EEW systems should consider leveraging more advanced IMs from the scientific entity in charge of EEW, such as spectral-shape-based IM or inelastic spectral acceleration values at a range of prescribed periods (e.g., Minas and Galasso 2019) when calculating predicted earthquake ground motion for RTPSHA and consequent loss estimates. This would notably enhance EEW suitability to risk-based engineering applications, as these IMs are much better correlated with structural response, damage and loss than those typically considered for EEW such as PGA or PGV (e.g., Shome et al. 1998). For example, it would enable interaction between EEW systems and structural control mechanisms that could rapidly alter the behaviour of a building in response to the forecasted spectral acceleration at the structure's fundamental period, which may reduce the structural vulnerability (and resulting losses). This would be particularly beneficial in critical buildings required to be operational for emergency management immediately after an event (such as hospitals and fire stations). Preliminary attempts to combine EEW and structural control exist in the literature (Maddaloni et al. 2011; Velazquez et al. 2017), however they rely on simplified structural models and there is poor statistical significance in the results. Future related studies should make use of more advanced (i.e. state-of-the-art nonlinear 3D) structural modelling techniques and account for proper treatment of uncertainty in the IMs via the RTPSHA framework (Convertito et al. 2008). Consideration of spectral acceleration values in RTPSHA would also allow ground shaking outputs of EEW systems to be combined with information from on-site structural health monitoring systems. This could result in more accurate rapid response (and therefore damage and loss) estimates (Cremen and Baker 2018), leading to more effective decision-making on the triggering of planned mitigation actions (e.g. controlling elevators, alerting occupants).

Up to now, evaluations of EEW systems have concentrated on the performance of magnitude predictions (e.g., Peng et al. 2013), ground shaking forecasts (e.g., Zollo et al. 2009) and macroseismic intensity estimates (e.g., Cochran et al. 2018), while optimisation of the systems has also considered the extent of the blind-zone (i.e. the size of the region that is too close to the epicentre to receive a warning in time; Kuyuk and Allen 2013). However, next-generation EEW systems should instead be analysed with explicit consideration of the risk-based variables incorporated within the decision support system component of various end users. For example, optimisation of seismic station locations could be based on minimising different types of damage and loss uncertainty observed within the blind zone, rather than simply focusing on its size. The optimal solution could furthermore be weighted in favour of stakeholders with the most urgent needs for timely and accurate consequence estimates, such as hospital managers and high-speed railway authorities.

5.6 Conclusions

Earthquake early warning is a relatively new innovation in seismology and earthquake engineering, with significant potential to increase the resilience of societies to seismic risk. It is currently operating in nine countries and is being or has been tested for operation in 13 more. This section has reviewed state-of-the-art approaches to EEW, including the various algorithms that have been developed for completing the four main steps involved, i.e., (1) detecting an event and estimating its location; (2) estimating the event magnitude, (3) estimating the resulting ground shaking; and (4) deciding whether to trigger an alarm based on the previous information.

Our review identified that modern advancements in EEW applications have been largely concentrated within the seismological aspects of the system, i.e., steps 1-3 of the previous paragraph; for example, recent notable applied EEW research efforts have focused on developing innovative finite-fault approaches for estimating magnitude that result in significantly better estimates of the size of an ongoing event than previously proposed magnitude estimation methods. On the other hand, we found that current methods for end-user-decision-making related to the triggering of alerts in EEW systems are relatively simplistic and do not explicitly account for risk. Risk-based (engineering-related) decision metrics are important to consider, since they accurately capture uncertainty in the damage and losses or consequences that result from a given level of ground shaking and can be used to provide informative, robust descriptions of an event that encourage the public to take preventative action.

We provided a number of suggestions for future advances in EEW, including the development of next-generation EEW systems that trigger interpretable alerts based on probabilistic risk-based estimates optimised for the preferences of the stakeholder. This type of system could be designed based on the findings of the few previous studies that have focused on damage- and loss-driven EEW approaches. In particular, we suggest implementing the robust theoretical loss-based framework of PBEEW, which explicitly tracks uncertainties at each stage in EEW, and improving its decision-making capabilities by also leveraging the MCDM methodology detailed in Caterino et al. (2009; 2008). This type of decision-making approach could be integrated into future EEW algorithms to determine optimal actions, considering multiple (weighted) criteria of interest to an end user that do not necessarily need to be measured in terms of monetary value. The result would be a novel dynamic real-time decision-support-and-risk management system aimed at resilient structure and infrastructure. Where relevant, the decision-making approach of next-generation EEW systems should also account for interdependencies in system-level losses across a region and more engineering-orientated IMs (e.g., elastic and inelastic spectral ordinates), which would transform EEW into a credible tool for seismic resilience assessment and promotion.

5.7 Acronyms

Table 25: Explanation of acronyms used throughout Section 5.

Acronym	Explanation
BEFORES	Bayesian Evidence-based Fault Orientation and Real-time Earthquake Slip
eBEAR	Earthworm Based Earthquake Alarm Reporting
EDAS-MAS	No explanation available in the literature
EEW	Earthquake Early Warning

ElarmS	Earthquake Alarm Systems
FinDER	Finite-Fault Rupture Detector
G-FAST	Geodetic First Approximation of Size and Time
G-larmS	Geodetic Alarm System
GMM	Ground-Motion Model
GPS	Global Positioning Systems
IM	Intensity Measure
IEEWS	Istanbul Earthquake Early Warning System
JMA	Japan Meteorological Agency
KEEWS	Korean Earthquake Early Warning System
MCDM	Mutli-Criteria Decision-Making
PBEEW	Performance-Based Earthquake Early Warning
PGA	Peak Ground Acceleration
PGD	Peak Ground Displacement
PGV	Peak Ground Velocity
PLUM	Propagation of Local Undamped Motion
PRESto	PRobabilistic and Evolutionary early warning SysTem
REGARD	Real-time GEONET Analysis system for Rapid Deformation monitoring
REWS	Rapid Early Warning System
RTPSHA	Real-Time Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Analysis
SASMEX	Sistema de Alerta Sísmica Mexicano
UrEDAS	Urgent Earthquake Detection and Alarm System

6 CURRENT SITUATION OF RRE SYSTEMS OPERATING IN EUROPE

This section presents a review of various RRE systems worldwide, with a focus on European coverage, especially the test bed areas. RRE systems are discussed in the light of two successive steps, namely the rapid generation of ground-motion maps at the sites of interest (i.e., shake-maps, in Section 6.1) and the rapid estimation of earthquake effects and losses (in Section 6.2). Current gaps and pending issues are then discussed in Section 6.3.

6.1 Review of shake-map systems

As opposed to predictive ground-motions scenarios, shake-maps refer to updated ground-motion maps that make the most of the available post-earthquake information in order to constrain uncertainties on expected ground-motion levels.

Therefore, the generation of shake-maps usually requires the following data and models:

- parameters of the earthquake event (e.g., faulting mechanism, magnitude, location);
- predictive models that estimate ground-motion distributions, such as ground-motion prediction equations (GMPEs) or intensity prediction equations (IPEs);
- accurate soil amplification models, in order to account for site effects at specific locations;
- on-site observations of the ground-motion, usually through strong-motion measurements from seismic stations or through macroseismic testimonies from citizens;
- an algorithm that updates the predictive models with the observations in order to generate the shake-map along with uncertainty fields.

6.1.1 The USGS ShakeMap[®] algorithm

The most widespread and elaborate shake-map system is the one operated by the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS), thanks to developments by Wald et al. (1999) and Wald et al. (2006). In its version 3.5, it is based on a weighted interpolation algorithm (Worden et al. 2010), which follows the main steps described below:

- collection of observations (i.e., ground-motion measurements and macroseismic intensities) and application of site amplification factors in order to revert the measurements from soil conditions to rock conditions;
- application of a GMPE in order to estimate mean ground-motion parameters at the locations of observations by using the characteristics of the earthquake;
- computation of the global bias introduced by the observations with respect to the initial GMPE estimates: the bias is corrected by finding the magnitude that reduces the errors between the observed and the predicted ground motions, when the GMPE is evaluated for the adjusted magnitude;
- application of the bias-adjusted GMPE in order to estimate corrected ground parameters over a spatial grid;

- at each grid point, updating of the ground-motion parameter of interest through a weighted average between the bias-adjusted GMPE estimate and the interpolated observations: the GMPE estimate is weighted by the inverse of the variance provided by the GMPE, while each observation is weighted by the term $1/\sigma_{obs}^2$ (i.e., σ_{obs} is the standard deviation assigned to the observation - it increases with the distance between the observation and the grid point based on a correlation model);
- in the case when macroseismic intensities are exploited as observations, a Ground-Motion-Intensity Conversion Equation (GMICE) is used in order to obtain ground-motion estimates, at the cost of an additional uncertainty source (i.e., the standard deviation related to the GMICE);
- application of site amplification factors at the grid points, in order to convert the ground-motion parameters from rock conditions to the actual soil conditions of the area.

Figure 10: Schematic view of the successive steps involved in the ShakeMap® v3.5 algorithm (source Worden and Wald, 2016)).

Based on the interpolation scheme proposed by Worden et al. (2010), the mean updated ground-motion parameter Y at grid point (x,y) is expressed as:

$$\overline{Y}_{xy} = \frac{Y_{GMPE,xy} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{Y_{obs,xy,i}}{\sigma_{obs,xy,i}^2} + \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{Y_{convobs,xy,j}}{\sigma_{convobs,xy,j}^2}}{\frac{1}{\sigma_{GMPE}^2} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_{obs,xy,i}^2} + \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{\sigma_{convobs,xy,j}^2}} \quad (6-1)$$

where $Y_{GMPE,xy}$ is the bias-corrected GMPE estimate at the point (x,y) , and $Y_{obs,xy,i}$ (resp. $Y_{convobs,xy,j}$) is the i^{th} ground-motion measurement out of n (respectively the j^{th} macroseismic observation out of m)

scaled to the point (x,y) . The scaling from the observation's location to each grid point (x,y) is performed using the relative source-to-distance factors provided by the GMPE:

$$\begin{cases} Y_{obs,xy,i} = Y_{obs,i} \times \left(\frac{Y_{GMPE,xy}}{Y_{GMPE,obs,i}} \right) \\ Y_{convobs,xy,j} = Y_{convobs,j} \times \left(\frac{Y_{GMPE,xy}}{Y_{GMPE,convobs,j}} \right) \end{cases} \quad (6-2)$$

Similarly, the total variance of the updated ground-motion parameter Y at grid point (x,y) is expressed as:

$$\sigma_{Y,xy}^2 = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{\sigma_{GMPE}^2} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_{obs,xy,i}^2} + \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{\sigma_{convobs,xy,j}^2}} \quad (6-3)$$

where σ_{GMPE} is the standard deviation of the intra-event error term associated with the GMPE (when enough observations are present, it is assumed that the inter-event error term is well enough constrained by the bias correction). $\sigma_{obs,xy,i}$ is the standard deviation associated with an observation location at a given distance d from the grid point (x,y) : for instance, $\sigma_{obs,xy,i} = \sigma_{GMPE} \cdot f(d)$, where f is a function decreasing with distance d . Usually, if d tends towards zero, $\sigma_{obs,xy,i}$ tends towards zero as well (i.e., the observed value becomes the dominant term in the near field); and if d tends towards infinity, $\sigma_{obs,xy,i}$ likewise tends towards infinity (i.e., the GMPE estimate becomes the dominant in the far field). The functional form and values taken by f depends on the spatial correlation model that is associated with the ground-motion parameter of interest. By default, Worden et al. (2010) propose a radius of 10 km, within which $\sigma_{obs,xy,i} < \sigma_{GMPE}$; a second radius of 15 km is defined, beyond which it is assumed that $\sigma_{obs,xy,i} = \infty$. However, the proper calibration of these distances for a specific site is not detailed.

On the other hand, the standard deviation $\sigma_{convobs,xy,j}$, related to the uncertainty associated with macroseismic observations, is decomposed into the distance-based standard deviation $\sigma_{obs,xy,j}$ (as detailed above), and the standard deviation of the GMICE (uncertainty from converting the macroseismic intensity into a ground-motion parameter):

$$\sigma_{convobs,xy,j}^2 = \sigma_{obs,xy,j}^2 + \sigma_{conv}^2 \quad (6-4)$$

The simple equations used by the algorithm prevent the build-up of computational complexity, since the optimization of Eq. 6-1 allows for the computation time to remain linearly proportional to the number of grid points (Worden et al. 2010). This shake-map system is flexible enough to produce updated maps of various types of ground-motion parameters (e.g., PGA, PGV, SA at different periods), as long as the ad-hoc GMPEs are available. Shake-maps in terms of macroseismic intensity are also provided, thus making direct use of the macroseismic testimonies that are collected after the earthquake event.

It should be noted that the recent version change of ShakeMap[®] (from version 3.5 to 4) has introduced a different interpolation scheme (Worden et al. 2018), namely the use of the multi-variate normal (MVN) distribution (Vanmarcke 1983; Stafford 2012). The vector of ground-motion parameters \mathbf{Y} (assumed to be normally distributed) is divided into \mathbf{Y}_1 (m prediction sites or grid points) and \mathbf{Y}_2 (n observations sites) with the following expressions for mean and variance:

$$\mu_{\mathbf{Y}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{Y_1} \\ \mu_{Y_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \Sigma_{\mathbf{Y}} = \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{Y_1 Y_1} & \Sigma_{Y_1 Y_2} \\ \Sigma_{Y_2 Y_1} & \Sigma_{Y_2 Y_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6-5)$$

Subsequently, given a set of observations $\mathbf{Y}_2 = \mathbf{y}_2$, a vector of residuals is defined as $\zeta = \mathbf{y}_2 - \mu_{Y_2}$. Thanks to the MVN, it is possible to express the mean and variance of the set of predictions \mathbf{Y}_1 as follows:

$$\mu_{Y_1|y_2} = \mu_{Y_1} + \Sigma_{Y_1 Y_2} \cdot \Sigma_{Y_2 Y_2}^{-1} \cdot \zeta \quad (6-6)$$

$$\Sigma_{Y_1 Y_2|y_2} = \Sigma_{Y_1 Y_1} - \Sigma_{Y_1 Y_2} \cdot \Sigma_{Y_2 Y_2}^{-1} \cdot \Sigma_{Y_2 Y_1} \quad (6-7)$$

The initial mean values of \mathbf{Y}_1 are obtained from a GMPE, and the variance-covariance matrix is assembled from the standard deviations associated with the GMPE and from the spatial correlation structure of the ground-motion parameter(s) of interest. Therefore, the results from Eq. 6-6 and 6-7 may be directly used as the updated ground-motion distribution for the generation of the shake-map. Worden et al. (2018) show in addition that this approach enables the consideration of multiple types of ground-motion parameters (e.g., PGA, SA at different periods) simultaneously: thanks to the cross-correlation structure among some ground-motion parameters (especially response spectral ordinates), it is possible to gain knowledge and constrain shake-maps even if only parameters of a given type have been recorded.

Some example of maps generated with the ShakeMap[®] v4 software are shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12.

SHAKING	Not felt	Weak	Light	Moderate	Strong	Very strong	Severe	Violent	Extreme
DAMAGE	None	None	None	Very light	Light	Moderate	Moderate/heavy	Heavy	Very heavy
PGA(%g)	<0.05	0.3	2.76	6.2	11.5	21.5	40.1	74.7	>139
PGV(cm/s)	<0.02	0.13	1.41	4.65	9.64	20	41.4	85.8	>178
INTENSITY	I	II-III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X+

Scale based on Worden et al. (2012)

Version 4: Processed 2019-08-16T21:08:59Z

△ Seismic Instrument ○ Reported Intensity

★ Epicenter □ Rupture

Figure 11: ShakeMap® in intensity for the Mw 6.4 Ridgecrest earthquake of July 4th 2019 (source USGS).

Figure 12: ShakeMap® in PGA for the Mw 6.4 Ridgecrest earthquake of July 4th 2019 (source USGS).

While very straightforward in theory, the ShakeMap® process in practice requires an accurate knowledge of several parameters and models:

- The selected GMPE and GMICE have an influence on the distribution of the ground-motion field, and the chosen models should be adapted to the specific area of interest.
- The knowledge of the finite fault is an essential factor: in the case of large earthquakes, a fault-source model (instead of a point-source) is required in order to better constrain near-field ground motions. However, such models may not be defined until several hours following the earthquake, leading to substantial uncertainties in the earlier versions of the shake-map.
- An accurate map of soil classes, associated to $V_{s,30}$ values or site amplification factors, is crucial in order to properly estimate the expected level of ground shaking.
- The radius of influence of observations (e.g., ratio between $\sigma_{obs,xy,i}$ and σ_{GMPE} used in version 3.5) has a strong influence on the local shape of the shake-map; and further sensitivity studies should be performed in order to assess its link with the spatial correlation of the ground-motion parameters.

- Finally, other parameters of the algorithm pertain to the seismic stations that are to be considered for the computation of the bias (i.e., global level of the shake-map): a selection is usually made based on a cut-off distance from the epicentre (i.e. far-field stations are screened out) or on a significant deviation of the observation from the initial GMPE estimate. The calibration of such choices deserves further investigations.

6.1.2 Alternative ground-motion inference methods

Apart from the above-detailed interpolation methods, other ways of generating shake-maps have been investigated by Douglas (2007). The methods are classified according to whether they take account of the spatial correlation of the ground-motion field. Among the methods ignoring the spatial correlation of shaking, the following ones are worth mentioning:

- *Unadjusted GMPE accounting for site effects*: this method merely consists in the application of a GMPE to the parameters of the earthquake event, while adding amplification factors to the soil conditions.
- *Bias-corrected GMPE accounting for site effects*: based on the ground-motion measurements, a global bias adjustment is performed on the GMPE, in order to account for the actual inter-event variation. This approach is similar to the bias adjustment performed in the ShakeMap[®] algorithm.
- *Derivation of an event-specific GMPE*: if there are sufficient ground-motion measurements, a specific GMPE with a simple functional form may be regressed from the data in order to account for both the rate of decay and the inter-event bias.

Additionally, two methods accounting for the spatial correction of shaking are detailed by Douglas (2007):

- *Universal kriging*: this is a geostatistical method that consists of kriging with a drift model, which accounts for data (i.e., the ground-motion measurements) and an underlying trend (i.e., decay with the epicentral distance). An exponential semi-variogram with a distance parameter a (which needs to be defined) is used in order to model the spatial correlation between the observations and the sites of interest.
- *Adapted method of King et al. (2004)*: observations are weighted with respect to their distance to the sites of interest, and a GMPE is used for correcting differences in epicentral distance (between the sites and the observations).

In Douglas (2007), all these methods are tested on ground-motion data from the 2004 Les Saintes earthquake (Guadeloupe, France) and the results are compared to the ones obtained using the ShakeMap[®] approach. It is found that the more elaborate methods accounting for spatial correlation are associated with lower aleatory variability and provided similar results in the vicinity of observations. However, at locations more than 10 km away from the nearest observation, much larger uncertainties (both aleatory and epistemic) are observed, with little leeway to better constrain the ground-motion field.

Various geostatistical interpolation techniques (e.g., kriging and cokriging methods) have also been benchmarked by Costanzo (2018) in order to derive shake-maps in terms of Arias intensity and cumulative absolute velocity for the M_w 6.0 Amatrice and the M_w 6.5 Norcia earthquakes, which both occurred in 2016. A comparison of the author's maps – based on various modelling assumptions – with the official shake-maps published following the two events has led to the identification of

current needs for the further improvement of shake-maps: extended regression models between macroseismic intensity and ground-motion parameters, introduction of local site effects, and integration of near-source effects when converting ground-motion parameters to macroseismic intensity.

In parallel, Gehl et al. (2017) have proposed an approach based on Bayesian updating of correlated Gaussian fields: the prior distribution of the ground-motion field, consisting of a simple predictive scenario of the earthquake event with a GMPE, is updated with the observations in order to generate a posterior distribution of the ground motion at each grid point. To this end, a Gaussian Bayesian Network (BN) models the distribution of a given ground-motion parameter Y at each grid point i (see Figure 13). Thanks to the lognormal assumption used in most GMPEs, a lognormal-normal conversion is able to express the conditional probability of Y_i as a normal distribution, with the mean expressed as:

$$\mu(Y_i|\mathbf{U}, W) = X_i + \sigma_\zeta \cdot \sum_{j=i}^n t_{ij} \cdot U_j + \sigma_\eta \cdot W \quad , \quad (6-8)$$

where X_i is the mean estimate of the ground-motion parameter from the GMPE, σ_ζ is the standard deviation of the intra-event term, and σ_η is the standard deviation of the inter-event term. The matrix of elements t_{ij} results from the Cholesky decomposition of the correlation matrix between the intra-event terms: spatial correlation models such as the one from Jayaram and Baker (2009) may be used to compute this correlation, based on the distances between all grid points and observations. The variables U_j and W follow a standard normal distribution and they are essential to model the statistical dependence between the Y_i , and consequently the updating process.

Figure 13: Illustration of a BN structure for the generation of a shake-map, with nine grid points $Y(.)$ and two observations Y_{obs} . $Y(i)$ represents the distribution of the ground-motion parameter at grid point i .

Observations, either in the form of ground-motion measurements or macroseismic intensities (with the associated uncertainties), are added to the BN as evidence. Subsequently, the posterior distribution of the ground-motion parameters is collected at the variables representing the grid points. This approach is able to generate updated maps for the usual ground-motion parameters (i.e., PGA, PGV, SA) as well as macroseismic intensity (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Shake-map generated with the Bayesian updating approach for the M 4.3 Lourdes (France) earthquake of December 30th 2012. Left: contour of PGA (in %g); right: field of associated uncertainty $\sigma_{\ln PGA}$. Triangles represent ground-motion measurements and circles are macroseismic observations.

The Bayesian updating method has been validated by Gehl et al. (2017) on a synthetic case, where the updated ground-motion parameters are shown to be identical to the “analytical solution” (i.e., resolution of a conditional multivariate normal distribution; Stafford 2012). This alternative approach has the merit of generating an exact solution for the uncertainty field associated with the shake-map, and of being transparent about the treatment of spatial correlation (i.e., direct use of correlation models from the literature). To some extent, it is able to model fields of different ground-motion parameters within the same BN, thus taking advantage of cross-correlation among parameters and potentially improving the precision of shake-maps (similarly to ShakeMap[®] v4). However, such features come at a higher computational cost than the ShakeMap[®] v3.5 method. Solutions such as the division of the BN into sub-grids have been proposed by Gehl et al. (2017): currently, shake-maps can be processed within a couple of minutes, on the condition that the number of observations to integrate as evidence is not too large (i.e., less than hundred data points).

6.1.3 Inventory of current shake-map systems

The USGS ShakeMap[®] system is applied to the U.S. territory, where specific site amplification models and GMPEs are designed for several regional areas (e.g., California and Pacific Northwest). It provides also a worldwide coverage of most earthquakes, at the cost of simplified models that have to cope with a paucity of detailed data in most locations. For instance, the estimation of soil amplification factors from the topographic slope (Wald and Allen 2007) constitutes a very convenient solution for first-order estimates, although its accuracy in less seismically active areas remains subject to debate (Lemoine et al. 2012). Therefore, the ShakeMap[®] package has been re-used and set up by several national or regional institutions worldwide (e.g., Switzerland, Italy, Greece, France and Romania): the algorithm remains the same, and local users have the possibility to exploit their own specific models and data streams (e.g., site amplification data, GMPEs, GMICEs and sources of observations), thus ensuring a great flexibility of the ShakeMap[®] tool.

Recently, the USGS ShakeMap[®] system has been upgraded from version 3.5 to version 4: one of the main changes pertains to the application of the “MVN approach” (Worden et al. 2018), i.e. the modelling of the ground-motion field through a conditional multi-variate normal distribution. This technique has the merit of removing “abrupt islands” close to the observations (due to the “radius of influence” in the former interpolation scheme) and of providing a much smoother field of uncertainty. However, most national implementations of the ShakeMap[®] system are still operating with the former version 3.5, and it is expected that the version upgrade might take several months or years in most countries.

A non-exhaustive list of the most common shake-map systems is described in Table 26, with a focus on Europe and TB areas of TURNkey.

Table 26: Global information on existing shake-map systems.

Name	Location	Institution(s)	Method	Status	References
Outside Europe					
USSG ShakeMap [®]	U.S. / Worldwide	USGS NEIC	v3.5: Weighted interpolation (Worden et al. 2010) v4: conditional MVN (Worden et al. 2018)	Operational	(Wald et al. 1999; Wald et al. 2006) earthquake.usgs.gov/data/shake-map
QuiQuake	Japan	AIST, GSJ	Interpolation from observations by IDW (Inverse Distance Weighted)	Operational	gbank.gsj.jp/QuiQuake
JMA shake-map	Japan	JMA	Generation of an instrumental intensity map	Operational	www.jma.go.jp/en/quake www.data.jma.go.jp/svd/cew/data/suikai/eventlist.html
NTU shake-map	Taiwan	National Taiwan University	Real-time interpolation from a dense network of low-cost accelerometers	Operational	(Wu et al. 2016)
GeoNet shake-map	New Zealand	GNS Science	Map of Felt Reports	Operational	www.geonet.org.nz/earthquake
BMKG shake-map	Indonesia	BMKG	ShakeMap [®] v3.5	Operational	(Pramono et al. 2017) http://inatews.bmkg.go.id/
CATnews	Worldwide	CEDIM, Risklayer, EQ Report	Calibration of stochastic scenarios with observations (esp. macroseismic testimonies)	Operational	(Schaefer 2018) https://twitter.com/CATnewsDE
In Europe (excluding TB areas and countries)					

ShakeMapEU	Euro-Mediterranean area	EMSC, ETH, ORFEUS, EFEHR	ShakeMap [®] v3.5	Under implementation	(Cauzzi et al. 2018) shakemap-eu.ethz.ch
SED shake-map	Switzerland	ETH SED	ShakeMap [®] v3.5	Operational	(Cauzzi et al. 2015) shakemap.ethz.ch
IPMA shake-map	Portugal	IPMA	ShakeMap [®] v3.5	Operational	(Marreiros and Carrilho 2012) http://shakemap.ipma.pt/
KOERI shakemap	Turkey (Istanbul)	KOERI, RETMC	Similar to ShakeMap [®] , or modified Kriging	Operational	(Zülfikar et al. 2017) www.koeri.boun.edu.tr/sismo
<i>TB areas and countries</i>					
INFP shake-map	Romania	INFP, NIEP	ShakeMap [®] v.3.5	Operational	atlas2.infp.ro/~shake/shakemap
SeisDaRo shake-map	Romania	INFP, NIEP	Custom Matlab code (based on ShakeMap [®] v.3.5)	Operational	(Dragos et al. 2016)
SisPyr	Pyrenees (France, Spain)	ICGC, OMP, BRGM, IGN, UPC	ShakeMap [®] v3.5	Operational	(Dumont 2012) www.sispyr.eu/shakemap
ICGC shake-map	Pyrenees (France, Spain)	ICGC	ShakeMap [®] v4	Under implementation (beta version online)	https://sismocat.icgc.cat/shakemap/index.php?lang=en
BCSF shake-map	France	BCSF	ShakeMap [®] v3.5	Operational	(Schlupp 2016) www.franceseisme.fr
CASSAT	South-East France	Geoazur	ShakeMap [®] v3.5	Operational	http://sismoazur.oca.eu/
IMO shake-map	Iceland	Icelandic Meteorological Office	ShakeMap [®] v3.2	No longer maintained	hraun.vedur.is/ja/alert/shake
NOA shake-map	Greece	NOA	ShakeMap [®] v3.5	Operational	accelnet.gein.noa.gr/shakemaps
EPPO-ITSAK shake-map	Greece	EPPO-ITSAK	ShakeMap [®] v3.5	Operational	shakemaps.itsak.gr
INGV shake-map	Italy	INGV	ShakeMap [®] v3.5	Operational	(Michelini et al. 2008) shakemap.rm.ingv.it/shake
KNMI shake-map	Groningen (Netherlands)	KNMI	ShakeMap [®] v3.5	Operational	www.knmi.nl/nederland-nu/seismologie/aardbevingen

For some of the selected shake-map systems, Table 27 provides further details on the sources of real-time measurements that are exploited: the characteristics of the earthquake event after its detection, the seismic networks that provide the ground-motion measurements, and the source of the macroseismic testimonies. Although technically possible in most algorithms, the integration of

macroseismic intensities is not systematic in all systems: due to the dense coverage of seismic stations, shake-maps in Japan rely only on ground-motion measurements, which are directly converted into the JMA instrumental intensity (Shabestari and Yamazaki 2001). It is worth noting that the collection of macroseismic intensities suffers from a lack of harmonized procedures among the different systems, with different types of online forms and possibly different interpretations of the accounts into a macroseismic scale.

Table 27: Sources of real-time data for selected shake-map systems.

Name	Earthquake parameters	Measured ground motions	Macroseismic observations
USGS ShakeMap®	NEIC	ANSS (accelerometers & broadband)	Did You Feel It? https://earthquake.usgs.gov/earthquakes/eventpage/tellus
JMA shake-map	JMA	JMA network (seismographs+seismic intensity meters) + NIED data	-
QuiQuake	-	NIED networks: K-NET (strong-motion accelerometers) and KiK-net (strong motion seismometers in boreholes)	-
SED shake-map	SED-data processing hubs from ETH	CHNet (SDSNet Streckeisen STS-2 broadband seismometers & SSMNet à broadband 200Hz accelerometer)	Seismo.ethz: Did You Feel an Earthquake?
KOERI shakemap	KOERI	KOERI, RETMC – Broadband (BB), Accelerometer (SM), Short-period (SP) seismometers	-
INFP shake-map	NIEP	Romanian Seismic Network (accelerometers)	-
SisPyr	ICGC, IGN, OMP, BRGM	ICGC, IGN, OMP, BRGM (BB and accelerometers)	franceseisme.fr/formulaire
BCSF shakemap	Detection by CEA/LDG	RESIF network (accelerometers)	franceseisme.fr/formulaire
NOA shake-map	NOA	Hellenic Unified Seismological Network-HUSN	noa.gr/did-you-feel-it/
EPPO-ITSAK shake-map	ITSAK	Permanent strong motion instruments + mobile accelerometers	-
INGV shake-map	INGV-Roma	RAN network (accelerometers)	Haisentidoilterremoto.it (=DYFI)
KNMI shake-map	KNMI	Netherlands Seismic and Acoustic Network, Groningen seismic network (accelerometers)	-

Finally, modelling and processing parameters for the different shake-map systems are detailed in Table 28: underlying GMPEs, GMICEs if a conversion to or from macroseismic intensity is used, and site amplification data. Most regional areas systems suffer from the lack of specific GMPEs and have to use GMPEs developed for the whole European continent or even global models. Regarding site amplification models, a national coverage in terms of soil classes or $V_{s,30}$ (average shear-wave velocity to a depth of 30 m) ranges is often not currently available. For now, local shake-map systems are more susceptible to benefit from an accurate soil classification, which is easier to generate over a small area (e.g., Pyrenees in France or Groningen area in the Netherlands).

Table 28: Modelling and processing parameters for selected shake-map systems.

Name	Most used GMPEs	Most used GMICES	Site amplification model
ShakeMap®	(Chiou and Youngs 2008) + specific regional models	(Atkinson and Kaka 2007) (Wald 1999) (Worden et al. 2012)	- U.S. regions : specific $V_{s,30}$ map - Worldwide: estimation of $V_{s,30}$ based on topographic slope (Wald and Allen 2007)
JMA shake-map	-	-	Amplification factors derived from Japanese $V_{s,30}$ map (geomorphologic + geological features)
QuiQuake	-	-	Amplification factors derived from Japanese $V_{s,30}$ map (geomorphologic + geological features)
SED shake-map	(Cauzzi et al. 2015) (Edwards and Fäh 2013)	(Faenza and Michelini 2011)	Amplification factors based on macroseismic intensity increments
KOERI shakemap	(Gülkan and Kalkan 2005) (Boore and Atkinson 2008)	(Wald 1999)	$V_{s,30}$ map for metropolitan Istanbul (from microzonation project; geology+topography)
INFP shake-map	(Sokolov et al. 2008) (Vacareanu et al. 2015)	(Stromeyer 2007)	Estimation of $V_{s,30}$ based on topographic slope (Wald and Allen 2007)
SisPyr	(Tapia 2006) (Akkar and Bommer 2007)	(Souriau 2006)	Regional map of EC8 soil classes (converted to amplification factors)
BCSF shakemap	(Akkar and Bommer 2010)	(Caprio et al. 2015)	Estimation of $V_{s,30}$ based on topographic slope (Wald and Allen 2007)
NOA shake-map	(Boore and Atkinson 2008) (Zhao et al. 2006)	(Worden et al. 2012)	Estimation of $V_{s,30}$ based on topographic slope (Wald and Allen 2007)
EPPO-ITSAK shake-map	(Akkar and Bommer 2007)	(Worden et al. 2012)	Estimation of $V_{s,30}$ based on topographic slope (Wald and Allen 2007)
INGV shake-map	(Akkar and Bommer 2007)	(Faenza and Michelini 2011)	Amplification factors obtained from $V_{s,30}$, using a map of EC8 soil classes
KNMI shake-map	Custom model (Bommer et al. 2017)	-	Amplification factors computed with zone-specific coefficients. The area around the gas field has been categorized in >100 zones, using a $V_{s,800}$ model, since the top 800 m consist of unconsolidated sediments.

6.2 Review of rapid loss assessment systems

This section details some of the current systems for the estimation of damage and losses in a RRE context. First, common software packages, which are able to perform rapid damage computation through mechanical or empirical approaches, are briefly described. Subsequently, the various existing RRE systems are discussed: a distinction is made between those that propose a direct

and automated link between the shake-maps and a damage or loss estimation software, and those that rely on alternative approaches.

6.2.1 Software performing structural damage and loss assessment

Structural damage and loss assessment software packages in a rapid response context need to be quick enough to deliver first estimates, and they should be able to cover potentially large built areas. Most of the current modules able to perform loss estimation have been reviewed in Erdik et al. (2014) and in Makhoul and Argyroudis (2018), the latter inventory comprising the characteristics of 50 software packages. In the following, we will analyse a selection of these packages based on their relevance in the TB areas, date of development, and accessibility, namely ELER (Hancilar et al. 2010), SELENA (Molina et al. 2010), Armagedom (Sedan et al. 2013), DBELA (Crowley et al. 2006) and SP-BELA (Borzi et al. 2008). These tools enable the use of ground motion estimates and of exposure and vulnerability maps in order to assess the level of damage and loss at different levels of resolution. They have originally been developed for the computation of prospective damage scenarios at city, regional or national scale in preparedness and mitigation phases; however, their approaches make them suitable for near-real-time computations in a RRE context.

ELER's routine performs loss estimation (building damage, casualties, economic loss) using building inventories (type, height and year) for the vulnerability assessment. At a high-resolution level, the damage to buildings and associated uncertainties are evaluated using spectral displacement-based analytical vulnerability relationships (Hancilar et al. 2010).

In SELENA (Molina et al. 2010), the vulnerability is assessed based on the spectral parameters (accelerations and displacements), and the ground motion estimates are provided using deterministic or probabilistic analysis, or near-real time data including site-effects. The uncertainties are computed via a logic-tree and a Monte Carlo approach.

In DBELA (Displacement Based Earthquake Loss Assessment; Crowley et al. 2006) and SP-BELA (Simplified Pushover-Based Earthquake Loss Assessment; Borzi et al. 2008), the vulnerability of the building is determined based on mechanical principles. DBELA evaluates the probability to exceed the capacity of a building class (corresponding to the occurrence of failure), for a given earthquake demand. SP-BELA uses a simplified technique in order to lower the computational cost, and it has been implemented essentially in regions with European or Mediterranean types of building.

At a global or regional scale, i.e. lower resolution level, one can also use empirical intensity-casualty or magnitude-casualty relationships and intensity-based vulnerability functions. The same principle of having different levels of loss estimation is implemented in the Armagedom software (Sedan et al. 2013; see Figure 15). The Armagedom tool is one of the potential candidates to be integrated as the loss estimation component in the TURNkey platform.

- Level 0 analyses rely on simplified empirical methods and basic exposure data (e.g. national census data). Vulnerability classes are described in terms of the A-F classification defined in EMS-98 (Grünthal 1998), therefore the seismic action has to be expressed as macroseismic intensity values. This level is well suited for results that aggregate at the scale of a city or municipality.
- Level 1 analyses are based on the empirical macroseismic methods as well; however, a more detailed description of buildings is employed. A vulnerability index V_i is estimated based on various building features, and the semi-empirical method by Giovinazzi and Lagomarsino

- (2004) is used in order to generate damage distributions. Results may be rendered at the scale of a municipality or a city district.
- Level 2 analyses are based on mechanical methods, namely the N2 approach (Fajfar 2000) that estimates the spectral displacement corresponding to the “performance point”. Then, the spectral displacement is either associated to a mean damage grade (and a damage distribution is generated as in Level 1 analyses) or to pre-computed fragility curves. Results may be rendered at the scale of a city district or a single building.

Figure 15: Organization of the Armagedom software adapted from Sedan et al. (2013). The green rectangle represents the hazard assessment part, which is replaced by a shake-map in a RRE context. The blue rectangle represents data and models that are gathered before the event (i.e., “cold data”). The red rectangle represents the data and models that are computed in near-real time after the event (“hot data”).

6.2.2 Description of RRE systems directly based on shake-maps

The following sub-sections discuss the RRE systems that directly use shake-maps that have been generated following the earthquake.

a. The USGS PAGER system

The PAGER (Prompt Assessment of Global Earthquakes for Response) system developed by the U.S. Geological Survey constitutes a prime example of robust tools used for loss and damage estimation (Jaiswal et al. 2010). Immediately following the earthquake, updated ground-motions maps are provided by the USGS ShakeMap[®] system. They can then be combined with vulnerability assessment

for loss estimation. Global population databases provide the number of people exposed to a given macroseismic intensity level, leading to the estimation of potential casualties and economic losses thanks to country-specific vulnerability and loss models (Jaiswal et al. 2010). The approach is empirical in developing regions having experienced a large number of damaging events. In highly developed countries, strong building codes and inventories enable the use of analytical methods, and semi-empirical solutions exist for regions corresponding to a mix of these end-members.

The use of global databases and models makes the PAGER system applicable worldwide, while its automated and fast execution is crucial for a timely sizing of the event and a triggering of appropriate response protocols. However, the global application of the PAGER system prevents it from using specific or local datasets: for instance, regarding the loss estimation, building exposure and vulnerability models are limited to national-scale datasets, and even to datasets adapted from similar countries when not available.

b. The USGS ShakeCast system

ShakeCast (ShakeMap Broadcast) constitutes a similar fully-automated open-source system using USGS data and HAZUS methodology (FEMA 2003). Shake-maps are applied to a list of facilities, for which a probability of damage is estimated through fragility curves. Alerts are broadcasted on a web interface, and sent by emails and texts to registered end-users, in order to be used for emergency response (see chart in Figure 16).

Figure 16: Overview of the Shakecast system (source <https://usgs.github.io/shakecast/index.html>).

c. The GDACS system

The PAGER tool providing casualties estimates is included in more general alert systems such as the Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System, GDACS (www.gdacs.org). GDACS is a cooperative framework between the United Nation and the European Union comprising and gathering data and tools from several organizations: JRC (Joint Research Center of the European Commission) & INFORM (Index for Risk Management), NEIC, OCHA (UN Office of Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs), INGV and USGS. Every 5 minutes, the data (earthquake magnitude, depth, location, population within 100 km, vulnerability) is gathered and a three-level alert is issued (green, orange, red), depending on the impact of the earthquake (this works also for other types of natural hazards).

d. The SeisDaRo system

In Romania, SeisDaRo 3 (Dragos et al. 2016) is a near-real-time system based on the PAGER methodology and the SELENA module. It is directly connected to the Romanian shake-map system and it can deliver loss maps by running all of the system's modules in less than 6 minutes.

Figure 17: Overview of the SeisDaRo system (source (Dragos et al. 2016)).

e. The ELER system

Operational in the Istanbul area, this system (Zülfikar et al. 2017) uses the shake-maps generated by KOERI/RETMC, which are available within a few minutes after the event. The calculations of damage and loss are then performed on a grid, using in addition to the ground motions: the local site

conditions ($V_{s,30}$), the building inventory on a 0.005° grid (year, numbers of floors, type) and the demographic data (population inventory data from Istanbul governorship). The building damage is evaluated using the ELER methodology, and the loss estimation is performed with the HAZUS-MH methodology (FEMA 2003).

f. The SEISAID system

In France, BRGM developed a rapid response system based on the PAGER approach (Auclair et al. 2014; Auclair et al. 2015). This is implemented in the Pyrenees area (i.e., Test-Bed 2) and in the whole French territory. The SEISAID tool generates rapid shaking estimates, and it projects population density data on seismic intensity levels in order to rapidly estimate the number of casualties and homeless people. Data from previous earthquakes and from a multitude of seismic scenarios have been used to calibrate the relation between macroseismic intensity and human losses. Currently, BRGM is upgrading the SEISAID system by automatically connecting the shake-map outputs to the Armagedom software in order to generate more accurate damage and loss scenarios for areas, in which vulnerability data are available. An example is the area of Mayotte (France, Indian Ocean), where a pilot service is under development. Upon the detection of an earthquake by BRGM, a shake-map is derived using the Bayesian updating approach (Gehl 2017), and the Armagedom software is automatically executed with the computed intensity map. The results (i.e., number of casualties and injured people, and number of partially or totally collapsed buildings, at the scale of a municipality) are intended to be communicated via e-mail to civil protection services a few minutes after the earthquake.

6.2.3 Description of RRE systems not based on shake-maps

In contrast to the systems detailed above, the following sub-sections describe tools that do not directly rely on the outcomes of shake-map systems: either since they use specific earthquake scenarios without accounting for field observations or because they directly estimate losses from the earthquake's characteristics.

a. The QLARM system

The ICES Foundation (www.icesfoundation.org) provides loss estimates within 24 hours after a potentially damaging earthquake worldwide. This is done in partnership with the Swiss Seismological Service and eventually provides alert levels with the number of fatalities and the average damage of buildings. The software used is called QLARM for “earthquake Loss Assessment Response” (Trendafiloski 2011). The ground shaking is estimated for each settlement using the earthquake characteristics and a $V_{s,30}$ map (based on the topography). The damage estimation is obtained using empirical relations derived from ~ 1000 previous earthquakes for which the losses are known. The percentage of population belonging to classes of vulnerability (definition of the classes based on the building type) is evaluated. The distribution of the population depending on the time of the event is also taken into account. The results are the percentage of buildings in each of the five defined damage states as well as the number of fatalities and injured people in each settlement. Results are available on the ICES Foundation website, and they are also automatically sent to the subscribers of the QLARM system.

b. The SIGE-DPC system

In Italy, an automatic procedure (SIGE - Information System for Emergency Management) activated and supervised, by the Civil Protection uses the early characteristics of the earthquake in order to estimate the expected distribution of structural damage and human casualties (Pasquale 2005). Interestingly, it appears that the shake-map step is bypassed, with no immediate use of measured or observed ground shaking in order to update intensity maps (only use of estimated ground-motion parameters with GMPEs).

c. Web-GIS tools by EUCENTRE

Web-based GIS tools have been developed at EUCENTRE for the Italian Department of Civil Protection (DPC) in order to calculate seismic risk and real time damage scenarios for Italian structures, such as residential buildings (Borzi et al. 2011; Faravelli et al. 2018; Borzi et al. 2011), school buildings (Borzi et al. 2011; Borzi et al. 2011; Faravelli et al. 2018), and infrastructures, e.g. ports (Bozzoni and Lai 2017; Bozzoni et al. 2018), roadway network (Onida 2011; Meo et al. 2018; Faravelli et al. 2018) and airports (Bozzoni et al. 2019). The GIS technology, through the coupling with external, purposely developed programs, is able to transform the multitude of heterogeneous datasets into interactive and intelligent map-based visuals. The web-GIS platforms are equipped with purposely-developed algorithms for the (near-) real-time assessment of earthquake-related damage and losses.

A comparison of the SIGE results and EUCENTRE results was carried out for Italian residential buildings by means of six earthquakes that struck Italy in the last 35 years. The comparison shows that the predictions obtained with the EUCENTRE methodology are in good agreement with real damage, while the SIGE system overestimates them (Sabetta et al. 2013).

Moreover, EUCENTRE is developing a tool to identify bridges that may have suffered damage after an earthquake for the Italian railway network manager (Rete Ferroviaria Italiana, RFI; Bellotti et al. 2019). The system aims to define the sections of the network in which traffic needs to be slowed down, and it prioritises the inspections of structures and infrastructures of the railway network in the phases immediately following an earthquake, through real-time or near real-time generation of shaking and resentment maps, and seismic damage scenarios.

EUCENTRE has recently developed a new platform called IRMA: Italian Risk Maps (Faravelli et al. 2019). IRMA addresses the scientific community and it allows sharing data, methods and models to evaluate the seismic risk and damage scenarios of Italian residential buildings using OpenQuake. IRMA was developed with funds of the DPC with the aim of providing a common tool that can be used by the scientific community to produce seismic risk maps for the "Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030" (Dolce et al. 2019).

d. Earthquake Qualitative Impact Assessment (EQIA) by ESMC

ESMC has developed EQIA, an Earthquake Qualitative Impact Assessment (Gilles 2010), which provides fast and automatic impact assessment for worldwide crustal earthquakes with magnitude 5 or higher. It provides a range of potential impacts (based on intervals of potential fatalities) in order to rate the severity of the event for the triggering of rapid actions. To this end, two empirical equations are used: a GMPE for the estimation of the impacted area, and an equation relating the number of

fatalities to the earthquake magnitude and to the population density. This approach has the merit of bypassing the shake-map step and of providing a direct impact estimate with little input data. For large earthquakes of magnitude 7 or higher, the source is modelled as a 1D finite rupture, and different assumptions regarding the position of the fault and its nodal plane are taken into account, adding to the uncertainties of the earthquake scenario. A comparative study by Julien-Laferrière (2019) between EQIA predictions of past earthquakes and actual impacts reveals a satisfying performance of EQIA. Currently, EQIA outcomes are not made publicly available; however, they are communicated to a group of selected end-users or to governmental organizations on request (e.g., French civil protection).

e. The TELES system

The Taiwanese system TELES (Taiwan Earthquake Loss Estimation System; Yeh et al., 2006) is based on the HAZUS methodology and provides decision support after strong earthquakes. The earthquake data comes from the Central Weather Bureau networks and the parameters (location, magnitude) are given by TREIRS (Taiwan Rapid Earthquake Information Release System) within 90 s after the event. This enables estimation of the ground motion (PGA and PGV) from an earthquake using GMPEs. Potential liquefaction effects are included in the method and probabilities of different damage states for 15 types of buildings are given using an analytical approach. Damage maps and tables are automatically generated within 3 to 5 minutes after receiving the earthquake alert. For now, this procedure does not seem to integrate the new Taiwanese shake-map system.

f. Japanese systems READY and SUPREME

Two other systems exist in Japan: the READY system (Midorikawa 2006) and the more specific SUPREME system (Nakayama et al. 2004) for assessment of possible damage to gas infrastructures. READY has an associated array of strong motion accelerographs and borehole systems for liquefaction monitoring. The stations are connected to observation centres thanks to high-speed telephone lines and satellites as a backup. The intensity map is immediately issued, along with other useful information such as hospital or refuge locations. Thanks to an agreement with civil construction firms, the damage to road structures and transportation systems can also be rapidly assessed. Concerning the SUPREME system, it uses spectrum intensity sensors in order to assess damage to gas pipes. The response spectra are evaluated in the range 0.1-2.5 s, and if the spectral intensity is greater than 30-40 cm/s, the decision to shut-down the gas supply is made.

g. The Earthquake-Report platform

The independent **Earthquake-Report** platform, created by researchers from various organizations, is able to provide earthquake reports, shake-maps (with CATnews), and damage estimates for worldwide earthquakes. It uses Did You Feel It data from EMSC and USGS, while the results are further constrained by social media feedback and specifically felt earthquake testimonies (own report form available on the website www.earthquake-report.com).

6.2.4 Summary of rapid loss assessment systems

A summary of the rapid damage and loss assessment systems is presented in Table 29, where the required input data and the output format of each system is given.

Table 29: Input data and expected outputs for the studied loss assessment systems.

Loss estimation system	Input data	Output	Scale
PAGER	Shake-map + empirical or analytical vulnerability assessment	Fatalities estimate	- Population exposed at each intensity level - At the level of the whole event
ShakeCast	Shake-map + facility inventory	Shaking values and damage state of facilities. Email/text alerts	At the level of single facilities
GDACS	PAGER output	Three-level colour alerts	At the level of the whole event
SeisDaRo	Custom shake-map + building inventory + vulnerability data	Fatalities graphs and exposure tables. Fast global damage estimates + more accurate analysis of fatalities due to building collapse.	At the level of cities / municipalities
Istanbul ELER	Shake-map + building inventory database + occupancy/population database	Loss maps	At the level of a city district / large building block
SEISAID	Shake-map + building inventory database + occupancy/population database	Damage and loss maps	At the level of a city district
QLARM	Scenario earthquake + empirical relations	Fatalities and average damage on buildings on global scale	- Exposure of each settlement - Grade for the whole event
SIGE-DPC	Earthquake characteristics + empirical relations	Collapsed dwellings, unusable dwellings, fatalities and homeless.	At the level of cities / municipalities
EQIA (ESMC)	Earthquake characteristics + population density (LandScan)	Global impact estimate (range)	At the level of the whole event
TELES	EQ scenario + liquefaction effects	Damage maps and tables	At the level of a city district
READY	Intensity map	Damages on roads and buildings, inaccessible roads	At the level of a city district / large building block
SUPREME	Spectral intensity	Damage on gas pipes / automatic shut-down	At the level of facilities (buried pipelines)
Earthquake-Report	Intensity maps, online news	Injuries, fatalities, evacuations	At the level of the whole event

Finally, a tentative review of the coverage of the TB areas by loss assessment systems is presented in Table 30.

Table 30: Implementation of rapid loss assessment systems in the TB areas.

Test Bed	System
TB1 – Bucarest (Roumania)	SeisDaRo
TB2 – Pyrenees (France)	SisPyr, SEISAID
TB3 – Hveragerdi and Husavik (Iceland)	Civil Protection and Emergency Management (system up-to-date?) & National Commissioner of the Icelandic Police (NCIP), but no detailed public information
TB4 – Patras and Aigio (Greece)	No automatic real time system?
TB5 – Port of Gioia Tauro (Italy)	SIGE-DPC & EUCENTRE web-GIS

TB6 – Groningen province (The Netherlands)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For the regional railway grid, managed by Prorail, automatic warnings are issued if 1) an $M \geq 3.5$ occurs in the region or 2) the maximum PGA of the computed ShakeMap exceeds 15%g. - For the regional road authority, Rijkswaterstaat, a similar system is in test phase. They are notified whether or not the 15%g threshold is reached at certain points of interest for their infrastructure.
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6.3 Key issues and recommendations for future work

The above literature review has highlighted several noteworthy points and issues related to the implementation of shake-map and rapid loss assessment systems in Europe, especially in TB areas (see summary in Table 31). Regarding shake-maps, the following observations could be made with respect to modelling data and real-time inputs:

- For the near real-time generation of shake-maps (i.e., in less than a few minutes), it is currently difficult to get an accurate knowledge of the faulting mechanism or of the fault geometry. First-order approximations usually consist of the adoption of a faulting style that is consistent with the seismo-tectonic context of the coverage area. In addition, empirical relations may be used to assume fault dimensions from the earthquake magnitude in order to estimate distance metrics such as Joyner-Boore distance or distance-to-rupture. Alternatively, the Earthquake Qualitative Impact Assessment by EMSC integrates these uncertainties on the source characterization by considering several extreme fault configurations, in order to estimate confidence bounds of the results: such an approach may be worth investigating for shake-maps, especially in the case of a large earthquake with an extended source.
- Another issue lies in the characterization of site amplification factors: by default, most shake-map systems use the Wald and Allen (2007) model based on topographic slope with very little guarantee that it provides accurate results for the area of interest. Moreover, a proper characterization of the sites where ground motions are recorded is crucial, since inaccurate amplification factors may introduce errors when deconvolving the observations to rock conditions and, in turn, they may alter the whole shake-map appearance. Therefore, recent efforts carried out in the SERA project for a better characterization of site conditions in Europe should be integrated in the upcoming developments.
- The choice of the GMPE models to be used in the shake-maps is also very disparate between the different systems due to the lack of *ad-hoc* equations for most areas in Europe. A solution might be to generate shake-maps with a logic tree of GMPEs (i.e., as in probabilistic seismic hazard analyses) in order to integrate the epistemic uncertainty due to GMPE selection: however, this might come at the expense of longer computation times and added complexity to the final outcome. It is worth noting that most shake-map algorithms adjust the global level by correcting the bias (ShakeMap[®] v3.5) or by updating the inter-event error term (ShakeMap[®] v4.0 and method by Gehl et al. (2017)). Hence, the influence of the GMPE on the global level of the updated ground-motion field may be limited: only local differences due to different decay rates and differences in the treatment of site amplification may remain.
- The integration of macroseismic testimonies is not systematic in all shake-map systems, with various ways of collecting and interpreting the data (i.e., different types of online forms). The duration required to collect meaningful data and to translate it into macroseismic values

constitutes a challenge for their use in near real-time applications. Less conventional sources of social data, such as the use of the mobile applications (LastQuake, EQN) or the data mining of social media (e.g., Twitter feeds), have proven to be very efficient thanks to the reactivity of users right after an earthquake (i.e., a few seconds to a few minutes). Their use as additional data inputs for shake-maps is worth investigating in order to cover the time gap before the arrival of more accurate macroseismic intensities (i.e., after several minutes).

In terms of shake-map algorithms, version 4.0 of ShakeMap[®] offers substantial improvements over the version 3.5. The weighted interpolation algorithm, which is based on the definition of “radii of influence” that are difficult to quantify in practice, is replaced by a matrix-based procedure that relies on the multivariate normal (MVN) distribution. The latter approach presents the benefit of generating exact solutions of the updated ground-motion field with an accurate uncertainty structure (Worden et al. 2018). Moreover, this approach is able to consider multiple types of intensity measures, for instance by accounting for the statistical cross-correlation between spectral ordinates at various periods. This feature is especially useful when dealing with inter-connected exposed assets that are susceptible to various types of intensity measures (i.e., loss assessment of infrastructure systems). In parallel, the Bayesian updating approach by Gehl et al. (2017) is based on the theory of spatially correlated Gaussian fields in order to update the ground-motion field from various types of observations. The Bayesian approach is based on the same mathematical concepts as the procedure by Worden et al. (2018), so that the results are identical when the same assumptions are used. It is also able to handle cross-correlation among different intensity measures, although at the cost of longer computation times. Whatever the approach used, it should be noted that these two recommended procedures provide an accurate description of the uncertainties associated with the updated ground-motion field, so that these uncertainties may be propagated to the loss assessment step. A proper uncertainty treatment, from the source characteristics to the loss estimation, is crucial in order to feed the Decision Support System in Work Package 5.

Finally, additional comments and recommendations can be made on existing rapid loss assessment tools:

- Some systems, such as PAGER, GDACS or EQIA, aim at providing a picture of the potential impact at the level of the whole earthquake. This scale is useful for rapidly sizing the disaster and for deciding at which level (e.g., regional, national, international) crisis management operations need to operate, as well as the amount of aid and resources to dedicate. However, much more detailed information is needed very quickly: usually first responders require a detailed account of the situation at a local level in order to establish in which street or building block to operate and to rescue potential casualties. Therefore, systems that estimate damage and losses at a more detailed resolution (e.g., SeisDaRo, ELER, SEISAID) constitute the strict minimum to meet these operational needs. As a result, the coupling between a shake-map system and a rapid loss assessment tool (at least at city district level) seems like the best way to pursue: shake-maps are able to provide updated ground-motion estimates, which can in turn feed fragility models of various structural typologies.
- Most rapid loss assessment systems predict damage to common buildings and estimate fatalities, while a few of them look at infrastructure components or critical facilities (ShakeCast, SUPREME). None of the current systems consider the effect of failed

components on the global performance of the infrastructure, which has a great influence on the crisis management operations (e.g., inaccessible roads, power outage and disrupted water supply). This crucial aspect requires further research efforts, since preliminary proof-of-concept studies have shown its potential (Gehl 2018), although modelling and computational issues need to be improved.

Table 31: Summary of recommended features for shake-map and rapid loss assessment systems.

Features	Current systems	Recommendations
<i>Shake-map estimation</i>		
Earthquake parameters	Point-like source with approximation of fault extent	Integration of uncertainties on fault geometries before it is characterized more precisely
Site amplification	Most systems are based on first-order approximations (topographic slope model for $V_{s,30}$)	Use of recent results on site characterization for Europe (SERA), while integrating uncertainties on amplification factors
Macroseismic data	Uneven use of macroseismic testimonies (if available, different formats of online forms)	Investigation of rapid online reactions (e.g., mobile apps, social media) before macroseismic intensities are processed
Algorithm	Mostly weighted interpolation algorithm (ShakeMap [®] v3.5)	Upgrade to ShakeMap [®] v4 or use of Bayesian updating approach, for a proper characterization of uncertainties
<i>Rapid loss assessment</i>		
Level of analysis	Mostly regional or city level	Building block or city district level
Types of assets	Mostly built areas, and sometimes infrastructure components (without systemic performance assessment)	Integration of the rapid performance loss assessment of infrastructure systems
Algorithm	Various types of treatments: empirical equations linking earthquake event to losses, or detailed analyses including shake-maps	Automated coupling between shake-map outputs and fragility/vulnerability models

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8 APPENDIX A: SUPPLEMENTAL DATA TO SECTION 4.2.4

8.1.1 UK's threat levels for terrorism¹

There are five levels of threat:

- low - an attack is highly unlikely
- moderate - an attack is possible but not likely
- substantial - an attack is likely
- severe - an attack is highly likely
- critical - an attack is highly likely in the near future

The threat level expresses the likelihood of an attack in the near future.

The threat levels do not require specific responses from the public. They are a tool for security practitioners and the police.

They do not have an expiry date, but they are reviewed regularly and if needed, altered.

8.1.2 UK's Met Office weather warnings²

There are four warning levels based on a warning impact matrix with axes of likelihood and impact:

- no warning
- yellow warning – either likely/very likely but low impact (“Daily routine generally unaffected but some travel disruption”) or unlikely and high impact
- amber warning – likely/very likely and moderate impact (“Potential travel disruption, power cuts and the potential risk to life and property. Consider changing plans.”)
- red warning – very likely and high impact (“Severe disruption and damage. Take action to reduce harm.”).

Figure 18: The UK MET office warning impact matrix (<https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/weather/guides/warnings/>).

The warnings are for rain, thunderstorms, wind, snow, lightning, ice and fog up to seven days ahead. They are indicated on a daily map with clickable sections.

The warning has four sections:

- headline: what weather type is forecast
- what to expect: types of impact and how likely they are

¹ <https://www.mi5.gov.uk/threat-levels>

² <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/weather/guides/warnings/>

- what should I do: links to advice and guidance from Met Office partners on how to stay safe
- further details (including where the warning falls on the impact matrix)

If applicable, warnings include information on why a warning has been updated. Access through Met Office app and website, social media, email alerts, TV, radio and RSS.

8.1.3 UK's Flood hazard³

Three-time periods considered, each with a separate resource:

- the immediate risk of flooding (<https://flood-warning-information.service.gov.uk/warnings>)
- the risk of flooding in the next five days (https://flood-warning-information.service.gov.uk/5-day-flood-risk?_ga=2.133272654.1739073358.1573043253-1107343386.1570528255)
- the long-term risk of flooding (https://flood-warning-information.service.gov.uk/long-term-flood-risk?_ga=2.69246928.1739073358.1573043253-1107343386.1570528255). This is not considered here as it is closest to a time-independent seismic hazard map.

For the immediate risk of flooding, there are four levels:

- no warning
- flood alert: flooding is possible – be prepared
- flood Warning: flooding is expected – immediate action required
- severe flood warning: severe flooding – danger to life

There is also a category: Warning no longer in force.

These warnings apply to small areas (e.g. a specific river's flood plain).

For falert, flood warning and severe flood warning there are a small set of actions proposed by the Environment Agency summarised as: prepare, act and survive, respectively.

It is possible to sign up (online or by phone) for warnings by phone, email or text message.

For risk of flooding in the next five days there are four risk levels:

- very low risk: flooding is very unlikely
- low risk: flooding is possible – be aware
- medium risk: flooding is expected – be prepared
- high risk: significant risk to life – take action

For each of these risk levels, there is a small set of recommended actions.

The risk levels are provided in the form of a map with the resolution of county rather than the level of a single river.

8.1.4 England and Wales Fire Severity Index⁴

Unlike the other warning systems, this website does not provide an assessment of the risk of wildfires occurring (which includes a human element that is not predictable), but it provides an estimate of how severe a fire could become if one were to start.

³ <https://www.gov.uk/check-flood-risk>

⁴ FSI, <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/public/weather/fire-severity-index/#?tab=map&fcTime=1573041600&zoom=5&lon=-4.00&lat=54.50>

There are five levels:

- level 1: low fire severity
- level 2: moderate fire severity
- level 3: high fire severity
- level 4: very high fire severity
- level 5: exceptional fire severity

The website provides an assessment for today and the next five days in the form of a map with pixels of size $10 \times 10 \text{ km}^2$.

The “exceptional” category was calibrated based on a set of historical exceptional fire events.

The FSI is used as a trigger for fire prevention restrictions on access land to minimise accidental fires. Access to land is suspended for level 5.

8.1.5 US national volcano alert-level system⁵

There are two parts to this system: 1) volcano alert level for people on the ground and 2) aviation color code for aviation due to the hazard from airborne ash. The results are shown on a national-scale map with a symbol for each volcano.

There are four volcano alert levels:

- normal: volcano is in typical background, non-eruptive state or, if the volcano was previously at a higher level, the volcanic activity has ceased
- advisory: volcano is exhibiting signs of elevated unrest above known background level or, if the volcano was previously at a higher level, the volcanic activity has decreased significantly
- watch: volcano is exhibiting heightened or escalating unrest with increased potential of an eruption in an uncertain timeframe or an eruption is underway, but poses a limited hazard
- warning: a hazardous eruption is imminent, underway, or suspected

The aviation color codes (green, yellow, orange and red) are similar but with the addition of information on the volcanic-ash emissions.

A subscription service via email and RSS is available for this alert service.

8.1.6 US tsunami warning centres⁶

Tsunami messages are provided by Tsunami Warning Centers to notify emergency managers and other local officials, the public, and other partners about a potential tsunami following a causative event (e.g. sub-seafloor earthquake).

There are four levels (the level may be changed when more information becomes available):

- information statement: generally issued to indicate that there is no threat of a destructive tsunami so as to prevent unnecessary evacuations
- watch: a tsunami may later affect the watch area so emergency managers and the public should prepare to take action
- advisory: a tsunami that is dangerous to those in or very near water (forecast/observed heights up to 1 m) is imminent, expected or occurring but significant inundation is not expected, so

⁵ https://volcanoes.usgs.gov/vhp/about_alerts.html

⁶ <https://www.tsunami.gov/?page=tsunamiFAQ>

appropriate actions include closing beaches, evacuating harbours and marinas and repositioning ships to deep water

- warning: a tsunami with the potential (forecast/observed heights more than 1 m) for widespread inundation is imminent, expected or occurring, so appropriate actions include the evacuation of low-lying coastal areas and repositioning of ships to deep waters.

The warnings are broadcast through local radio and TV, marine radio, wireless emergency alerts, NOAA weather radio, websites and social media. They also may come via outdoor sirens, local officials, emails, text messages and telephone notifications.

8.1.7 French Meteorological alert-level system for hurricanes⁷

For communicating the level of warning related to hurricanes in the Caribbean area, the French authorities use a six levels scale, referring to colours, timing and intensity of expected impact and issue the following recommendations to the population:

- green: no particular vigilance;
- yellow: be careful, practice activities sensitive to the weather risk and the proximity to a shoreline or watercourse; the usual phenomena in the area may occasionally be locally dangerous within 48 to 72 hours;
- orange: get ready, dangerous phenomena are expected within 48 hours;
- red: protect yourself, dangerous phenomena of exceptional intensity are expected in 6 to 18 hours;
- violet: isolate yourself, major impacts associated with the hurricane are expected in 3 to 6 hours;
- grey: decreasing phase, the phenomenon is moving away, but dangers persist.

In the other French overseas departments, the actions are similar, but the terms for the alerts vary slightly in terms of a number of levels and detail of recommendations.

It is interesting to note that most of them include an alert level for residual danger following the main impact.

8.1.8 Landslide EWSs around the world

The experience of the implementation of landslide EWSs is very diverse and strongly influenced by the connection of this sort of hazard with other triggering phenomena (mainly heavy rainfall and earthquakes) and the proximity of the dangerous area to populated areas. The “parasitic” character of this sort of phenomenon and the variability of its evolution (from very slow to very fast) add further challenges to the implementation of EWSs accepted and trusted within the threatened communities. Limiting this review to weather-induced mass movements, including rainfall and snowmelt induced landslides, most of the EWSs exploit “rainfall thresholds” (White and Mottershead 1998), i.e. the minimum amount of rainfall for triggering a displacement or changing the state of an unstable slope within a specified period (Segoni et al. 2018). Thresholds can be defined empirically, statistically, or using physics-based approaches.

Another parameter influencing the approach of the landslide EWS is the extent of the area of interest or the scale of the concerned analysis. Taking into account the objective and the context of this review,

⁷ <http://www.meteofrance.gp/vigilance-antilles-guyane>

we focus mainly on systems able to provide alerts for phenomena potentially occurring anywhere within regional, national or supranational boundaries. Landslide EWSs cover an entire nation or a large part of a nation or state. Piciullo et al. (2017) reserve the term “global” for landslide EWSs covering a larger portion of the globe: in parallel, they also provide a review of dozens of “territorial” landslide EWS that cover a local area. At a national level, an excellent example consists of the landslide EWS and real-time scenario tool operating in Norway (Devoli et al. 2015). At a global level, a Landslide Hazard Assessment for Situational Awareness (LHASA) model has been proposed by Kirschbaum and Stanley (2018) in order to deliver “nowcasts” indicating potential landslide activity in near real-time: this approach relies on satellite-based precipitation estimates, susceptibility maps derived from information on a slope, geology, road networks, fault zones, and forest loss.

The process of a landslide and the technologies available for monitoring it also pose the question of the differences among “prediction”, “forecast” and “nowcast”. Within the scope of this document, we follow the definition of Guzzetti et al. (2020) about a “warning system” as the physical implementation of a warning model, which may contain one or more landslide forecast models generally based on the assumption that:

- precipitation is the primary or the only trigger (Campbell 1975);
- landslides can be forecasted with sufficient lead time to allow organizations, communities, and individuals to take mitigation actions (Wilson 2012; Calvello and Piciullo 2016);
- landslide forecasts are reasonably accurate and contain valuable information to help mitigate landslide risk;
- the inherent probabilistic content of the forecasts and their uncertainties are mapped to meaningful advisory levels. The same landslide forecast may be mapped differently (e.g., using different advisories schemes) depending on the beneficiaries and on the user needs (Piciullo et al. 2017; Piciullo et al. 2017);
- the information on the expected landslides is conveyed from the LEWS to the interested organisations, communities or persons at a reasonable time by a trusted source, and in a way and format that is known to and understood by the beneficiaries (Wilson 2012; UNISDR 2009).

Summarising the general characteristics of the most effective known EWSs implemented according to these assumptions:

- their input, i.e. precipitation rate, is represented by both rainfall measures (from rain-gauges) and forecasts;
- usually, the system output is not automatically addressed to the public, as it is verified by qualitative or quantitative criteria and in case heuristically adjusted by geotechnical specialists, considering specific weather conditions and the susceptibility to the rapidly changing nature of the concerned phenomena; and
- authorities communicate the alert to the public through local media, radio and televisions.

In this configuration, local government agencies use the notice to activate the emergency response and to suggest evacuations according to predefined plans. The population can rarely safely react independently from their activation, so that no general recommendations are usually provided except for avoiding the dangerous areas.

9 APPENDIX B: OEF IN ROMANIA

Institutul Național de Cercetare - Dezvoltare pentru Fizica Pământului (INFP) is the National Institute for Research and Development for Earth Physics in Romania. As Bucharest is one of the testbeds of the Turnkey project, INFP has primarily focused on the literature and networks that are monitoring the Vrancea seismogenic zone, in terms of earthquakes precursors. INFP has used the assessed Romanian seismic hazard, and decided that for the Bucharest testbed, the OEF is useful only for the Vrancea intermediate-depth seismogenic zone. The crustal seismogenic sources from Romania do not present a significant danger for the Bucharest testbed. Beside the studies focused on Vrancea (Romania) seismicity, other relevant studies have been reviewed. Because it is focussed on a specific testbed this review is provided in the Appendix of this report, although some of the appendix (e.g. the section on non-seismic parameters and temporal variations in the b value) applies globally and not just to Romania.

9.1.1 Vrancea zone

The Vrancea seismogenic area is located at the curvature of Carpathians, see Figure 19, at the intersection of three major tectonic units: (a) East European Platform to Northeast; (b) Moesian platform to South; and (c) Transylvanian Basin to the West.

Figure 19: The Vrancea seismogenic area, affecting Bucharest crustal seismicity (blue dots) and intermediate-depth seismicity (orange and red dots) and the location of geomagnetic observers included in the study.

The Vrancea zone represents the most active seismic zone in Europe and is located on the Eastern edge of the strongly bent Carpathian arc. In this area, shallow seismic activity with moderate earthquakes ($M_w < 5.6$) is found together with intermediate-depth activity featuring strong earthquakes. Earthquakes at intermediate depths occur between 60 and 200 km depth and are located

in a confined area of only 40x80 km². The crustal seismicity of the Vrancea zone is shifted to the east and is concentrated in the Eastern Carpathians foredeep region (Focsani basin; Popescu and Radulian 2001). The shallow seismicity corresponds to the recent deformations along the major faults that bound the SE-Carpathians as the Intramoesic fault to the south and the Peceneaga-Camena and Trotus faults to the north. The crustal earthquakes are affected by an extensional regime with normal and strike-slip faulting (Radulian et al. 2000).

Intermediate-depth (60-300 km) earthquakes occur along convergent plate margins, but their causes remain unclear. The mechanism that generates earthquakes at these depths is different from crustal mechanisms. The intermediate range is affected by a compressive regime, with reverse faulting and extension on a vertical axis (Radulian et al. 2002). Because of the high pressure at intermediate depths and the lack of pore pressure, brittle failure is unlikely to occur at intermediate depths. The mechanisms which cause crustal earthquakes are not sufficient to explain the occurrence of intermediate-depth earthquakes, and brittle failure should be accompanied by a ductile deformation (John et al. 2009).

Many authors debated the occurrence of intermediate-depth earthquakes and several theories were proposed regarding the subduction process affecting this area. McKenzie et al. (1970) suggested that the intermediate earthquakes beneath the Vrancea zone occur in a relict oceanic slab hanging vertically in the mantle. According to Sperner et al. (2001), the absence of intermediate seismicity in the northern part of the Carpathians indicate that in this zone the collision was followed by a slab break-off and today, the remaining slab hangs beneath the Vrancea zone. Another model suggested for the Vrancea zone was the delamination mechanism by Knapp et al. (2005) and Lorinczi and Houseman (2009), which refers to the foundering of the portion of the lowermost lithosphere from the tectonic plate to which it was attached. The delamination process seems to be more suitable for continent collisions and includes sudden mafic volcanism and acceleration of uplift. According to Sperner et al. (2001), the absence of intermediate seismicity in the northern part of the Carpathians indicates that in this zone the collision was followed by a slab break-off and as of today, the remaining slab hangs beneath Vrancea zone. The major shocks produced in the last hundred years were generated in the upper and lower segments alternatively: October 6, 1908 ($M_w = 7.1$, $h = 90$ km), November 10, 1940 ($M_w = 7.7$, $h = 150$ km), March 4, 1977 ($M_w = 7.4$, $h = 89$ km), August 30, 1986 ($M_w = 7.1$, $h = 131$ km) and May 30, 1990 ($M_w = 6.9$, $h = 90$ km).

9.1.2 Seismic precursors

The particularities of the seismic process in the Vrancea zone render the application of numerical simulation techniques attractive as competent tools to investigate the earthquake process and to explain the seismic cycle evolution and precursory phenomena. The Vrancea zone is an interesting test site to investigate and constrain the process of earthquake generation, from many points of view, including that it is easier to study than other seismic active areas in the world, due to the concentration and stability of earthquake generation as well as the well-defined alignments of seismic activity (Carbunar and Radulian 2011). Even so, the statistical numerical techniques applied on Vrancea catalogues have not yet given reliable results, and long-term forecasts were rarely confirmed.

Previous studies were based on the analysis of background seismicity patterns and of the aftershock distribution (Dimiskovska 2008). Carbunar and Radulian (2011) showed that the deformation in the Vrancea zone concentrates beneath about 60 km depth and tends to be released in two segments: 70–100 km depth (in the upper part of the subducted lithosphere) as well as 120–170 km depth (in the lower part of the subducted lithosphere). The inspection of the historical data over a 700-year-long

catalogue suggests seismic cycles of about four shocks with a magnitude above seven per century in the Vrancea subcrustal slab (Nathan and Scobell 2012). The hypocentre distribution concentrates in a narrow volume that is NE–SW oriented and close to vertical. However, despite the concentration of foci in space (), the persistence of earthquake production in time (a relatively constant rate of 15–20 events/month with magnitudes $M_w > 2.5$) and of the seismicity clustering properties (Dimiskovska 2008), the process of triggering the strongest shocks has a chaotic character, which renders any medium- and short-term prediction using numerical models difficult. The statistical studies including wavelet analysis were completed with fractal and chaotic models, but the obtained results cannot be used for an effective operational forecast of earthquakes (Enescu et al. 2008; Enescu et al. 2006; Enescu et al. 2005).

From a global perspective, the Gutenberg–Richter b-value in broad seismic regions is close to 1.0. For smaller-scale regions (a few to tens of kilometres), the temporal and spatial variations in b-values may be significantly large, ranging from 0.5 to 1.5 in Japan and from 0.5 to 1.3 near Parkfield at the San Andreas fault. The variation of the b-value within a region is commonly correlated with characteristics of regional seismic activities. For example, high seismicity in magma chambers may be characterized by high b-values. The initial rupture of large earthquakes, by contrast, was found to occur in regions where b-values are low. Previous studies pointed out that regions with low b-value imply large differential stress and suggests they are close to the end of their seismic cycle. Such a relationship can be applied for evaluating seismic hazard and earthquake forecasting, even though the validity of earthquake prediction experiments remains controversial (Chan et al. 2012).

A large number of scientific studies on seismicity parameters deal with the Gutenberg-Richter b-value as a possible earthquake precursor. The b-value time series are computed in different ways (e.g. time-based or event-based) with moving time windows or overlapping time windows. The analysis of the b-value may be realised in space or versus depth, and it is considered that its variations are related to the changes in the stress regimes and indicate the inverse relationship between b-value and differential stress in the crust. Other papers mention the b-value ratio time variation as a precursor parameter of large earthquakes. Most of these studies were realised in seismogenic zones with high seismic activity to assure a complete data set with thousands of events, e.g. in India, China and Japan (Enescu et al. 2011; Varotsos et al. 2017; Zhao and Wu 2008; Pallav 2017; Nuannin and Kulhanek 2012; Nuannin et al. 2005; Enescu et al. 2012; Ashtari-Jafari 2008; Gardonio et al. 2015). However, b-value changes in time, space or with depth have also been monitored all over the world, including Romania (Stănică et al. 2006; Enescu et al. 2008). The systematic study of b-values in different parts of the world has shown that within the vicinity of future large earthquakes, there is initially a decrease in b-value towards 0.5 and then a return to the previous level. This could be related to the stress changes expressed as seismicity changes.

9.1.3 Earthquake forecasting and predictions in Romania

INFP has a seismic network and multidisciplinary monitoring stations for radon concentration, CO₂, earth radiation, air ionization, telluric currents, ULF radio waves disturbance, magnetic field, temperature in boreholes, infrasound and acoustic waves. Specifics in the geological structure determined the monitoring locations. Seismicity is analysed using the cumulative energy method. Romania is divided into areas of release and accumulation of tectonic stress that are evaluated with polynomials permanently updated for the realization of seismicity evolution profiles for periods of maximum ten years. The results of interpolation over ten years are not reliable. The next step is to select the periods of analysis of precursor factors using the stress–rupture area diagrams. Every

earthquake has certain characteristics (distance between the epicentre and faults, depth, possibility to be induced by petroleum exploitation). For this reason, seismic precursors and analysis methods differ. Several parameters have the highest success rate a few hours before the micro-fracturing noise produced by rocks, borehole temperature and radon. This study highlights the interaction between seismic areas, faults, station locations and monitored parameters. By correlating the measured parameters with the geological characteristics of the monitored area, we can obtain a high probability of seismic prognosis. The main goal is to use the experience gained from the analysis of events produced to anticipate the future. An application of the cumulative energy method for Greece seismicity is presented in Thanassoulas (2007).

The monitoring area of Vrancea is presented in Figure 20. Many faults and intermediate earthquakes characterize the curvature of the Carpathian Mountains. The multidisciplinary monitoring stations are marked by red squares (Figure 20). Each location is in the area of influence of a fault. This is important for monitoring aerosol, ions, radio ULF waves propagation and radon monitoring. Figure 21 represents the seismicity of Vrancea and the cumulative seismic energy, a method of analysis used in this case: short-term earthquake forecast based on multi-parametric observations (Toader et al. 2019). The role of monitoring stations is to highlight the phenomena that precede intensive seismic periods for a short-term forecast. The monitoring equipment is chosen according to the geological features of the location. For example, radon detectors have been moved several times in search of a correlation with seismic activity.

Figure 20: Monitoring area, main faults, seismic stations (map by Dinu et al. CEEX 647/2005).

INFP uses the cumulative seismic energy method to forecast the seismicity for the next ten years. Over this period, the results are not reliable. The method is useful for a short-term forecast by correlating statistical data with multidisciplinary information acquired from monitoring stations. For this purpose, INFP developed a software application that allows updating the predicted seismicity according to the real one. A part of the information in the analysis is from the Romplus Catalog (created by NIEP), and another part of data is retrieved from the International Seismological Centre (ISC) web site. The software application uses four types of seismic bulletins. The magnitudes M_d , M_L , and m_b are transformed to M_w . The process begins by selecting the analysis area (Figure 21). In Figure 22 we use the same polynomial equation as in Figure 21. The equation is an interpolation

of known seismicity (1990 – 2019). The energy flow cases are presented in Figure 23, and they are the basis of the forecast of the evolution of seismicity. Each case is analysed for its duration and amplitude and the evaluated polynomial. The result is shown in Figure 22 for a period of +10 years.

Figure 21: Vrancea seismicity, 1990 – 2019, and the cumulative seismic energy.

Figure 22: Polynomial seismic energy evolution for Vrancea area (2004 – 2030).

Figure 23: Seismic energy evolution, acceleration, quiescence, shock.

Figure 24: Seismic energy evolution for Vrancea area (1990 – 2019.11).

This process is permanently updated and correlated with multiparametric real-time monitoring. Figure 24 presents (from top to bottom) the b-value of the Gutenberg-Richter law, gaps in seismicity (see also Figure 25 for a zoom), the evolution of hypocentral depths with time (the Moho area is visible in Figure 26 as well), magnitudes, cumulative energy, and the number of earthquakes in a period of time (displayed for a 7-day interval).

Figure 25: Gaps in seismicity evolution forecast earthquakes.

Figure 26: Vrancea seismicity, hypocentres, rupture areas, strains, 1990 – 2019.11.

Figure 26 presents the evolution of earthquake depths; hypocentral depths reported to latitude and longitude, the evolution of rupture areas and strains in time. A histogram presents the distribution of the number of earthquakes with depth. The tectonic stress generates many effects like increasing temperature, radon release, ionization, acoustic emission, variations of the telluric currents, variations of the local magnetic field and infrasound, variations of the atmospheric electrostatic field, electromagnetic effects, clouds formation, seismic activity and animal behaviour modification.

Besides the statistical and fractal methods for the study of seismic catalogues, including the slope of the frequency magnitude relationship (seismicity parameters a and b), time-independent and -dependent hazard assessments, the energy release evolution correlated with the occurrence of large earthquakes, and taking into account the distribution of real geophysical and geochemical fields related to the preparatory stages of earthquakes (Figure 27) there are many other studies. These studies have been realised all over the world to meet the desired outcome associated with earthquake predictions and forecasts: stress and strain monitoring, seismic velocities and all possible geophysical and geochemical fields as e.g. the geomagnetic field, electric resistivity, radon and other gases emissions, infrasound, and so on.

Figure 27: Preparatory stages of earthquakes after Pulinetz (2018).

Electromagnetic variations associated with earthquakes have been studied for many years by many authors. The short-term variations of the geomagnetic field in seismogenic zones have been associated with the physical processes that occur in the crustal areas affected by tectonic stress. Such natural electromagnetic phenomena may be caused by electromagnetic induction inside the Earth due to temporal variations of each magnetic and electrical component in a given area. In other words, the phenomena that occur during the "preparation" phase of an earthquake may cause anomalies that can be recorded. Crustal deformation and the appearance of these variations in the geomagnetic field have been analysed and explained by many researchers. Under stress, a piezo-magnetic effect occurs in rocks rich in ferromagnetic minerals from the earth's crust. Thus, ferromagnetic minerals in the rock's structure are magnetized, when the rocks are subjected to mechanical stress. Experimental studies have shown that the magnetization of rocks is directly proportional to the stress applied (Yamazaki 2011). Peroxide defects are defects in the structure of the silicates matrix. The theory of peroxidic

defects involves the generation of electromagnetic signals by breaking down these peroxidic defects. Silicates represent one-third of the total number of minerals and 75% of the volume of the earth's crust. Usually, the mineral structure of silicates is formed by pairs of oxygen anions having a valence of 2. Although less commonly encountered in the structure of silicates, there are anions with a valence of 1, forming a very short bond of the type "O - O-". These connections are also called peroxidatic defects, and subjected to stress are susceptible to breakage. With the breaking of these bonds, positive electric charges are released, which can disturb the geomagnetic field measured at the earth's surface (Freund and Sornette 2007).

The unusual behaviour of diurnal geomagnetic variations was observed before the 2011 earthquake located on the Pacific coast of Tohoku (Mw 9.0). The earthquake occurred on March 11, 2011 and was located 70 km from the shoreline of the Oshika peninsula (Japan). It generated a tsunami whose waves reached over 10 m high. The representation of diurnal variations between two stations showed an anomaly recorded on the vertical component of the geomagnetic field two months before the occurrence of this massive event. This study used three years of data, and this anomaly was unique. Further, a stochastic analysis was performed and demonstrated that this anomaly is unlikely to be a random observation (Xu et al. 2013).

Bleier et al. (2009) observed an increase in the number of electromagnetic pulses in the ULF domain with a band width of 0.01-12 Hz and short periods (1 s-30 s) before the Alum Rock (California) earthquake of M 5.4. The peak of the pulsations was reached 13 days before the earthquake, and the amplitude of the pulses was strong (3-20 nt), but the nature of these pulsations has been attributed to other causes: a) magnetic contamination generated by human anthropic activities, and b) magnetospheric noise (micro-pulses Pc 1, Pc3 and Pc4; Bleier et al. 2009).

The use of the electromagnetic method for earthquake prediction, obtaining some results regarding the short-term prediction of the earthquakes in Vrancea is discussed next. In order to test this method, INFP installed two electromagnetic stations in the Vrancea seismogenic area in 1997. This was the first time that this method was applied in Romania. Observations revealed that 57 earthquakes were clearly preceded by significant magnetic disturbances between 1997 to 2002. The disturbances were recorded several days to several weeks before each earthquake of magnitude larger than 3.9. During periods of seismic quiescence, no significant disturbances were recorded, which reinforces the conclusion that earthquakes of magnitudes greater than 3.9 are preceded by anomalies that can be recorded (Enescu et al. 2004; Enescu et al. 1999; Enescu and Enescu 1999).

Measurements of the electromagnetic signals in real-time were performed in the vicinity of the Vrancea seismic zone at Provița de Sus observatory (Prahova). This observatory belongs to the Sabba S. Stănescu Institute of Geodynamics and has both a fluxgate magnetometer and various geomagnetic sensors required for multiparametric and electromagnetic measurements.

The detrended fluctuation analysis (DFA) was employed on measurements recorded on fluxgate and search-coil magnetometers in ULF range (scales 10-90 s or 0.1-0.011 Hz) from January to April 2009, using data from South European GeoMagnetic Array stations. DFA is a processing method that allows the detection of scaling behaviours in observational time series even in the presence of non-stationarities. The H and Z field components have been examined at night hours (00-03 UT, 01-04LT) at the following stations: Castello Tesino (CST), L'Aquila (AQU), Nagycenk (NCK) and Panagyuriste (PAG). Their scaling characteristics were analysed depending on geomagnetic and local

conditions. As expected, the scaling exponents increased when the K_p index increases, indicating a good correlation with geomagnetic activity. Additionally, the scaling exponent also reveals local changes at the L'Aquila station, which include an increase of the amplitude on the vertical component (Z), followed by a decrease of the amplitude of the horizontal component during February more than two months before the mainshock (Nenovski et al. 2013).

The most powerful intermediate earthquake in the last 18 years produced in the Vrancea zone (2004, Mw 6) was accompanied by a geomagnetic anomaly, which affected only the horizontal component of the geomagnetic field. This anomaly was found by correlating the geomagnetic field recorded at Muntele Rosu (MLR) with the geomagnetic field recorded at Surlari (SUA) and Tihany (THY) stations. The last two stations were used as reference stations and are located outside the Vrancea seismogenic zone. The decrease was recorded two weeks before the earthquake occurred (Mason et al. 1998). The aim of the study by Mason et al. (1998) was to study the dynamic of geomagnetic field variations in relation to Vrancea seismic activity. A similar geomagnetic anomaly that affected one or more components of the geomagnetic field was pointed out by Takla et al. (2011) for the earthquake (Mw 6.4) that struck Taiwan in 2009. The anomaly was visible at the Hualien (HLN) station, located about 20 km away from the epicentre. Data sets from Hualien (HLN) were compared with datasets from Amani Oshima (AMA) from Japan, used as a remote reference. The geomagnetic east-east and vertical components recorded at HLN station showed a decrease of ~ 10 nT on these components one week before the occurrence of the earthquake that vanished after two weeks.

Similar anomalies with periods between 3 weeks and 6-7 months were analysed by Mihai et al. (2019), who noticed that the decrease in the geomagnetic components is directly proportional to the seismic activity. The morphology of these anomalies is mostly step-type, and a significant drop on one component is accompanied by larger earthquakes (Mihai et al. 2019). It has been observed that similar geomagnetic anomalies can accompany different types of seismic activity. The unequal distribution of seismic energy during two similar anomalies is explained by the depth occurrence of mainshocks (Mihai et al. 2019). In other words, days or weeks before a large earthquake, the magnetic sensors can record phenomena that may indicate the imminent occurrence of an earthquake.

A result of monitoring radon, solar radiation, magnetic field, atmospheric electrostatic field and lightning, CO_2 , air ionization, K_p , can be a short-term forecast. Figure 28 presents the case of two earthquakes with Mw 5.8 and the result of multidisciplinary monitoring. Data analysis involves knowing the daily, seasonal and annual evolution of measured parameters. Figure 29 presents the evolution of radon at the Bisoca station. However, during the lifetime of the geophysical networks, no large earthquake has occurred, so the methods are not yet calibrated or validated for earthquakes with magnitudes larger than Mw 6.0.

Figure 28: Multidisciplinary analysis.

Figure 29: Radon evolution at the INFP station Bisoca.

The only scientific gravimeter in Romania belongs to the Geodynamical Institute of the Romanian Academy of Science. An analysis of a database of over 2000 earthquakes by Cadicaneanu and Ruymbeke (2006), which occurred in Romania between 1982 and 2004, shows a tendency for the seismic activity to be linked to gravitational effects. The variety of the gradients that characterize a seismic zone (rigidity, heterogeneity, fluid circulation) could play an important role under the influences of the earth tides. In addition, the correlation of earthquakes with earth tides can be explained if local heterogeneities are amplifying the magnitude of the tidal stresses (Cadicaneanu and Ruymbeke 2006). The results indicate that more detailed work should be carried out with particular attention being paid to the geodynamical implications.

In 2009, the INFREP cooperation started in order to investigate the precursors of earthquakes. INFREP is a scientific cooperation among different international research teams. The cooperation aims to build up networks for measuring different physical and chemical parameters in order to search and study effects related to the occurrence of earthquakes. Currently the network is formed by ten receivers: two each in Italy, Romania and Greece; one each in Austria, Portugal, Cyprus and Georgia (Figure 30). The receivers, built by an Italian factory, can measure the intensity of ten radio signals in the band VLF (10-50 kHz) and LF (150-300 kHz) with a 1-minute sampling rate. The data collected are transmitted every day to the server located at the Department of Physics of the University of Bari (Italy) that is the central node of the network. The different temporal trends (10 for each receiver) are available to the public in real-time using the INFREP web site (infrep-eu.it), while the data base is protected by username and password.

Figure 30: INFREP Network.

As the purpose of this project is to reveal potential radio precursors, the data are analysed to discover “anomalies”, i.e. deviations from usual variations of the data trends. Generally, due to the different conditions of the ionosphere, the VLF/LF radio signals are less disturbed during nighttime than during daytime. Therefore, the analysis of the radio data is performed only on the data recorded at nighttime. To this end, the wavelet spectra are used. The “Morlet function” of the wavelet transform of a time signal is a complex series that can be usefully represented by its square amplitude, i.e. considering the so-called wavelet power spectrum. The power spectrum can be represented in a two dimensional plot that, once normalized with respect to the power of the white noise, gives information on the strength and precise time of occurrence of the various Fourier components that are present in the original time series. Generally, a colour from blue to red indicates an increase in the power strength; so, red zones define anomalies.

A software package able to automatically apply the wavelet analysis on radio data at the end of each day has been planned and developed. Currently, the software operates on the nighttime data of four signals collected by each of the following receivers: Cyprus, Crete, Greece and L'Aquila (IT). An alarm is triggered if an anomaly above a threshold is revealed. All results obtained with the wavelet analysis are archived on the INFREP web site.

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D3.1 – Part2: OEF, EEW and RRE feasibility studies

Report on the limits and potential applications of current state-of-the-art OEF, EEW and RRE systems for European conditions

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GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description

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TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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1 COST-BENEFIT ANALYSES TO ASSESS THE POTENTIAL OF OPERATIONAL EARTHQUAKE FORECASTING IN EUROPE

This report is part II of D3.1, the first deliverable of WP3 of the TURNkey project. Part I presented a literature review of Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF), Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) and Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE), while part II (this report) presents feasibility studies for OEF (section 1), EEW (section 2) and RRE (section 3) for Europe.

1.1 Introduction

The purpose of this section is to assess the potential of OEF for the mitigation of earthquake risk in Europe at a continental scale. For OEF to be useful, it needs to be able to trigger risk-mitigation actions (e.g. encourage citizens to reinforce earthquake drills, so they are better prepared in the case of a strong earthquake). OEF should aim at providing complete, authoritative, reliable and timely information before an event as well as during the aftershock period. All actions should be recommended but not prescribed, since political and psychological aspects must also be taken into consideration. A review of OEF is provided in Part I of this deliverable.

From a technical point of view, OEF works with the increase in the seismic hazard over a specific time window: short (days), moderate (weeks) or long (months) durations. Here, we focus on short-term OEF, corresponding to time ranges between one week (7 days) and one month (30 days). Therefore, the most important issue is whether (or, even if) we should recommend a specific action based on the level of hazard increment and the set of actions that are possible.

Simple cost-benefit analyses are conducted to assess in which cases such actions would be cost-beneficial. The approach is based on the proposal by Gordon Woo in the REAKT project (Deliverable D6.3, Woo, 2013) to use the benefit-to-cost ratio (Marzocchi and Woo 2009; Woo 2010; Woo 2013).

In the following section, the benefit-to-cost ratio is introduced as the basis of the approach. This section also includes a discussion of the assumptions and limitations of the approach. Following this, a brief review of the literature is provided on the use of cost-benefit analyses to rank risk mitigation actions for natural hazards. Next, the relevant inputs to the analyses are discussed, and some estimates of the key input parameters are made. The penultimate section presents generated maps for a range of input parameters. The final section presents brief conclusions. The analysis of if and when actions could and should be triggered by OEF is continued in subsequent deliverables of TURNkey, in particular within Tasks 3.2 and 5.3.

1.2 Cost-benefit analysis for OEF

The method used to assess the potential for OEF at a continental scale is based on the benefit-to-cost ratio, R , which is defined as, e.g. Marzocchi and Woo (2009); Woo (2010); Woo (2013):

$$R = \frac{pL}{c} \quad (1-1)$$

where p is the probability of occurrence of a ground motion intensity measure (IM), e.g. peak ground acceleration, PGA, above a threshold with the potential to cause loss during a specific number of days d ; and C is the cost of taking an action that leads to a reduction of that loss by an amount L . In general, the action will not mitigate the entire loss, but only a proportion of it. For example, if the action considered is an evacuation of a town then the total loss would include any structural damage that occurred, but this part of the loss would not have been mitigated by the action, only the loss associated with fatalities and injuries to the population evacuated. In this analysis, we are only considering direct costs and losses related to the action and not indirect costs, e.g. long-term business implications and losses, e.g. long-term environmental damage.

A beneficial action is one where $R > 1$. Brooks et al. (2016), for example, use the net benefit to decide when an action is beneficial rather than the benefit-to-cost ratio. The break-even point in the two cases is the same, but the benefit-to-cost ratio is easier to understand and is more commonly used within the field of natural hazards (see below).

1.2.1 Assumptions and limitations of the approach

A complete cost-benefit analysis of OEF would not be straightforward, and it is acknowledged that the assumptions made in the following analyses are considerable. These analyses aim to provide easily understandable maps and results on which parts of Europe would potentially benefit from the installation and operation of OEF. This information would be useful for deciding on which areas TURNkey, and subsequent projects, should focus their efforts with respect to OEF. Because of the requirement to cover all of Europe and the need to be general (i.e. not for a specific type of infrastructure or city), there is a need for simplification. Originally, we considered using the probability of a potentially damaging earthquake (e.g. magnitude 5+ earthquake at a given location) to conduct these analyses rather than the probability of exceedance of a ground-motion level. This approach was rejected because, firstly, it is more difficult to assess probabilities of earthquakes from the available input data and, secondly, because it is the ground motion itself rather than the earthquake that causes damage.

Readily available data, in particular the European Seismic Hazard Model 2013 (ESHM13) (Giardini et al. 2013; Woessner et al. 2015), are used for these analyses. This makes the analyses easier and quicker to undertake as well as being based on results that are well-respected and commonly used within the community. There will be updates to the seismic hazard assessments for the TURNkey testbeds (TBs), but these updates will not be made for all of Europe as this is outside the scope of TURNkey. There is also an update of ESHM13 planned for 2020, but this will be published too late to be included in the analyses presented in this section. It is worth mentioning that a comprehensive time-dependent PSHA is planned in Task 3.2, which will be employed in the OEF decision making procedure in Task 5.3.

The analyses below do not include the costs of installing and operating a system for OEF. Much of the required infrastructure (e.g. instruments, communication networks and personnel) are already operating over much of Europe as part of local, regional, national and international seismic monitoring programmes. Therefore, the additional cost of the monitoring part of OEF

is likely to be marginal and also spread out over the continent, so it is not correct to include it within the costs of a specific forecast. There will be a cost for communicating the forecasts to the public and other stakeholders, but this is not assessed here – again because it is likely to be minimal as communication channels through, for example, radio, TV and the internet already exist and are communally used for hydro-meteorological hazards (e.g. floods). This document aims to assess where OEF systems could potentially trigger cost-beneficial actions and assess the maximum cost of such actions to ensure that they are cost-beneficial.

It is common in cost-benefit analyses to adjust the costs or benefits by a discount rate, because they do not occur immediately but sometime in the future. In the case of short-term OEF, however, this adjustment is not required because of the short time scale considered (days to months) and the low inflation rates of European economies. The costs would incur now, and the loss avoided (benefit) would occur within the coming days or weeks.

One of the main assumptions of the approach is that the costs and losses mitigated are binary, i.e. either 0 or 1. The matrix of the four possible costs and losses is shown in Table 1. This assumption is justified for the scale of the analyses considered here and the requirement for the analyses to have general applicability. To use a more sophisticated loss model (e.g. a lognormal distribution as used for vulnerability curves) or cost models would require specific actions and elements at risk to be considered. This is out of the scope of these analyses, but will be considered within Tasks 3.2 and 5.3, once inputs from the TURNkey testbeds are used.

Table 1: Matrix of the possible costs and losses assumed within the cost-benefit analyses.

	No action taken	Action taken
$IM < \text{threshold}$	0	C
$IM \geq \text{threshold}$	L	C

Fiore et al. (2019) provide a justification for the use of Eq. 1-1 to conduct cost-benefit analyses. They find that the same formula provides a good first approximation to a more complete expression when: a) the discount rate is low, b) the period of consideration is also low and c) the rates of failure (before and after the action is taken) are also low (all of these are valid assumptions for short-term OEF given the actions that can be envisioned and the intervals of interest). By using Eq. 1-1, we are assuming that the rate of failure (loss) after the action is taken zero or more generally much less than the rate of failure (loss) if that action had not been taken.

Another strong assumption is that there is no epistemic uncertainty within the input parameters (although by employing the mean hazard curve from ESHM13, there is a certain consideration of the epistemic uncertainty, but this is only one aspect on the total uncertainty). This assumption is obviously not realistic when considering a specific testbed of action, but again considering the continental scope of these analyses, it is considered justified. In addition, through the production of maps for many choices of the input parameters, the sensitivity of the results to the inputs can be recognised.

In the following, PGA is used as the single IM within the calculations. This assumes that it is the most appropriate description of the earthquake ground motions that could cause a loss that

is reducible by taking an action associated with OEF. This is obviously not true as many studies have shown that IMs such as response spectral accelerations at the fundamental period of a structure or peak ground velocity are more appropriate in many situations. PGA was chosen, however, as it is a readily understood parameter for communication with end-users. PGA is also reasonably well correlated with macroseismic intensity, which means the use of PGA roughly captures the damage potential of earthquake ground motions. Finally, because of the relatively strong correlation between other measures of the amplitude of earthquake ground motions (e.g. Arias intensity, peak ground velocity and short-period response spectral accelerations) and PGA, e.g. Baker and Bradley (2017), it is likely that using one of these other IMs would lead to similar conclusions.

A fundamental assumption in the following calculations is that cost-benefit analyses are a good model for how people make (or should make) decisions. Cost-benefit analyses have a relatively long history in deciding on which risk mitigation actions should be funded, although often the results are used to “guide”, rather than make, decisions. A brief discussion of cost-benefit analyses in this context is provided in the following section. Wanigarathna and Yarovaya (2018) provide a useful overview of this topic, including a discussion of the various costs and benefits that should be considered in more detailed analyses.

1.3 Cost-benefit analyses for natural hazards

Mechler (2016) presented a useful review of cost-benefit analyses for risk mitigation. Mechler (2016) reports that R for earthquake risk mitigation actions ranges from 0.08 to 15.6 (average of 3.0) in the eight identified studies, which is lower than the average of 4.6 (range 0.1 to 30) from 21 studies on flood risk mitigation, but slightly higher than the average of 2.6 (range 0.05 to 50) from 7 studies on extreme wind risk mitigation. An excellent summary of the results of over a hundred cost-benefit analyses for natural hazards (floods, landslides, earthquakes, droughts, storms and combinations of hazards) is provided by Hugenbusch and Neumann (2016). They identify 11 studies conducting cost-benefit analyses for earthquakes. In almost all cases the mitigation actions were “structural” (e.g. retrofitting of vulnerable buildings) rather than “non-structural” (e.g. knowledge transfer, capacity building and codes or norms, such as land-use planning). In nine of these studies, earthquakes actions were not assessed as cost-beneficial either in whole or in part. Hugenbusch and Neumann (2016) find that non-structural actions are often more cost-beneficial when considering all natural hazards together. Godschalk et al. (2009), who summarise benefit-to-cost ratios for projects funded by the US’s Federal Emergency Management Agency, reached similar conclusions. They note that process grants (investments in human, social or institutional capital) for earthquake risk mitigation have an average ratio of 2.5, which is higher than for wind (1.7) and flood (1.3) process grants, whereas project grants (investments in physical capital) for earthquake risk mitigation have an average ratio of 1.4, which is much lower than for wind (4.7) and flood (5.1) project grants. As the type of actions that is possible in the context of OEF would be classed as “non-structural” or “process grants”, given the time available to take them, this finding is promising for OEF.

There have been a number of probabilistic cost-benefit analyses for retrofitting vulnerable structures against earthquakes. Examples of these include Smyth et al. (2004), Ghesquiere et al. (2006), Kunreuther and Michel-Kerjan (2012), Liel and Deierlein (2013), and Wei et al.

(2014) and references therein. These studies often find that extensive retrofitting is not cost-beneficial ($R < 1$) or is only marginally cost-beneficial (R between 1 and 1.5) except for the most vulnerable structures and those with many inhabitants. Such calculations rely on extensive computations using earthquake risk assessment software and detailed hazard and vulnerability inputs. As such they are unfeasible for the purpose of this part of Task 3.1 of TURNkey, because of the scale of the analysis (all Europe), the resources available and the need to be general about the type of mitigation actions considered. For earthquake risk, there are very few studies that conduct cost-benefit analyses for actions other than retrofitting buildings. Retrofitting is not possible to undertake in the context of short-term OEF because it would take longer to perform than the period of heightened hazard will likely last. A recent discussion of the issues surrounding the use of cost-benefit analyses for relatively short periods (weeks or months) of heightened hazard (in this case volcanic hazard) is provided by Woo (2015).

Brooks et al. (2016) conduct simple cost-benefit analyses to assess whether a water heater should be secured against earthquake shaking. They concluded that for areas of low seismic hazard, such as Chicago, this action is not beneficial, but that in areas of higher seismic hazard it could be. Strauss and Allen (2016) present some simple cost-benefit analyses for the operation of an earthquake early warning system for the west coast of the USA. The costs of this system were taken from a previous study, and the benefits were assessed in a simple way using losses from a variety of causes in recent earthquakes and based on simulations. There is little discussion of the probabilities associated with these potential losses. Holden et al. (1989), when studying the potential for an earthquake early warning system for California, find that there is too much uncertainty (based on the results of a survey of potential end-users) in the potential benefits of such a system to conduct a detailed cost-benefit analysis. They do, however, formulate the analysis in a similar way as proposed here, although they use the net benefit (rather than the benefit-to-cost ratio). Plag et al. (2014) use simple cost-benefit analysis (using Eq. 1-1 to estimate how much money should be invested per year worldwide to reduce the risk associated with extreme volcanic eruptions (they estimate this total as several billion dollars per year).

Cost-benefit analyses for short-term forecasts (often called “early warning” in the literature) of other natural hazards (e.g. floods or extreme winds) often show values of benefit-to-cost ratios much larger than unity (i.e. they are clearly cost-beneficial), e.g. Hallegatte (2012). Therefore, “early warning” has been recommended as a good way of mitigating risk in less developed countries, e.g. Copenhagen Consensus Center (2012). This is because the probability of the hazardous event occurring following a forecast is much higher, so costly actions such as evacuation (in case of a hurricane warning or flood) or construction of temporary protective works (e.g. sandbags to protect against floodwaters) become beneficial. As shown below, the probabilities of potentially damaging earthquake ground motions occurring in a short interval are small, even in periods of increased seismicity. Therefore, the costs of risk mitigation actions also need to be small to make them cost-beneficial.

1.4 Assessment of the input parameters to the analyses

In this section, potential risk mitigation actions are listed (that could be triggered by OEF), the various input parameters to the cost-benefit analyses are discussed and a range of plausible values for these input parameters are proposed.

1.4.1 Potential actions and corresponding thresholds, losses and costs

The above framework, as expressed in Eq. 1-1, is based on three principal variables: p , L and C . The first variable, p , is an indicator of the real-time seismic hazard for the location considered (this is discussed in a subsequent section). p is also a function of d , the number of days for which the action is implemented. Finally, p is also a function of the threshold PGA (as noted above, only PGA is considered in these calculations): as the threshold PGA increases, p decreases. The effect of changing the threshold PGA can be estimated by making use of the observation that seismic hazard curves typically follow a power law, which is discussed next. If L/C remained the same, a lower threshold would make the mitigation actions appear more beneficial and vice versa for a higher threshold.

Seismic hazard curves can often be parameterised using a power law, i.e.: $H(y)=k_0 y^{-k_1}$, where y is the value of the IM of interest (e.g. PGA), H is the annual frequency of exceedance, and k_0 and k_1 are site-specific coefficients chosen to fit the hazard curve over the exceedance frequencies of interest. Therefore, assuming that annual frequency of exceedance and daily probabilities of exceedance are proportional (this is not strictly correct, but it is likely almost true for the ground-motions levels of interest here), there is roughly a one-to-one mathematical relationship between the daily probabilities of exceedance of two ground-motion levels. This relationship is given by $(y_2/y_1)^{k_1}$, where y_1 is the lower ground-motion level, and y_2 is the higher ground-motion level. Figure 14 of Gkimprixis et al. (2019) shows that k_1 varies between 1.5 and 2.5 for much of Europe (based on ESHM13). Therefore, if for example, $y_1=0.05$ g and $y_2=0.2$ g, then the ratio of the weekly probabilities of exceedance of these ground-motion levels would be between 8 and 32. This technique can be used to obtain the ground-motion levels for any frequency of exceedance, when ground-motion levels are only available for a handful of frequencies of exceedance (usually provided by design codes).

The second and third variables within Eq. 1-1, L and C , are functions of the risk-mitigation actions that are considered in the analysis. Rather than using actual values of loss and cost, it is easier and more general to use the ratio L/C . Therefore, this ratio is used from now on. Potential actions and corresponding L/C values are discussed in the following section.

1.4.2 Potential risk-mitigation actions

Because of the relatively short periods for which OEF is likely to operate, only actions that can be taken quickly can be considered. Therefore, it is not possible to recommend structural retrofitting of vulnerable structures, for example, as this would take many weeks or months to put in place. In this section, some example actions are discussed. Many of these are taken from previous publications on OEF, others originated within the TURNkey community.

The types of losses that the actions seek to mitigate, are:

- human losses, e.g. death, major and minor injuries that require hospitalisation and very minor injuries (e.g. cuts and bruises);
- damage to non-structural elements and building contents;
- knock-on impacts such as fire, chemical leaks and business interruption due to damaged equipment.

As noted above, OEF cannot typically be used to mitigate structural losses (e.g. building collapse). When proposing the framework used here, Woo (2013) considered four actions for a period of heightened hazard in Emilia (northern Italy) in June 2012 (following the destructive earthquakes the month before). He proposed that:

1. the civil protection supplies could be restocked ($C=1,000$ euros and $L=500,000$ euros);
2. the military and fire-fighters contingent in the area could be increased ($C=5,000$ and $L=1,000,000$ euros);
3. a rapid vulnerability map of the city of Ferrara could be created ($C=1,000$ euros and $L=1,000,000$ euros); and
4. all stocks of the Ferrara Nord petro-chemical complex could be removed ($C=20,000$ euros, $L=20,000,000$ euros).

The values of L and C for these actions, taken from Woo (2013), lead to L/C ratios between 200 and 1,000. Other potential actions, grouped into categories depending on who would be responsible for taking and requiring the action, are given in Table 2. Field et al. (2016) provide a comprehensive discussion of the types of actions that could be triggered by OEF.

Table 2: Potential actions for OEF.

Responsible party	Potential actions
General public	Checking food, water, medical supplies; having cash on hand; keeping phones charged and fuel in the car; reviewing family emergency plans; securing household objects
Private sector	Insurance/banks/industry advisory; securing business premises; relocating business premises; relocating employees to other branches of the business; activating structural control systems
Public sector	Assuring smooth operation of important infrastructure, hospitals, police, mobile phone network, etc.; checking emergency plans/monitoring systems; reinforcing earthquake drills; school/hospital/transportation/police/services advisory; conditioning earthquake early warning systems to expect future earthquakes in regions of increased seismic activity; checking the town for dangerous non-structural elements (e.g. flower pots and shop signs) and removing them; require the evacuation of vulnerable buildings; require sleeping outside; restrict travel to an area with elevated hazard; evacuating people to areas where the hazard is not elevated.

Within WP3, discussions with TURNkey's testbed partners were undertaken to decide on appropriate L/C ratios for different potential actions of relevance to the testbeds. The purpose of these discussions was not to assess L and C for every possible action at all testbeds but to assess the overall range of possible L/C ratios, which can then be used to decide on which ratios to use for the maps below. Because of the limited experience of OEF in practice, it proved impossible to assess L/C through this approach. Therefore, four possible actions are considered below to provide more guidance on the L/C values to be used for the maps. Because it is comprehensive, the main basis for potential actions is FEMA (2012) – all images come from that source. FEMA (2015) provides a very comprehensive set of illustrations of the importance of non-structural damage during the 2014 Napa earthquake in California. Non-structural components often contribute a large proportion of the costs of a building and its contents, e.g. Porter (2016) notes that they are on average about two-thirds of the total cost. Therefore, even if OEF cannot be used to mitigate major structural damage and associated deaths or injuries, if OEF can help to reducing non-structural losses, even by a small amount, this would constitute a significant contribution.

Below the list of losses mitigated and costs of the actions, there is an estimate of the losses in terms of dollars based on the photo shown. Note that these estimates are very rough as there is insufficient detail in the photo to provide a more accurate estimate. Ideally, these estimates should be made for each testbed. From these examples, L/C ratios between about 20 and 1,000 can easily be justified.

Table 3: Four potential actions for OEF, the losses mitigated by these actions, the costs of taking the action and estimated values of *L* and *C*. All images from FEMA (2012).

Action	Example of damage without this action [photos from FEMA (2012)]	Losses mitigated by taking this action	Cost of taking this action
<p>Removal of heavy objects from shelves or securing the objects so that they cannot fall in case of an earthquake.</p>	<p>Damage to overloaded racks during the 1994 Northridge earthquake.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • value of the objects stored on the shelves (or a proportion of this in case the objects are not completely destroyed); • potentially human losses if the objects hit persons during the shaking; • damage to other items if they are hit by falling objects. <p>Estimated minimum total loss for this picture=100 boxes x 100 dollars per box=\$10,000.</p> <p>This assumes that the boxes do not contain fragile or particularly valuable goods. Also, it assumes that they are located in a room where people do not circulate (if not,</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • surveying to see what elements are at risk of falling; • time to remove the objects from the shelves and move them elsewhere; • potentially cost of additional storage space if it needs to be hired/bought; • potentially increased cost of additional time if objects are not close at hand. <p>Estimated cost of removal of items from shelves=100 boxes x 1/10 hour (6 minutes) per box x 20 dollars per hour=\$200</p> <p>Hence $L/C=20$ (minimum) but it could be much higher if people are at risk of injury or there are knock-on costs .</p>

		then the loss could be much higher).	
<p>Removal or securing of non-essential exterior or interior elements at height from buildings (e.g. signs, plant pots and air-conditioning units).</p>	<p>Failure of commercial sign during the 1979 Imperial Valley, California earthquake.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • value of the element (generally this will not be very high in comparison with the knock-on impacts); • potentially human losses if the objects fall on persons during the shaking; • damage to other items (e.g. cars) if they are hit by falling objects. <p>Estimated total loss for this picture=\$1,000,000 (loss of life) x 1/100 (the chance that a person will be hit by sign)=\$10,000.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • surveying to see what elements are at risk of falling; • time to remove/secure the elements; • loss of business (if signs), discomfort (if air-conditioning units) or use if elements removed or secured so that they cannot be used. <p>Estimated cost of removing the sign from the building=\$20 (one hour's work).</p> <p>Hence $L/C=500$ but it could be much higher if this is a busy street or the sign can be removed easily.</p>

<p>Securing (even temporarily) or removal (out of endangered area) of gas cylinders (or other dangerous product) so that they cannot fall over or be damaged.</p>	<p>Unanchored tanks inside a fenced enclosure during the 1994 Northridge earthquake.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • value of the element (generally this will not be very high in comparison with the knock-on impacts); • knock-on impacts, e.g. fire or chemical spill. <p>Estimated total loss for this picture=\$1,000,000 (loss of building due to fire) x 1/100 (the chance that cylinder will explode when it falls)=\$10,000.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • surveying to see what objects are at risk of damage; • time to remove/secure the cylinders; • loss of use of the product if elements removed or secured so that they cannot be used. <p>Estimated cost of securing cylinders using rope=\$20 (one hour's work).</p> <p>Hence $L/C=500$ but it could be much higher if the building is very valuable or lower if the cylinders are more robust.</p>
<p>Securing (even temporarily, e.g. putting into a padded box) or removal (out of endangered area) of a precious artistic or heritage objects (e.g. sculptures).</p>	<p>A fallen sculpture that collapsed in the 2010 Chile earthquake.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • value of the element (this could be very high); • potentially human losses if the objects fall on persons during the shaking; • damage to other items (e.g. cars) if they are hit by falling objects. <p>Estimated total loss for this picture=\$50,000 (price of repairing sculpture).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • surveying to see what objects are at risk of damage; • time to remove/secure the objects; • loss of use (e.g. museum closures) of the object if elements removed or secured so that they cannot be viewed. <p>Estimated cost of removing sculpture=\$50 (2.5 hours work).</p> <p>Hence $L/C=1,000$ but it could be much higher if the sculpture is very valuable or lower if it is difficult to remove.</p>

1.4.3 Assessment of the probability of surpassing the PGA threshold

The assessment of p , the probability of surpassing the PGA threshold, is made using ESHM2013¹ (Giardini et al. 2013; Woessner et al. 2015). The annual frequencies of exceedances for the considered PGA thresholds were assessed through spline interpolation of the hazard curves (in terms of logarithms) calculated using the ESHM2013 maps for all six available return periods (72, 102, 475, 975, 2475 and 4975 years). Extrapolation has been done for the points less than 72 or greater than 4975 years return period, by assuming a linear regression in logarithmic space using the two nearest data points.

Next, the annual frequencies of exceedance are converted to daily rates (dividing by 365) and from these, p is estimated using a Poisson distribution for the considered number of days, d . Because OEF is generally used to trigger actions during short periods when the chance of a damaging earthquake ground motions has increased, only relatively low values for d (≤ 30) are considered in the following. The probability indicated employing this method is the long-term (time-independent) chance of surpassing the PGA threshold. Therefore, in areas for which the considered action is shown to be cost-beneficial ($R > 1$), the action should be taken without any need for OEF, i.e. it is cost-beneficial for the time-independent seismic hazard of that area.

The potential utility of OEF is to trigger additional risk mitigation actions during periods of a heightened chance of occurrence of a large earthquake. Therefore, increases in the time-independent probabilities obtained from ESHM2013 are considered in the following analyses by increasing p by a factor. Because this study aims to provide general guidance on where and for which actions OEF may be cost-beneficial, the factor of how much p can increase from its time-independent value is assessed using available literature as well as by using simple probabilistic seismic hazard assessments (PSHAs) for the six geographical testbeds of TURNkey.

There are a number of studies available in the literature that provide estimates of how much the probability of a potentially damaging earthquake increased during particular sequences. In this report, we are using the probability of potentially damaging ground motions (in terms of PGA) rather than an earthquake to compute the benefit-to-cost ratio of different actions. The relationship between the probability an earthquake exceeding a particular size (e.g. Mw 6) and the probability of PGA exceeding a threshold is not linear (see e.g. Figure 3 from Douglas and Danciu (2020)), and hence there is a potential difficulty in using the probability increases reported in the literature. For the relatively low daily probabilities and PGA thresholds considered here and given the large assumptions in other parts of the analysis, however, the slight nonlinearity in the relationship is ignored. PSHAs, conducted especially for this study, for a single source zone of uniform seismicity following a Gutenberg-Richter law and considering different long-term activity rates showed that assuming equality between an increase in the probability of an earthquake larger than a certain magnitude and the increase in the probability of a PGA larger than a certain threshold leads to an error that is negligible for the purposes of this analysis.

¹ <http://www.efehr.org/en/hazard-data-access/hazard-maps/>

Reported increases in daily probabilities of potentially damaging earthquakes range from about 20-fold (Marzocchi et al. 2015) to roughly 1000-fold (Gulia et al. 2016; McBride et al. 2020). Jordan and Jones (2010) noted that the short-term earthquake probability (STEP) model that used to be deployed by USGS (Gerstenberger et al. 2005) often showed increases in probabilities of ground motions exceeding a modified Mercalli Intensity of VI of 10 to 100 times (Gerstenberger et al., 2005, displayed a map with increases of up to 30-fold in parts of California). These observed increases in previous sequences will define the values considered when drawing the maps below (Figure 3 to Figure 8). It is noted that all identified studies providing estimates of probability increases of either large earthquake occurrence or ground-motion exceedance are for highly seismically active areas such as Italy and California. Therefore, these large increases in probabilities may not be appropriate for all areas of Europe, including areas of very low seismicity such as a large part of the north of the continent. There is insufficient information and earthquake catalogues are too sparse in these regions to allow to distinguish those areas from the more active areas concerning the size of any potential increase in probability. This is another uncertainty in the following maps.

It is also worth noting that in this report, the focus is on natural seismicity rather than seismicity induced by human actions (e.g. fluid injection, mining and dam impounding). Induced seismicity can lead to rapid increases in the probability of a potentially damaging earthquake occurring within a small area (e.g. earthquakes caused by gas extraction in the TURNkey testbed of Groningen). The approach followed in this report could be applied to induced seismicity by using an appropriate value for the increase in the probability of an earthquake occurring. It is unlikely, though, that the assumption that the hazard curve shape remains the same would hold in the case of induced seismicity (induced events are likely to be biased towards smaller magnitudes than natural events, i.e. resulting in a larger b value).

To provide additional guidance on the possible increases in short-term hazard, a small-scale study has been undertaken for the six TURNkey geographical testbeds, including TB 3 in south Iceland, which is used as a common testbed throughout WP3. The approach followed is illustrated for TB 3. The earthquake catalogue has been gathered from the International Seismological Centre² between 1980 and 2017 and from the European Mediterranean Seismological Centre³ between 2017 and 2019. This catalogue is filtered with respect to the centre of each testbed (Hveragerdi for testbed 3) to provide the seismicity for a circle of 100 km radius and a minimum moment magnitude of 3. Monthly catalogues have been used to calculate the Gutenberg-Richter relationship by assuming a slope equal to unity. Therefore, only the Gutenberg-Richter a -value changes in each monthly window. The monthly catalogues are used within a conventional PSHA assuming a circular area source of 100 km radius and a threshold PGA equal to 0.05 g. The Boore and Atkinson (2008) ground-motion model is used for the hazard calculations. The probability gain is defined as the ratio between the annual frequency of exceedance based on the current one-month catalogue to the annual frequency of exceedance based on the previous one-month catalogue. The results of the probability gains (only showing increases) are shown in Figure 1, from which a maximum gain of 1,258 can be deduced. The probability gain results for other testbeds are summarised in Table 4. Based on Table 4 and the available literature, we have assumed probability gains of 1, 10, 100, and 1,000 for the parametric

² <http://www.isc.ac.uk/>

³ <https://www.emsc-csem.org/>

analyses in the next section. It is worth emphasising that a more comprehensive estimation of the probability gain is planned in Task 3.2, where we will develop time-dependent seismicity models as well as short-term probabilistic seismic hazard analyses.

Figure 1: The variation of probability gain in TB 3 (south Iceland) between 1980 and 2019.

Table 4: The maximum probability gain for the six TURNkey geographical testbeds.

Testbed	Representative Lat. (N)	Representative Lon. (E)	Maximum Probability Gain
1- Bucharest	44.4268	26.1025	1613
2- Pyrenees	42.6682	1.0012	136
3- Iceland	63.9995	-21.1797	1263
4- Patras and Aegio	38.2466	21.7346	21
5- Gioia-Tauro	38.4262	15.8989	59
6- Groningen	53.2194	6.5665	530

1.5 Maps indicating areas in which actions are cost-beneficial

To show the impact of the various input parameters and because of the large uncertainties in their assessment and how they vary for different actions and locations, a large number of maps is shown in the following. The input parameters considered are:

- the crisis duration (d): 7 days and 30 days (1 month);
- loss to cost ratio (L/C): 10, 100, 1,000, and 10,000;
- the threshold PGA: 46 cm/s^2 (corresponding to macroseismic intensity V), 84 cm/s^2 (corresponding to macroseismic intensity VI), and 154 cm/s^2 (corresponding to macroseismic intensity VII) by using the relationship of Caprio et al. (2015);
- the probability gain, which indicates the earthquake hazard probability increases within the duration of the crisis: 1 (no increase), 10, 100 and 1,000.

As any triggered action should be cost-beneficial (i.e. R must be greater than unity), the following ranges of R are indicated: $R < 1$ (not cost-beneficial), R between 1 and 1.5 (marginally cost-beneficial), R between 1.5 and 2.5 (moderately cost-beneficial), R between 2.5 and 5 (clearly cost-beneficial) and R greater than 5 (highly cost-beneficial). It is worth emphasising that this indicator is a real-time variable based on the OEF framework and hence within a future TURNkey platform, the real-time value for this parameter could be provided to the user to make their own decisions.

The benefit-to-cost ratio results are shown in Figure 2 in the case of $L/C=1,000$, probability gain=100, threshold PGA=46 cm/s^2 and for both $d=7$ and $d=30$ days. $L/C=1,000$ may seem like a high ratio as it suggests that mitigation only costs 0.1% of the total loss, but some actions discussed in Table 3 would have such high ratios. A probability gain of 100 corresponds to a significant increase in the earthquake hazard in the crisis duration period, which has been observed in past earthquake sequences (see Table 4 and section 1.4.3). As seen in Figure 2, OEF is beneficial in the most of Europe except in a few parts in the north of the continent. This demonstrates that OEF cheap actions are clearly beneficial, especially when the hazard increases for a short time period.

For the longer crisis period (30 days), the OEF actions are even more cost-beneficial as visible in Figure 2 by comparing the maps for 7 and 30 days, e.g. OEF is marginally, moderately or clearly cost-beneficial in the south of the UK and parts of Norway in the case of $d=7$ days, but it becomes highly cost-beneficial when the crisis duration increases to 30 days. Maps for the various combinations of d , L/C , threshold PGA, and probability gains are shown in Figure 3 to Figure 8. For example in Figure 3, the L/C ratio increases from top to bottom (10 to 10,000), and the probability gain increases from left to right (1 to 1,000). The top-left cell in Figure 3 corresponds to no probability gain and $L/C=10$, which shows no OEF benefit. This seems reasonable, since this case corresponds to no short-term increase in the hazard and the mitigated cost action is 10% of the loss, which is expensive. When either the seismic hazard increases significantly or large L/C ratios are considered, OEF becomes cost-beneficial (highly cost-beneficial in some cases). The threshold PGA increases from Figure 3 to Figure 5 and shows that the highest OEF benefits are obtained for the lowest threshold PGA (i.e. 46 cm/s^2) as expected. One interpretation would be that the actions for mitigating secondary systems are beneficial for OEF as also described in section 1.4.2. Figure 6 to Figure 8 present the results for 30 days of crisis duration. If Figure 6 to Figure 8 are compared to Figure 3 to Figure 5, it can be seen that OEF actions are more justifiable for long crisis periods.

Figure 2: Cost-benefit analysis assuming $L/C=1000$, probability gain=100, and threshold $PGA=46 \text{ cm/s}^2$. $d=7$ days in the top figure and $d=30$ days in the bottom figure.

Figure 3: Crisis duration=7 days, $PGA=46 \text{ cm/s}^2$, rows from top to bottom corresponding to the L/C 10, 100, 1000 and 10000, and columns from left to right are corresponding to probability gains equal to 1, 10, 100 and 1000.

Figure 4: Crisis duration=7 days, PGA=84 cm/s², rows from top to bottom corresponding to the L/C 10, 100, 1000 and 10000, and columns from left to right are corresponding to probability gains equal to 1, 10, 100 and 1000.

Figure 5: Crisis duration=7 days, PGA=154 cm/s², rows from top to bottom corresponding to the L/C 10, 100, 1000 and 10000, and columns from left to right are corresponding to probability gains equal to 1, 10, 100 and 1000.

Figure 6: Crisis duration=30 days, PGA=46 cm/s², rows from top to bottom corresponding to the L/C 10, 100, 1000 and 10000, and columns from left to right are corresponding to probability gains equal to 1, 10, 100 and 1000.

Figure 7: Crisis duration=30 days, PGA=84 cm/s², rows from top to bottom corresponding to the L/C 10, 100, 1000 and 10000, and columns from left to right are corresponding to probability gains equal to 1, 10, 100 and 1000.

Figure 8: Crisis duration=30 days, PGA=154 cm/s², rows from top to bottom corresponding to the L/C 10, 100, 1000 and 10000, and columns from left to right are corresponding to probability gains equal to 1, 10, 100 and 1000.

1.5.1 How often would an OEF system trigger a potential action?

The interval between potential triggers of actions by an OEF system needs to be sufficiently short, such that the local population is aware of what to do and such that the system can be calibrated and tested during actual periods of heightened hazard. If an OEF system only triggers once every century or less frequently, it is unlikely that the local population will take the warning seriously or even be aware that earthquakes are a potential threat. The average interval between potential triggers using time-independent seismicity (i.e. not including crisis periods) is simply the return period of the intensity of interest. The map of the average interval between potential triggers is shown in Figure 9. As seen in Figure 9, grey denotes an interval of less than 50 years and red an interval of less than 10 years (i.e. a potential trigger once a decade).

Figure 9: The average interval between potential triggers using time-independent seismicity (the return period of the intensity of interest). The top, middle and bottom figures correspond to 46 cm/s², 84 cm/s², and 154 cm/s², respectively.

1.6 Nomogram for quick calculations of benefit-to-cost ratios

Nomograms e.g. Levens (1959) are graphical tools that allow complex equations to be evaluated to high accuracy simply using a print-out of the nomogram and a straight edge. They were common in many fields of engineering in the era before digital computers became ubiquitous, i.e. up to the 1980s, as they reduced the likelihood of computational errors. As argued by Douglas and Danciu (2020), who present a nomogram summarising the results of simple PSHAs, nomograms are still potentially useful as they visually present the connections among the variables within an equation and allow the sensitivity of the results to changes in those variables to be assessed easily. In this section, a nomogram for the simple cost-benefit analyses for OEF is presented.

The nomogram presents the relations between five variables: threshold PGA (in g), daily probability of an earthquake of moment magnitude 4 or larger, the number of days for which the OEF action is taken (d), the ratio of the loss mitigated to the cost of the OEF action (L/C) and the benefit-to-cost ratio (R). The nomogram was created using the open-source pynomo software⁴ using a type 3 nomogram, which consists of five parallel vertical axes. Note that one advantage of a nomogram over normal graphs is that any variable of the equation can be the subject, i.e., in this case, the value of any of the five variables can be found given the other four. Before presenting the final nomogram, the steps followed to construct it are briefly described.

Following the success of Douglas and Danciu (2020) in deriving a nomogram for PSHA, a similar approach was followed here. The first step was to evaluate the daily frequencies of exceedance of three potential PGA thresholds: 0.05 g, 0.1 g and 0.2 g for the OEF actions for different daily probabilities of earthquakes of moment magnitude 4 or larger. This was done using the Excel spreadsheet developed by John Douglas for PSHA of a circular area of radius 100 km of uniform seismicity⁵, but modified to use the Cauzzi and Faccioli (2008) PGA ground-motion model. This ground-motion model was used because it was one of the two highest weighted ground-motion models in the logic tree for crustal earthquakes used to derive ESHM13 (Delavaud et al. 2012).

This Excel spreadsheet was evaluated considering nine logarithmically-spaced daily probabilities of earthquakes of moment magnitude 4 or larger between 0.0087% and 58%. A b value of 1 was assumed as was a Poisson distribution to convert between frequencies of exceedance and probabilities. The result was the daily probabilities of exceeding the three threshold PGAs for each of the nine daily earthquake probabilities. Using the common assumption of a power-law to approximate the hazard curve, which Douglas and Danciu (2020) demonstrated to perform very well for simple PSHAs, linear equations were derived between the logarithms of the PGA thresholds and their corresponding probabilities of exceedance for each of the nine daily earthquake probabilities considered. It was found that the slope of these linear equations was almost identical for all earthquake probabilities, but that the intercept changed. This intercept could be itself expressed as a linear function of the daily earthquake probabilities. The result of these steps is a function connecting the daily probability of occurrence of an earthquake of magnitude 4 or larger (for any value between 0.0087% and 58%) and the corresponding daily probability of exceeding any PGA value between 0.05 and 0.2 g.

⁴ http://pynomo.org/wiki/index.php/Main_Page

⁵ https://figshare.com/articles/Probabilistic_seismic_hazard_assessment_for_circular_area_using_Excel/11726631

Because the daily probabilities of exceeding the PGA thresholds considered are all lower than 1%, it was assumed that the probability of exceeding the threshold within a period of days (up to 30 days, i.e. a month) was simply the daily probability multiplied by the number of days. This is not correct as the Poisson distribution should be invoked, but the error introduced by this assumption is low, and it allows the equation for the benefit-to-cost ratio to be expressed as a linear function in terms of logarithms (in order to convert from a product), i.e.:

$$\ln R = \ln d + \ln p_{GM} + \ln L/C, \quad (1-2)$$

where $\ln p_{GM}$ is the logarithm of the daily probability of exceeding the threshold PGA, which itself (given the previous step) is a linear function of the logarithm of the daily probability of an earthquake of moment magnitude 4 or large occurring.

Through these steps, it is possible to express the equation for the benefit-to-cost ratio in the form required for a type 3 nomogram, i.e.:

$$f(R) + f(d) + f(p_E) + f(y) + f\left(\frac{L}{C}\right) = 0, \quad (1-3)$$

where y is the threshold PGA considered for the action. It is possible to consider L and C as two separate variables, but it was decided that this would complicate the use of the nomogram without much benefit as it is often easier to consider the ratio L/C rather than the individual components.

The resulting nomogram is shown in

Figure 10 with an isopleth drawn for a threshold PGA of 0.05 g, a daily probability of a moment magnitude 4 or larger earthquake occurring of 4%, a week-long OEF action (i.e. $d=7$ days) and an L/C of 1,000. This leads to an R of about 3.5. To use this nomogram, values on the five vertical principal axes should be connected by straight lines via the two vertical secondary axes (labelled R_1 and R_2).

Figure 10: The nomogram developed for cost-benefit analysis of OEF actions.

1.7 Conclusions

Areas of high seismic hazard (e.g. Iceland, Italy, Greece and Turkey) will benefit from OEF if there are low-cost (cost ratios $< 0.1\%$) short-term mitigation actions that can be performed even if the increase in the weekly probability of an earthquake is moderate. These triggers would also occur sufficiently often (more frequently than every 10 to 50 years) in these areas for the local population to have prior experience of what actions to take. Areas of moderate seismic hazard (e.g. Alps, Pyrenees, Rhine graben and south Spain) would only benefit from OEF in the case of very large increases in weekly probabilities and only if low-cost actions are possible (here, the triggers would occur infrequently, i.e. less often than once every 50 years). If the crisis period (heightened hazard) persists for a number of weeks, more expensive actions become cost-beneficial. If actions can mitigate losses that are caused by low-amplitude ground motions, then these actions are more cost-beneficial than actions related to losses caused by stronger earthquake shaking, because low-amplitude ground motions occur much more frequently.

It is possible that even if R is less than unity for a given action (i.e. it is not assessed as being cost-beneficial) that the action may be taken by some people if it was sufficiently cheap (low C) or easy to do. For example, there is a personal cost of risk mitigation actions in day-to-day life (e.g. keeping a well-stocked first aid cabinet) that may not be cost-beneficial given the chance that it is required, but the cost to most people is sufficiently low that this cost is not a barrier to choosing this action.

In conclusion, despite the considerable assumptions made, the results of the simple cost-benefit analyses presented here show that short-term OEF has the potential to trigger cost-beneficial actions over much of Europe, especially if low-cost actions (cost ratios $< 0.1\%$) are identified for an element at risk.

2 EXPLORING EARTHQUAKE EARLY WARNING FEASIBILITY ACROSS EUROPE

This section aims to quantitatively assess the limits and potentials of EEW for various shallow crustal rupture scenarios in Europe and surrounding areas. Findings from this analysis represent a baseline at the start of TURNkey that will be used at the end of the project to judge its effectiveness in improving EEW for European applications.

EEW systems are a relatively recent innovation in earthquake-induced disaster risk reduction and resilience promotion (Allen and Melgar 2019). Their goal is to detect earthquakes in the early stages of fault rupture; to rapidly predict the source parameters (e.g., location and magnitude) and/or the intensity of the consequent ground motion; and to warn end users before they experience the strong shaking that might cause damage and losses.

EEW systems may be broadly categorised as “regional”, “on-site” (or “hybrid”). Figure 11 illustrates the principles of an EEW system (in its regional configuration). Regional EEW systems are presently operating in nine countries (including USA, Mexico, and Japan), and have been tested for application in a further 13 (Cremen and Galasso 2020).

We specifically focus on regional EEW systems in this deliverable.

Figure 11: Schematic of a regional EEW system.

These systems are based on a dense sensor network covering a geographical area of high seismicity. When an earthquake occurs, the relevant source parameters are estimated from the early portion of signals recorded at sensors close to the rupture. Location (and resulting site-to-source distance, R) is generally computed by accounting for geometrical constraints associated with both triggered and not-yet-triggered stations, and earthquake magnitude (M) is typically calculated based on empirical relationships relating the earthquake size to parameters obtained in the first 3-4 seconds of P- and (sometimes) S-wave signals. (For a more detailed review of various approaches to estimation of location and magnitude in regional EEW systems, interested readers are referred to Cremen and Galasso, 2020).

R and M estimates can be continuously updated (through Bayesian approaches or otherwise) by adding new station data, as the P-wave front propagates through the regional EEW network. The real-time values are then used to predict, with a quantified uncertainty, ground-motion intensity measures (IMs) at sites far away from the source (where target structures/infrastructure of interest are located), by using region-specific attenuation relationships, such as ground-motion model (GMMs). If probabilistic distributions of M and R are available, the prediction of different IMs (e.g., Convertito

et al. 2008; Iervolino et al. 2006) may be performed by analogy to the well-known Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment (PSHA) framework but in real-time, as discussed in detail in Iervolino et al. (2009). Regional EEW systems typically require the arrival of P-wave signals at a number of stations in order to provide stable early estimates of R, M, and IM. Thus, event detection is a fundamental task for EEW. Erroneously detected or inaccurate phases, along with poor event associations, lead to inaccurate location and magnitude estimates, and, ultimately, false or missed alerts.

Alert messages enable various stakeholders (e.g., individuals, communities, governments, businesses) located at a distance to take timely measures for reducing the likelihood of damage or loss before strong shaking reaches them (UNISDR 2009). Examples of important risk-mitigation actions that can be taken in the short warning time provided by EEW systems (typically seconds to minutes) include:

- (1) performing “ drop, cover and hold on” (DCHO; Porter 2016) or moving to a safer location (either within a building or outside) to avoid injuries;
- (2) slowing down high-speed trains to reduce accidents (Fabozzi et al. 2018);
- (3) shutting off gas pipelines to prevent fires (Gasparini et al. 2011), and
- (4) switching signals to stop vehicles from entering vulnerable infrastructure components (such as bridges) to avoid fatalities (Guenan et al. 2016).

This list accounts for merely a small number of the vast array of critical applications that may benefit from EEW (Velazquez et al. 2020).

It is worth noting that regional EEW algorithms generally assume a point-source model of the earthquake source and isotropic wave amplitude attenuation, which neglects the finite geometry of earthquake ruptures. These assumptions are generally suitable for estimating the final magnitude of events with $M < 6.5-7.0$ (Meier et al., 2020). However, they are often not adequate enough to represent the earthquake sources and wave amplitude attenuation effects of large earthquakes, which can introduce significant biases in real-time location and magnitude estimates of such events. Within this context, new developments have been proposed. These include the use of continuous GPS measurements and methodologies to determine displacement time series, and consequently recover slip estimates (through inversion) for more refined magnitude estimation (e.g., Colombelli et al., 2013; Grapenthin et al., 2014; Minson et al., 2014). Another option is the employment of image-recognition technologies to estimate fault rupture lengths, which can then be used to calculate magnitude via an empirical relationship (Böse et al., 2012). These advanced approaches, discussed in detail in Deliverable 3.1 part I, are outside the scope of this deliverables, since the magnitudes of the events considered in this study range from 5.5 to 6.9 and are consistent with the largest seismicity that is typically observed in Europe.

This chapter consists of two main sections, presenting:

1. a simulation-based exercise based on seismic hazard results (e.g., the FP7 SHARE seismic hazard model) to explore EEW feasibility across Europe in terms of probabilistic lead times and a newly defined EEW feasibility index proposed within TURNkey;

2. a simulation-based exercise based on both playbacks of real ground-motion data from historic seismic events and analysis of physics-based synthetic broadband seismograms obtained through advanced kinematic modelling of extended seismic sources to explore the performance of state-of-the-art regional EEW algorithms (as discussed in the deliverable 3.1. Part I) for different tectonic settings in Europe.

2.1 Mapping Earthquake Early Warning Feasibility across Europe

2.1.1 Introduction

This section investigates the feasibility of EEW application in the Euro-Mediterranean area, where there is a strong need to develop effective measures for mitigating seismic risk (Crowley et al. 2018); this is underlined by the fact that the average annual European GDP affected by earthquakes exceeds \$20 billion (World Bank 2017). In addition, the only European countries with current operational EEW systems are Romania (Mărmureanu et al. 2011) and Turkey (Alcik et al. 2009). In particular, we focus on EEW warning time (i.e., the time between the delivery of an EEW alert and the arrival of strong shaking at target sites). We compute probabilistic distributions of warning times available for various seismicity scenarios in high-hazard areas across the continent using a sophisticated travel-time algorithm incorporating wave propagation physics. We also explicitly quantify the risk-mitigation potential of these times for specific magnitude events, by establishing their spatial relationship with values of well-known proxy measures for both seismic vulnerability and exposure that are used in earthquake engineering.

A number of studies previously explored the feasibility or potential of EEW in different parts of the world, including France (Auclair et al. 2015), Italy (Picozzi et al. 2015(b); Picozzi et al. 2015(c); Emolo et al. 2016), Spain (Pazos et al. 2015), Portugal (Oliveira et al. 2015), Turkey (Oth et al. 2010), Japan (Meier et al. 2020), California (Minson et al. 2018; 2019), Hawaii (Thelen and Bodin 2016), the New Madrid Seismic Zone (Ogwenno et al. 2019), and Kyrgyzstan (Picozzi et al. 2013). This work significantly advances the state-of-the-art established by the aforementioned studies for a number of reasons. It examines EEW feasibility on a much larger (i.e., continental level) scale by combining EEW methods, models, and tools in a harmonised framework across Europe. Furthermore, we introduce a novel feasibility metric that enables identification of priority regions for further, more refined EEW feasibility analyses or actual investment in EEW systems for targeted end-users. This study, therefore, offers a unique transnational perspective on the potential of EEW that is highly relevant for intergovernmental stakeholders, such as the International Search and Rescue Advisory Group (INSARAG) of the United Nations (United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian 2015). It also provides valuable new insights on the possible benefits and limitations of EEW for regions (e.g., Iceland and Georgia) that have not recently experienced large earthquakes, but are likely to do so in the future.

2.1.2 Methods and results

2.1.2.1 European seismic station density

We conduct a preliminary feasibility study for EEW across the European region by considering the availability of its most fundamental component, i.e. seismic networks, on which the early seismic

signals could be detected and recorded for rapid event characterization. Seismic station locations are obtained using the IRIS Google map (GMAP) station mapping service (<http://ds.iris.edu/gmap/>). We consider all stations (both temporary and permanent arrays) between -26° and 45° longitude, and 34° and 72° latitude that were in operation until at least the start of 2020. Figure 12A displays a map of these stations (2,880 stations in total).

It can be seen from Figure 12B that approximately 55% of interstation distances (i.e., average distances to the closest three stations) are less than 20 km and almost all interstation distances are within 100 km.

Figure 12: Examining seismic station coverage across Europe. (A) Map of European seismic stations considered. (B) Distribution of interstation distances.

2.1.2.2 Lead-time mapping for high hazard areas

We focus on crustal point sources associated with large seismic hazard of engineering significance, which we define as those for which the event with a recurrence interval of 500 years is at least Mw 6.5 (see Figure 13A). We use the area source model of the 2013 European Seismic Hazard Model, which accounts for crustal seismicity with depth ≤ 40 km (Woessner et al. 2015; Giardini et al. 2014). To define seismic sources, we discretise the model into $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ cells. We specifically make use of the depth, maximum magnitude, style-of-faulting, and Gutenberg-Richter a , b parameters from the model. Each source is assumed to be characterised by all parameter values associated with the corresponding area source zone. We use the values associated with the highest weight in the logic tree where applicable, and average depth values for stable continental regions. The moment magnitude of the event with a recurrence interval of 500 years for a given source m satisfies the following equation:

$$\lambda_m - \lambda_{m_{max}} = 0.002 \quad (2-1)$$

where λ_m is the annual rate of earthquakes with magnitude greater than m , according to the Gutenberg-Richter magnitude-frequency relationship (Santis et al. 2011), and m_{max} is the modal maximum magnitude for the given source. We focus on the 37,869 sources for which $m \geq 6.5$. Predictions of PGA and peak ground velocity (PGV) associated with events with a recurrence

interval of 500 years are the median values computed using the epicentral distance version of the Akkar et al. (2014) ground motion model. The site amplification input to this model is the shear wave velocity in the uppermost 30 m, which is estimated at each target site from a topographic slope map (Wald and Allen 2007).

For each of these area sources, we calculate potential lead times (i.e., warning times that would be provided by EEW before shaking occurs) at target sites where the predicted peak ground acceleration (PGA) associated with the selected events exceeds 0.05 g (see Figure 2(B)), which is a commonly used threshold value for strong earthquake shaking in several engineering applications, including seismic design aimed at the life-safety performance (Bolt 1973; Vanmarcke and Lai 1980; Elghazouli 2016). Target sites are equivalent to all land-based seismic sources (i.e. those without a water layer at or above zero-elevation in the corresponding velocity profile), located within the same coordinate boundaries as the seismic stations. The lead-time (in seconds) for target site j due to an event at a given seismic source a is calculated as follows:

$$LT_j = TT_{a,j}^S - TT_{a,st3}^P - 4 \quad (2-2)$$

where $TT_{a,j}^S$ is the S-wave arrival time at j , and $TT_{a,st3}^P$ is the P-wave arrival time at the third closest station to the source. We account for the triggering of three stations, as it is the minimum required for many popular regional EEW algorithms to report reliable source parameter estimates (Allen et al. 2009; Satriano et al. 2011(a); Cua et al. 2009). A four-second interval is assumed to capture both data telemetry delays and the P-wave window required by an EEW algorithm to compute location and magnitude estimates, in line with previous studies (Picozzi et al. 2015(c)). We use the travel-time algorithm of the NonLinLoc software package (Lomax et al. 2000). This method calculates first arrival travel times for the nodes of a spatial grid using the Eikonal finite-difference scheme of Podvin and Lecomte (1991), which is an approximation of Huygen's principle (Wagner et al. 2013). We use a grid spacing of 10 km (5 km for the Italy benchmarking case study) in all directions. Both source-to-site and source-to-station travel times are calculated using 1-D velocity profiles from the CRUST 1.0 velocity model (Laske et al. 2013) at the location of the target site. Travel times are computed to zero-elevation at the target site.

Figure 14 displays histograms of lead times computed at selected target sites in three major cities covered by the study area, i.e., Rome, Istanbul, and Athens, due to the area sources that comply with the previously outlined criteria. It can be seen that the majority of lead times are positive for all three sites. The median lead times for the sites are 4.0 s (Rome), 6.5 s (Istanbul), and 5.8 s (Athens). The standard deviations of the times (in the same order) are 3.6 s, 5.7 s, and 5.0 s; these uncertainties are significant, reflecting the large variation in source-to-site distances for a given site.

Figure 13: Input data for lead-time mapping calculations. (A) Seismic sources (colour-coded in accordance with corresponding modal maximum magnitude values from the seismic hazard model). (B) Target sites examined.

Figure 14: Distributions of lead times for target sites in three major European cities. (A) Rome. (B) Istanbul. (C) Athens. Note that the red dashed lines indicate the corresponding median lead times and the solid black lines denote the positive lead-time threshold.

Figure 15 contains maps displaying the following three summary statistics for all affected target sites across the continent: (1) minimum lead time (i.e., “worst-case scenario”), (2) median lead time and (3) maximum lead time (i.e., “best-case scenario”). Note that negative lead times correspond to blind zones, where no warning is received before strong shaking occurs. Of all target sites examined, 7% have positive minimum lead times (<1% greater than 10 s, 2% between 5 and 10 s, and 5% less than 5 s); 46% have positive median lead times (2% greater than 10 seconds, 9% between 5 and 10 s, and 35% less than 5 s); and 91% have positive maximum lead times (44% greater than 10 s, 30% between 5 and 10 s, and 17% less than 5 s). The maximum lead time achieved across all target sites examined is 34.0 s (near Bafra, northern Turkey). Countries containing target sites with the longest overall lead times are Iceland, Greece and Turkey, which are characterized by some of the strongest seismicity in Europe and surrounding areas. On the other hand, countries containing target sites with the shortest overall lead times are Iraq, Georgia, and Russia. Table 5 provides a summary of potential risk-reducing actions that can be carried out for the various ranges of lead time investigated.

Figure 15: Lead-time mapping across all examined target sites. (A) Minimum lead times. (B) Median lead times. (C) Maximum lead times.

Table 5: EEW risk mitigation. Possible risk-mitigation actions that can be taken by various stakeholders for different lengths of EEW lead time. Adapted from previous work (Goltz 2002; Iervolino et al. 2007; Iervolino 2011; Porter 2016; Oliveira et al. 2015).

Lead-Time Range (s)	Possible Actions
0-5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> stopping traffic (i.e., turning lights red); switching on semi-active control systems for structures.
5-10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> performing DCHO; stopping elevators at the nearest floor and opening doors; shutting off gas supplies; shutting down computers and related equipment; evacuating the ground floor of buildings.
> 10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> shutting down industrial equipment;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • controlling production lines; • directing traffic away from underpasses; • stopping surgical procedures; • removing vehicles from garages.
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2.1.2.2.1 Benchmarking the calculations

The lead-time maps presented in Figure 2.4 are computed using a complex travel-time algorithm explicitly accounting for the physics of seismic wave propagation (Podvin and Lecomte 1991; see section 2.1.2.2). Many previous studies of EEW lead time and blind zone extent (Kuyuk and Allen 2013; Iervolino 2011; Stankiewicz et al. 2013; Pazos et al. 2015; Ogwen et al. 2019; Picozzi et al. 2015(b)) have adopted far more simplified approaches to the calculation of travel time, which only consider the arrival of direct P-waves (i.e., do not fully incorporate wave-motion physics) and may also only account for average values of wave velocities. We now benchmark the lead-time maps of Figure 15 (i.e., the “original case”) against those obtained using a simplistic travel time calculation, which is similar to the methods adopted in the aforementioned literature, i.e.:

$$TT_{x,y} = \frac{d_{hypo_{x,y}}}{v_{avg}} \quad (2-3)$$

where $TT_{x,y}$ is the travel time from the source (x) to the target site or station of interest (y), $d_{hypo_{x,y}}$ is the hypocentral distance between x and y , and v_{avg} is the average P- or S-wave velocity across the CRUST 1.0 velocity model profile at the location of the target site. Travel times are computed to zero-elevation at the target site.

The results of this benchmarking exercise are plotted in Figure 18. The greatest discrepancies between the maps developed using the two travel-time models tend to occur for the largest absolute values of lead time in the original case. In general, the simplistic model results in higher lead times at target sites where the lead time is positive for the original case, and it results in lower lead times at sites where the original lead time is negative. 5% of minimum lead times, 16% of median lead times, and 64% of maximum lead times are over-estimated by at least one second when the simplified travel-time model is used, whereas 13% of minimum lead times, 8% of median lead times, and 4% of maximum lead times are underestimated by at least the same amount.

Secondly, we verify the adequacy of the resolution chosen for the lead-time map by benchmarking the resulting times for Italy with those obtained using a finer seismic source and target site grid spacing. For this investigation, the area source zones are instead discretised into $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$ cells, which is equivalent to the resolution used in Italy’s official seismic hazard map (Stucchi et al. 2004). Assignments and calculations of seismic parameter values and ground shaking intensity predictions are as described for the European-wide seismic sources. This results in a total of 4804 sources that satisfy the Mw 6.5 threshold for the events with a recurrence interval of 500 years and result in a PGA greater than 0.05 g for at least one target site of interest. Target sites in this case are defined as

all land-based seismic sources that are categorised under 'Italy' in the 'Countries WGS84' shapefile, retrieved from the ArcGIS Hub (<https://hub.arcgis.com/search>). From a visual comparison of Figure 15 and Figure 16, it can be concluded that there are no notable differences in the lead times obtained at both resolutions. Therefore, the grid spacing of the European-wide map is deemed adequate.

Figure 16: High-resolution lead-time maps of Italy. (A) Minimum lead times. (B) Median lead times. (C) Maximum lead times. (A)-(C) are to be compared with the corresponding times mapped in Figure 15.

2.1.2.3 Risk quantification

We examine the risk-mitigation potential of the calculated lead times by defining their spatial relationship with ambient (average day and night) population distributions and the average seismic intensity across all events with a recurrence interval of 500 years that produce a PGA greater than or equal to 0.05 g at the affected site. Seismic intensities are calculated from the bilinear equations for EMS-98 macroseismic intensity developed by Masi et al. (2020) using the PGV predictions discussed in section 2.1.2.2. Population data are obtained from the 2018 LandScan database (Rose et al. 2019), which contains global ambient population distributions at a 30" × 30" spatial resolution. Each target site is assigned the aggregated population across all LandScan grid points closest to it.

The population is an important consideration in seismic risk assessment (Tenerelli et al. 2015) that often acts as a proxy for the exposure (i.e., the value at risk) of the built environment and assets in earthquake engineering and risk modelling applications (Ceferino et al. 2018). Seismic intensity, which describes the effect of the earthquake ground shaking on the built environment and communities, is a well-established proxy for both damage (Wald et al. 1999) and vulnerability (Grunthal 1998). We use the EMS-98 seismic intensity scale (Grunthal 1998), which is specifically designed for European countries.

98% of the total ambient population surrounding the examined target sites are affected by average EMS-98 values between V ("strong," e.g., top-heavy objects topple over) and VII ("damaging" e.g., many objects fall from shelves, and there is partly damage to walls). Figure 17(A) indicates that approximately 38% of the ambient population are affected by EMS-98 values between V and VI ("slightly damaging" e.g., objects fall from walls, and there is partly damage to plaster), while approximately 60% are affected by values between VI and VII (Figure 17 (B)). 38% of the ambient population affected by average intensities between V and VI have maximum lead times greater than 10 seconds, while 10% have negative maximum lead times (i.e., they are located in the "blind zone"). 59% of the population affected by these intensities have positive median lead times, and 18% have positive minimum lead times. 65% of the ambient population affected by average intensities between VI and VII have maximum lead times greater than 10 seconds, while 4% are located in the "blind zone". 56% of the population affected by these intensities have positive median lead times, and 1% have positive minimum lead times.

Figure 17: Risk modelling results. (A)-(B) Average EMS-98 macroseismic intensities experienced by the affected ambient population during events with a recurrence interval of 500 years that result in a PGA greater than 0.05 g at the associated target site, categorized by the corresponding lead times of the maps presented in Figure 14. Note that seismic intensities V, VI, and VII denote “strong”, “slightly damaging”, and “damaging” events, respectively. Relative Feasibility Mapping for (C) the case in which lead time, intensity, and population are equally weighted by a

stakeholder, as well as the cases in which (D) lead time, (E) seismic intensity, and (F) population are respectively weighted three times more than the other variables.

2.1.2.3.1 EEW feasibility calculation

For a given target site j , we combine estimates of median lead time (L), average seismic intensity (I), and affected ambient population (P) into a single, novel metric of EEW feasibility, termed the EEW Relative Feasibility Index (RF_j), defined as follows:

$$RF_j = F_L(l_j) * w_L + F_I(i_j) * w_I + F_P(p_j) * w_P \quad (2-4)$$

where $F_X(x_i)$ is the empirical cumulative distribution function of X (across all examined target sites with a positive median lead time) evaluated at i , and w_X is the stakeholder-assigned weight for X (note that $w_P + w_I + w_L = 1$). Higher values of this index correspond to key characteristics that maximise the effectiveness of an EEW system (Kuyuk and Allen 2013), i.e.: (1) longer lead times; (2) higher potential for shaking causing losses that can be avoided with EEW; and (3) larger affected populations. They, therefore, indicate greater EEW feasibility for a given target site.

It can be seen from Eq. 2-4 that the index accommodates a user-defined weight for each measurement to account for stakeholder preferences and priorities. Figure 17(D)-(F) include EEW Relative Feasibility Index mapping of all target sites with positive median lead time for the equally-weighted case (i.e., $w_P = w_I = w_L = 0.333$) and for cases where one variable (e.g., lead time) is weighted three times more than the other two (e.g., $w_L = 0.6$, and $w_P = w_I = 0.2$). Also highlighted in each subplot are the fifty target sites with the largest index values for the corresponding case.

For all cases, the countries containing sites with the largest feasibility indices are Italy, Greece, and Turkey. However, both the locations and the number of sites per country differ between cases. Relative to the equally weighted case, target sites with the largest increase and decrease in feasibility index for the case where lead time is the highest weighted variable are located in Iceland and Turkey, respectively; target sites with the largest increase and decrease in this value for the case where seismic intensity is the highest weighted variable are located in Turkey and Georgia, respectively, and target sites with the largest increase and decrease in feasibility index for the case where the population is the highest weighted variable are both located in Turkey.

2.1.3 Discussion

This study has examined the feasibility of EEW for Europe and surrounding area. Our initial analysis examined the density of seismic station coverage across the continent. We found that over half (i.e., approximately 55%) of interstation distances are between 0 and 20 km, which corresponds to the distance range recommended for optimum EEW performance in previous work (Kuyuk and Allen 2013). These findings are a preliminary signal that there is significant potential for operational EEW across the continent.

Our detailed feasibility analysis focused on Euro-Mediterranean regions affected by significant seismic hazard. Probabilistic distributions of EEW lead (warning) times were determined for target sites in these areas by randomly varying the location of seismic sources in line with regional seismicity. Summary statistics of these times were then translated into maps, which give additional

promising indications of the potential usefulness of EEW in Europe. For example, in a “best-case scenario”, they show that almost half (i.e., 44%) of the examined target sites benefit from warning times that are sufficiently long to accommodate major risk intervention actions, such as the shutting down of industrial equipment or the removal of vehicles from garages. 11% of all examined target sites have a 50% chance of receiving an EEW alert that allows time for people to “drop, cover and hold on”, shut off gas supplies, or evacuate ground floors in buildings. Even in a “worst-case scenario”, more than 5% of target sites have sufficient warning time for the switching on of semi-active control systems in structures (Maddaloni et al. 2011), which could significantly reduce structural vulnerability and resulting damage or loss. We found that the longest overall lead times occur at sites in Iceland, Greece, and Turkey. Areas associated with the shortest overall lead times, where therefore the feasibility of EEW could be particularly improved through increased seismic station density, are northern Iraq, north-western Georgia, and southern Russia.

The lead times were computed using a sophisticated travel-time model accounting for wave-motion physics. Our subsequent benchmarking study compared the summary maps with lead times computed using a notably more simplistic travel-time method, which does not accurately consider wave propagation; similar versions of this method are frequently used in the literature for assessing EEW feasibility. We found that positive lead times calculated using the simplistic travel-time method tend to be overestimated, which may result in unconservative and therefore, sub-optimal decision-making by a stakeholder. Additional benchmarking studies that used higher resolution maps of Italian-specific lead times confirmed the adequate accuracy of the European-wide maps.

We further contextualised the significance of the lead times by combining them with spatial distributions of two risk proxies often used in earthquake engineering (i.e., population and seismic intensity). We found that almost all (i.e., approximately 98%) of the affected ambient population are exposed to average seismic intensities from nearby seismic sources that at least result in falling objects. Over 50% of these people have more than 10 seconds of warning time in a “best-case scenario”, which enables them to carry out the major risk intervention actions mentioned in the previous paragraph. A significant proportion (> 55%) have positive warning times from events at 50% of relevant sources, while approximately 8% have some warning time in a “worst-case scenario”.

Finally, we translated the aforementioned features (i.e., lead time, average seismic intensity from nearby sources and ambient population affected) into a novel indicator for measuring relative EEW feasibility at a given target site that also accounts for stakeholder-specific preferences. A corresponding feasibility map was developed for the case in which the features were equally weighted, as well as cases where each feature was weighed three times more than the other two. While there was some variation in the results obtained across the three cases, all maps indicated that Turkey, Italy, and Greece contain the target sites with the highest EEW feasibility. The findings for Turkey suggest that an expansion or enhancement of its Istanbul-focused EEW efforts could be highly beneficial for mitigating seismic risk in many regions throughout the country. The results are particularly notable for Italy and Greece, since neither currently has a operational EEW system. In summary, we ultimately conclude that this work provides strong evidence to suggest that EEW could be an effective tool for supporting earthquake-related disaster risk reduction across a significant proportion of Europe and surrounding areas. TURNkey aims to address this issue by developing a holistic earthquake information system that incorporates state-of-the-art seismic risk mitigation tools

for both operational earthquake forecasting and EEW in real- and near-real-time, with selected testbeds in Italy and Greece (as well as Iceland) to be the focus of more detailed analyses for EEW and the target of end-user-orientated applications of the system.

It is important to note that there are some limitations and simplifying assumptions associated with this work. Firstly, it is assumed that the seismic stations currently installed across the Euro-Mediterranean area (both permanent and temporary) are capable of being used for early warning purposes (e.g. they have adequate data acquisition and transmission systems, real-time communication capability, robust dissemination methods and power supply systems; Auclair et al. 2015; Thelen et al. 2016), which may be an over-simplification (Allen and Melgar 2019). We did not explicitly consider the performance of existing EEW algorithms in the lead-time calculations. Instead, we simply assumed that 4 seconds was sufficient to capture both data telemetry delays and the length of time required by the algorithms to estimate relevant source parameters (see section 2.1.2.2); a slightly longer time (~5 seconds) may be required for certain algorithms and transmission features (Allen 2007; Behr et al. 2015). Our detailed EEW feasibility analysis only accounted for crustal seismic sources, thereby yielding conservative lead times for target sites that would additionally be affected by the deeper seismicity of subduction zones in the Central and Eastern Mediterranean Sea. It therefore also neglected the seismicity of the Vrancea region in Romania (Ismail-Zadeh et al. 2012), which has significantly associated hazard (Sokolov et al. 2009); examination of this region is not crucial in the context of our study, however, given that it already has an operational EEW system (Ionescu et al. 2007; Mărmureanu et al. 2011). To maintain a consistent approach for the entire examined region, the considered seismicity scenarios were defined using an area source model (see section 2.1.2.2), which assumes a uniform occurrence of earthquakes as point sources; thus, the resulting calculations of the hazard near faults (corresponding to large seismogenic sources) may not be completely realistic (Valentini et al. 2017). Finally, we did not consider the economic value of EEW, i.e., the costs required to build and maintain EEW systems compared to the monetary savings they provide through avoided damage (Klafft 2011). Despite these constraints, this study nevertheless represents an innovative attempt to comprehensively quantify EEW feasibility on a continental scale and to identify priority regions for more detailed EEW feasibility analyses and investment in EEW implementation.

Figure 18: Differences obtained in lead-time maps, using the simplified travel time model. (A) Differences in minimum lead times. (B) Differences in median lead times. (C) Differences in maximum lead times. Red colours indicate larger and blue colours indicate shorter lead times for the simplified case.

2.2 Exploring the performance of regional EEW algorithms in Europe

2.2.1 Introduction

Methodologies for regional EEW will be implemented within the TURNkey FWCR, which will rely on SeisComp3 (SC3, <https://www.seiscomp3.org/>), a freely available standard real-time earthquake monitoring platform developed by the GEOFON Program at Helmholtz Centre Potsdam, GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, and Gempa GmbH. SC3 has become a popular tool among seismic network operators in Europe and worldwide (Hanka et al. 2010). It is a comprehensive software framework, which includes algorithms for waveform acquisition (SeedLink), automated earthquake detection, source location and characterization, manual event relocation, event alerting and waveform archiving and dissemination. SC3 follows a modular approach in which every module is a standalone program communicating with other modules through a Control Protocol/Internet Protocol (TCP/IP) messaging system and connecting to a common database containing, among other

information, the station metadata. Due to its modular structure, it also allows to easily incorporate different EEW algorithms, for instance methods devoted to the estimation of earthquake location and its magnitude.

Due to the short available lead times for most target sites in Europe (section 2.1), it is essential to compute rapid and accurate EEW estimates of earthquake location and magnitude, as discussed above. Therefore, this section aims at evaluating the performance of alternative EEW algorithms, particularly in terms of location and magnitude estimation, considering representative European conditions of seismicity and existing station density. The impact of these algorithms on the final ground-motion IM estimation – through GMMs – is also investigated. The overall aim is to identify the best-performing EEW algorithms for location and magnitude estimation to be integrated into SC3 and finally included in the TURNkey platform.

We consider five European geographic areas – Southern Italy, Pyrenees, Iceland, Greece and Romania – representative of different hazard levels and seismotectonic settings: a collisional subduction complex with a complicated back-arc, fore-arc and trench system (Southern Italy), a continent-continent collision with the evolution of an orogenic belt (Pyrenees), mid-ocean ridges (Iceland), interface subduction zones (Greece) and intermediate-depth subcrustal seismicity (Romania).

2.2.2 EEW algorithms and methodology for comparison

We investigated the performance of three well-known EEW algorithms, namely PRESTo (Lancieri and Zollo 2008; Satriano et al. 2011(a); Satriano et al. 2008), ElarmS (Brown et al. 2011; Allen et al. 2009), and Virtual Seismologist (Cua, 2005; Cua et al., 2009; Cua and Heaton, 2007). These algorithms are designed for estimating magnitude, location, and ground shaking within regional EEW systems, which consist of seismic stations networks installed within the expected epicentral (or high seismicity) area.

PRESTo is a free and open-source software platform for EEW (<http://www.prestoews.org/about.php>). The system, designed by the RISSC Lab at the University of Naples, is currently operating in real-time in Southern Italy, Turkey, Romania, and South Korea. It has also been tested for application in Austria and Slovenia (Picozzi et al., 2015), as well as on the Iberian Peninsula (Pazos et al., 2015). PRESTo produces hypocentral location estimates in the form of a multivariate normal probability density function (PDF), using the *RTL*oc method developed by Satriano et al. (2008). A Bayesian framework is used for predicting magnitude according to the RTMag procedure proposed by Lancieri and Zollo (2008), in which the likelihood function depends on initial characteristics of the P-wave at triggered stations as well as location estimates. The prior PDF is the posterior distribution obtained at the previous time step, and the first prior is optionally set as the Gutenberg-Richter distribution. Peak ground-motion parameters are computed based on the location and magnitude estimates using a GMM.

ElarmS is an EEW algorithm developed by the Berkeley Seismology Lab at the University of California, Berkeley, for application in California, and is currently included in the California Integrated Seismic Network ShakeAlert® EEW system (<http://www.cisn.org/eew/>). It is also used

for EEW in Korea (Allen and Melgar 2019) and has been tested for implementation in Israel (Nof and Allen, 2016) and Chile (Allen and Melgar, 2019). This algorithm estimates locations through a grid search routine, which minimizes the residuals between observed seismic phases and those predicted from a velocity model. Magnitude is estimated from initial characteristics of P-waves, using an empirical scaling relationship. Ground motion predictions are obtained based on the source parameter estimates and ShakeMap (Wald et al. 1999b) ground shaking prediction tools.

Virtual Seismologist (VS) is an alternative EEW algorithm initially developed at Caltech for California. It was originally part of the ShakeAlert® EEW system, but the slow operational performance of the algorithm resulted in its removal in 2016 (Chung and Allen 2019). VS operates within a Bayesian framework, in which magnitude and location are jointly conditioned on the available set of ground motion amplitudes, and the prior PDF incorporates an existing state of knowledge on relative earthquake probability. The magnitude and location estimates are subsequently translated to peak ground shaking predictions using envelope attenuation relationships.

We also evaluated VS(SC3), which is the VS magnitude likelihood component integrated within the SC3 system (Behr et al., 2016). VS(SC3) uses the locations from SC3, available picks and envelope data. It is currently operational in Switzerland (Behr et al., 2016) and has been tested for use in Nicaragua (Massin et al. 2017). SC3 location estimates are typically performed using the standard module *scautoloc*; however, this algorithm aims to robustness rather than speed and requires at least 6 P-wave detections to estimate a location. We instead used the *scanloc* algorithm (Roessler et al. 2016) for this study, which is capable of producing fast location estimates with very few P-wave detections. *scanloc* makes use of a cluster search algorithm to associate phase detections to potential earthquakes. The cluster search itself is based on P phases only; in a second step, S phases are also associated and used for locating the earthquake.

The study presented in this section focuses on algorithmic performance in terms of magnitude and location estimation accuracy. However, we also investigate the impact of precision in these parameter estimates on the quality of ground shaking predictions. These are important for decision-making on the triggering of EEW alerts using a common GMM for Europe. The performance was quantitatively assessed using a two-step approach. The first step investigated the operational performance of the PRESTo and SC3 platforms, using off-line playbacks of seismic waveforms recorded or simulated across a wide variety of seismic network configurations (i.e., geometries and densities) stemming from a range of different European seismotectonic environments. The prior distribution for the PRESTo magnitude calculation was not considered at this stage in order to be consistent with the format of the VS(SC3) magnitude algorithm. This initial assessment was useful for comparing the two platforms in real-time simulation mode, accounting for the continuous streaming of data to the systems and their effective processing times. It is important to note that the accuracy of the computed location and magnitude estimations is directly affected by the performance of each platform's event detection algorithm (i.e. phase picking and seismic phase association methodology). The event detection algorithms were therefore optimized consistently for each region of interest through an ad-hoc tuning of the relevant parameters. However, discrepancies in phase picking and event association may still persist due to the different parameters and algorithms used in both platforms. To eliminate this inconsistency, the second step of the study focused on theoretical separate (isolated) evaluations for both location and magnitude computations, using identical phase picking and event association

procedures as well as input data for all algorithms (i.e. the same P-wave arrivals for location and the same origins for magnitude evaluation, respectively). To facilitate these calculations, we coded the complete location and magnitude modules of the PRESTo, and VS (original version) algorithms, along with ElarmS, in MATLAB, including any relevant Bayesian priors and other probabilistic details. This setup provided maximum flexibility to produce rigorous statistical comparisons that properly account for uncertainty propagation through the EEW process at the expense of preventing real-time operational constraints, such as data processing times, from being considered. Table 6 summarizes the algorithms used to estimate the location and magnitude in this study.

Table 6: Summary of the location and magnitude algorithms evaluated in this study.

Component	Algorithm			
	PRESTo	ElarmS	VS	SC3
Location	<i>RTL</i> oc (Satriano et al. 2008)	(Brown et al. 2011)	(Cua and Heaton 2007)	<i>scanloc</i> (Roessler et al. 2016))
Magnitude	<i>RTMag</i> (Lancieri and Zollo 2008)	(Wurman et al. 2007)	(Cua and Heaton 2007)	VS(SC3) (Behr et al. 2016)

2.2.3 Data

2.2.3.1 Velocity models

We used regional velocity models found in the literature for both location estimation and the computation of synthetic seismograms. They are listed in Table 6. Where not explicitly defined, P-wave velocities were converted into S-wave velocities (and vice-versa) using the Poisson solid's approximation. Densities were converted from P-wave velocities using the Nafe-Drake relationship (Ludwig 1970). Concerning the quality factors, necessary for the computation of synthetic seismograms, they were set to $Q_s=100 \times V_s$ (V_s in km/s) and $Q_p=9/4 \times Q_s$ (Lay and Wallace 1995).

We computed 3D travel-time grids for both P and S waves at all stations using the NonLinLoc software (Lomax et al. 2000). They were used to locate earthquakes by a grid search in the Matlab-based EEW algorithm implementations and in the PRESTo platform. For SC3, travel-time tables for the LocSAT locator were prepared by appending the IASP91 model (Kennett and Engdahl 1991) at the base of the velocity models of Table 7 in order to extend them at greater depths.

Table 7: Regional velocity models used in this study.

Region	Velocity model
Southern Italy	Barberi et al. (2004)
Pyrenees	Theunissen et al. (2108)
Iceland	Tryggvason et al. (2002)
Greece	Rigo et al. (1996)
Romania	Raykova and Panza (2006) – Vrancea cell

2.2.3.2 Seismic waveforms and EEW parameters for the MATLAB implementation of the considered algorithms

We use both observed (i.e., recorded during past events) and physics-based synthetic seismograms. Specifically, we consider real recordings for Iceland, Romania and Greece, while synthetic seismograms were computed for southern Italy and the Pyrenees to address the lack of recordings from moderate-to-large events in these regions. The use of seismograms from different regions enables the evaluation of the performance of the considered EEW algorithms for a wide range of focal mechanisms, magnitudes and hypocentral depths. It also allows us to consider seismic networks with different densities and configurations with respect to the main seismicity of the region.

We identified observed recordings by selecting earthquakes with magnitude greater than 5.5 that occurred in the last 20 years, recorded by at least eight recording stations. Recordings for Greece and Romania were retrieved from the European Integrated waveform Data Archive (EIDA, <https://www.orfeus-eu.org/data/eida/>) through the ORFEUS Data Centre WebDC3 Web Interface (<http://orfeus-eu.org/webdc3/>). Both broadband and strong-motion sensors were considered. In case of stations equipped with more than one sensor, only one sensor was used, giving preference to the strong-motion one. Strong-motion recordings from Iceland were obtained from the Internet Site for European Strong-motion Data (ISESD, <http://www.isesd.hi.is/>).

We computed synthetic seismograms from physics-based numerical simulations using the broadband ground-motion simulation code described in Crempien and Archuleta (2015), which is able to properly simulate the high-frequency content of seismic waves and proved to be suitable for EEW feasibility studies (Zuccolo et al. 2016). In order to generate synthetic seismograms for Southern Italy and the Pyrenees, one scenario earthquake was defined for each active fault located in those regions. Faults parameters were retrieved from the European Database of Seismogenic Faults (ESDF; Basili et al. 2013). The magnitude of each scenario earthquake was randomly determined by assuming a uniform distribution between 5.5 and the maximum magnitude associated to the fault; the hypocentre was located at a depth equal to 2/3 of the seismogenic layer, while the focal mechanism was defined using average strike, dip and rake values. Rupture fault dimensions were estimated from the Wells and Coppersmith (1994) relationships, while the position of the hypocentre on the fault plane was established using the distributions by Causse et al. (2008). The average rupture velocity was determined assuming a uniform distribution between 65% and 85% of the shear wave velocity on the fault plane. The corner frequency was estimated from the stress drop (Allmann and Shearer 2009) assuming a stress drop equal to 3 MPa (Caporali et al. 2011) for both regions. Synthetic seismograms were computed at the location of the currently operating permanent stations retrieved from the IRIS database (<https://ds.iris.edu/gmap>) up to a maximum epicentral distance of 100 km. Finally, white noise was added to the computed seismograms in order for the STA/LTA picking algorithm included in SC3 to function properly.

In total, 27 events were considered. Their locations are illustrated in Figure 19, while their main features are listed in Table 8.

Figure 19: Locations of the earthquakes (red circles) and target sites (green squares) considered in this study. Blue triangles represent the considered seismic stations.

Table 8: Magnitude, longitude, latitude, depth and focal mechanism of the events considered in this study. The origin time and the EDSF fault ID is also provided for real and scenario earthquakes, respectively.

Region	Fault ID	Origin time	Mw	Lon (°)	Lat (°)	Depth (km)
Southern Italy	ITCS042	Simulated	5.6	15.03	38.35	17.0
	ITCS016	Simulated	6.9	15.60	38.03	9.3
	ITCS053	Simulated	6.2	16.19	38.63	8.3
	ITCS055	Simulated	5.9	15.91	38.23	9.0
	ITCS068	Simulated	6.4	16.49	38.87	11.0
	ITCS080	Simulated	5.6	16.18	38.42	9.0
	ITCS082	Simulated	6.3	16.02	38.37	8.3
Pyrenees	ESCS071	Simulated	5.6	2.47	42.10	6.8
	ESCS112	Simulated	6.0	3.26	42.04	6.8
	FRCS007	Simulated	6.2	2.07	42.48	10.3
	ESCS126	Simulated	5.7	0.64	42.64	6.3
	FRCS002	Simulated	6.0	2.77	42.51	10.3
	ESCS125	Simulated	6.5	0.89	42.67	6.7
Iceland ⁽¹⁾		1998-06-04T21:36:53	5.5	-21.29	64.04	5.9
		2000-06-17T15:40:41	6.4	-20.37	63.97	6.4
		2000-06-17T15:42:50	5.7	-20.45	63.95	5.4
		2000-06-21T00:51:47	6.5	-20.71	63.97	5.0
		2008-05-29T15:45:58	6.3	-21.07	63.97	5.1
Greece ⁽²⁾		2014-01-26T13:55:43.0	6.0	20.53	38.22	16.4
		2014-02-03T03:08:44	5.9	20.40	38.25	11.3
		2015-11-17T07:10:07	6.4	20.60	38.67	10.7
		2018-10-25T22:54:49	6.7	20.51	37.34	9.9
		2018-10-30T15:12:02	5.8	20.45	37.46	5.5
Romania ⁽³⁾		2014-11-22T19:14:17.2	5.6	27.16	45.87	39.0
		2016-09-23T23:11:20.2	5.7	26.62	45.71	92.0
		2016-12-27T23:20:56.3	5.6	26.61	45.72	91.0

		2018-10-28T00:38:10.8	5.5	26.40	45.60	151.0
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- (1) Event parameters retrieved from a catalogue assembled and revised by Panzera et al. (2016).
- (2) Event parameters retrieved from <https://bbnet.gein.noa.gr/HL/>
- (3) Event parameters retrieved from <https://www.emsc-csem.org/>

Seismic waveforms are directly used as input into SC3 and PRESTo platforms for the first step of the analysis. For the second step, it was necessary to extract the relevant information for the estimation of magnitude and distance, respectively.

Table 9: Data used as input for the evaluation of magnitude and distance performance.

Component	Algorithm			
	PRESTo	ElarmS	VS	<i>scanloc</i>
Location	P-wave arrival times, velocity model	P-wave arrival times, velocity model	P-wave arrival times, velocity model	P- and S-wave arrival times, velocity model
Magnitude	origins, Pd(2P), Pd(4P), Pd(2S), location from SC3	origins, Pd	origins, ZA, ZV, ZD, HA, HV, HD	

Locations were computed using arrivals retrieved from the off-line playbacks executed with SC3. Specifically, only the picks associated with the preferred origin were used as input to the MATLAB codes and to the *scanloc* module. For each seismic event, the preferred origin is one of the origins computed by SC3, automatically selected as preferred based on predefined criteria (e.g. number of picks and RMS).

Magnitudes were estimated using the *scanloc* origins computed with the set of P-wave arrivals associated with the preferred origin. Waveforms were preliminarily processed in order to extract the EEW parameters to be used as input to the magnitude estimation algorithm (MATLAB code). The following approach was used: 1. resampling to 100 Hz to be consistent with the ElarmS computation of the predominant period; 2. gain correction; 3. baseline correction; 4. derivation of velocigrams to obtain accelerograms; 5. band-pass filter (0.075–3 Hz) applied to accelerograms for PRESTo and ElarmS (Satriano et al. 2011(a); Allen and Kanamori 2003) and a high-pass filter with a corner frequency of 3 s for VS; and 6. integration and double integration to obtain velocities and displacement time histories, respectively.

For each station, we computed the following parameters:

- peak displacement (Pd) for three different time windows for PRESTo, considering the vector modulus of the three-component seismogram in that time window proposed by Satriano et al. 2011(a): 2 s following the P-wave arrival (if the P and S arrivals are more than 2 s apart), 4 s following the P-wave arrival (if the P- and S arrivals are more than 4 s apart), 2 s following the S-wave arrival. At each instant, the theoretical S-wave arrival time is determined using the P-wave arrival time and the theoretical travel times are computed according to the continuously updated origins;
- peak displacement (Pd) measured on the vertical component velocity waveforms, computed at 0.1 s intervals across a 4 s-window starting 0.5 s after the P-wave arrival time (Allen et al. 2009);
- maximum envelope values of vertical acceleration (ZA), velocity (ZV), displacement (ZD) and root mean square horizontal acceleration (HA), velocity (HV) and displacement (HV) computed within 1 s intervals starting from the P-wave arrival time.

2.2.3.3 Ground-motion models

We computed Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) values by using the GMM by Akkar et al. (2014) for all earthquakes with hypocentral depth < 40 km and the model by Youngs et al. (1997) for the intermediate-depth Vrancea earthquakes (Vacareanu et al. 2013). We estimated PGA values assuming representative rock ground conditions at the following target sites: port of Gioia Tauro for Southern Italy, Andorra for the Pyrenees, Reykjavík for Iceland, Patras for Greece and Bucharest for Romania.

2.2.3.4 Bayesian priors for the MATLAB implementation of the considered algorithms

The maximum magnitude and scaling (b) parameters of the Gutenberg-Richter distribution required for the definition of the Bayesian prior distribution in PRESTo were retrieved for each event from the nearest point on a 0.1 degree by 0.1-degree grid of the European Seismic Hazard Model (ESHM13; Woessner et al. 2015). The minimum magnitude of 4 was assumed for all cases. We used the same distribution for the magnitude prior for the VS algorithm. The parameterisation of the location prior for the VS algorithm depends on both the number of stations triggered at a given time as well as spatial constraints provided by data associated with not-yet arrived P waves (Cua and Heaton 2007). If only one station triggered, the location was constrained to the area of the associated Voronoi cell that was geometrically consistent with the surrounding non-triggered stations. For two triggers, the location was assumed to be situated on the hyperbola passing between both stations, in line with the methodology described by Rydelek and Pujol (2004). For three triggers, the location was constrained to one point, i.e. the intersection of the hyperbolae that pass between all stations. All possible locations included in the prior were assigned equal weighting (i.e., a uniform distribution), and every other grid-point was assigned zero probability. The P-wave velocity used for computing location constraints was taken as the average value within a 10 km depth, according to the appropriate velocity model provided in Table 7.

2.2.4 Performance assessment

2.2.4.1 Comparison between the SC3 and PRESTo platforms

We ran offline playbacks of the seismic waveforms associated with the 27 events shown in Figure 19 in both SC3 (with VS(SC3) and *scanloc* module) and PRESTo in order to evaluate the performance of the two platforms. Figure 19 demonstrates the performance of both platforms for two sample earthquakes. The timeline plots represent the full temporal evolution of the magnitude and location estimates. They allow assessing how quickly the system can produce the first estimate, the time necessary to get stable estimates and how accurate the estimates are at each update.

Figure 20: Evolution in time (starting from the origin time) of the estimates by SC3 (grey dots) and PRESTo (black dots) for two earthquakes: (left) scenario event with fault ID ITCS080 in Southern Italy; (right) the 2016-09-23 event in Romania. Top: magnitude timeline; middle: epicentral error timeline; bottom: depth timeline. The target (real) values are represented by grey horizontal lines.

We chose two different temporal instants to quantify and compare the performance of the two systems:

- a) time of the first estimate, which is the time necessary to compute the first joint estimate of location and magnitude (i.e. the earliest dot in the plot);
- b) time of stable estimate, which is the time required before the EEW estimate ceases to change significantly, i.e. the estimated value remains within a prefixed difference threshold from its final value. Different stable estimate times were defined with respect to the magnitude, epicentre and depth estimate. The difference thresholds were fixed at 0.2 units for magnitude, 5 km for epicentral distance if the final estimated depth is less than 30 km and 10 km for larger depths, as well as 5 km for depth.

The comparison has been assessed in terms of both timeliness and accuracy of the estimated magnitudes and locations. Finally, the effect of the magnitude and distance interdependency on the computed ground motion has been explored.

2.2.4.1.1 Timeliness

The comparison in terms of timeliness is provided in Figure 20. Concerning the time of the first estimate, our analysis shows that the first EEW estimate is provided slightly faster by PRESTo. This is partially related to the fact that VS is capable of estimating magnitude with 3 s of P-wave information at a single station, while PRESTo's magnitude module needs only two seconds of P-waves signal. Concerning the speed in getting stable estimates, SC3 locations converge to the final values faster than those by PRESTo; in contrast, VS(SC3) magnitude estimates require a long time to become stable, thus confirming the observation by Chung and Allen (2019).

Figure 21: Comparison between SC3 and PRESTo platforms in terms of timeliness. avgRatio is the average ratio between PRESTo and SC3 time estimates.

2.2.4.1.2 Accuracy

We assess the accuracy of the estimates (magnitude, epicentre location and depth) provided by the two platforms by computing their difference with respect to the true values (listed in Table 8). The comparison in terms of accuracy is given in Figure 21.

Concerning magnitude, the first estimate is generally underestimated with respect to the true value because it is constrained by only a few stations. The underestimation is larger for VS(SC3) than for PRESTo, whose mean and median magnitude estimate is within 0.5 units of the true value. However, magnitude estimates by PRESTo are characterized by a larger standard deviation with respect to those estimated by VS(SC3). In contrast, the stable magnitudes computed by VS(SC3) are slightly more accurate than those computed by PRESTo; however, it should be highlighted that the accurate magnitude from VS(SC3) is obtained after a significantly longer time (Figure 20), which does not justify the amount of greater accuracy achieved. Concerning the location (epicentral distance and depth), SC3 first estimates are more accurate than those provided by PRESTo, while the performance at the stable instant is fairly similar, even if PRESTo is characterized by a larger dispersion for depth.

Figure 22: Comparison between SC3 (grey bars) and PRESTo (black bars) platforms in terms of magnitude (left), epicentre (middle) and depth (right) accuracy. The top row corresponds to the time at which the first estimate is available; the bottom row corresponds to the time at which the magnitude, epicentre and depth estimates become stable. From left to right: difference in terms of magnitude, epicentre and depth, respectively. The median (η), mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of the distributions are provided above each plot.

2.2.4.1.3 The trend of PGA estimates

Because of the time evolution of the location and magnitude estimates (Figure 19), the resulting computation of ground-shaking IMs is evolutionary as well. For instance, an alert is issued when the expected ground shaking exceeds a prefixed threshold. However, magnitude and location estimates can evolve over time in a non-monotonic way. As a result, a prefixed ground motion threshold (in terms of a given IM) can be exceeded at a certain instant, but not exceeded at a subsequent instant, then exceeded again later in time, and so on. This behaviour can raise questions about maintaining an issued alarm, which have to be properly taken into account when designing a decision support system for EEW. Therefore, a third comparison has been performed by evaluating the number of trend inversions in the temporal evolution of the predicted PGA. A large number of trend inversions is an index of an unstable PGA estimate over time, which affects the performance of the EEW system, even if both the initial and final estimated magnitude and location are accurate.

In this study, PGAs were computed using the GMM mentioned in paragraph 2.2.3.3. The hypocentral distance was used as distance metric. It is important to underline that the GMM by Youngs et al. (1997) was developed using the rupture distance as a distance metric. However, the rupture distance can be approximated by the hypocentral distance for magnitudes less than 5.7 (Cauzzi et al. 2015), as in this study.

Figure 22 shows the number of trend inversions in PGA estimates associated with the magnitude and location computed by SC3 and PRESTo platforms. In order to detect only significant trend inversions, a tolerance of 20% with respect to the PGA associated with the earlier inversion was used. Our analysis shows that the median trend inversions are the same for both platforms ($\eta=2$). However, VS(SC3) is characterized by the lowest mean and standard deviation. PRESTo has a greater number of cases with zero inversions, but also features earthquakes with more than 10 trend inversions. The first cases correspond to situations in which there is no significant variation in time of the computed PGA values (ideal case, in which the lead time is maximum) or there is a nearly monotonic increase of the computed PGA values. The latter cases are associated with two Greek offshore events and one event located in the central Pyrenees. It has to be highlighted that the magnitude estimated by PRESTo strongly depends on the location, since the S-wave arrival time is predicted from the estimated location. Therefore, in the case of inaccurate locations, due for example, to the failure of the binding criterion in associating picks to a particular event, the magnitude will be miscalculated.

Figure 23: Number of trend inversions in the evolution of PGA estimates. The median (η), mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of the distributions are also provided.

2.2.4.2 Comparison between magnitude and location components

In addition, we evaluated the accuracy of the magnitude and location components independently, using *ad-hoc* MATLAB codes for PRESTo, ElarmS and VS (original version), along with the SC3 *scanloc* module for location. VS(SC3) was not considered at this step due to the long time it requires to provide stable magnitude estimates (Figure 20). Across the four algorithms, common P-wave arrival times were used for the location estimation, and identical origins were adopted for the magnitude evaluation, as outlined in paragraph 2.2.3.2. The purpose of this comparison is to determine the precision of the estimates for different levels of algorithmic uncertainty in the source parameters. Since the precision of estimates should increase in time while their uncertainty decreases,

this assessment captures various accuracy versus speed trade-off thresholds that may be of interest to stakeholders for guiding decision-making and alert issuance. The exact values of uncertainty examined for both parameters are discussed in subsequent sections. It is noted that, since the ElarmS algorithm does not account for parameter uncertainty (Cremen and Galasso 2020), we examined its performance at the point when four stations had triggered, which is the minimum required for an alert to be issued in the system (Kuyuk et al. 2014). Location and magnitude accuracy were quantified for each algorithm using the root mean square error metric (Hyndman and Koehler 2006), which is a common tool for measuring the quality of models that are sensitive to outliers.

2.2.4.2.1 Location evaluation

We compared the location estimates in terms of their epicentral distance to the respective target sites outlined in section 2.2.3.3. The uncertainty levels considered for the estimates, in this case, are expressed in the form of coefficients of variation (CV, i.e., the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean), given the large range of source-to-target distances across the regions of interest. We specifically examine the mean distance prediction of each algorithm for $CV = 0.1$, $CV = 0.2$, and $CV = 0.3$ (Figure 23). It is worth noting that if the uncertainty of an algorithm's distance prediction does not reach one of these levels for the station density considered, we instead use its distance prediction at the lowest CV obtained.

It can be seen that the *scanloc* module of SC3 yields the best distance predictions across all uncertainty levels investigated; its associated RMSE value is consistently significantly lower than that of any other algorithm. The second-best performing algorithm depends on the uncertainty level of interest; the PRESTo algorithm is associated with the second smallest RMSE value for both $CV = 0.1$ and $CV = 0.2$, while ElarmS performs second best when the largest level of uncertainty is analysed. VS (original version) is the third-best performing algorithm for $CV = 0.3$ and the worst performing algorithm for the two lower levels of uncertainty.

To further investigate the performance of the three best algorithms, we also examine the RMSE values associated with hypocentral distance (this metric is not available from the VS algorithm, as it does not compute depth). The *scanloc* module yields the lowest hypocentral distance RMSE values across all levels of uncertainty (16.08 for $CV = 0.3$, 12.71 for $CV = 0.2$, and 4.94 for $CV = 0.1$), further confirming that it is the best algorithm for location estimation. The PRESTo RMSE value for $CV = 0.1$ (15.01) is lower than that of ElarmS (21.23), but higher than ElarmS for the other two uncertainty levels (28.36 for $CV = 0.2$ and 37.73). This finding verifies that the second-best performing algorithm is CV-specific and also depends on the choice of distance metric.

Figure 24: Evaluation of distance performance for three levels of the coefficient of variation: CV = 0.3 (left), CV = 0.2 (middle) and CV = 0.1 (right). Different symbols identify different EEW algorithms. The RMSEs are also provided.

2.2.4.2.2 Magnitude evaluation

We compared the mean magnitude predictions across all algorithms, for the following standard deviations (σ) of the estimates: 0.1, 0.2, and 0.3 (Figure 24). It can be observed that the optimal algorithm depends on the level of uncertainty. Results of the PRESTo algorithm are the most accurate for the lowest level of uncertainty investigated (i.e., $\sigma = 0.1$); the associated RMSE value is almost 10% lower than that of ElarmS, which is the second-best performing algorithm. ElarmS provides the optimal estimates when the two larger values of sigma are of interest, yielding at least an 18% lower RMSE value than that of any other case. The VS (original version) algorithm estimates are consistently the least precise and result in significantly larger RMSE values than those of the other two algorithms across all uncertainty levels considered.

Figure 25: Evaluation of magnitude performance for three levels of the standard deviation: CV = 0.3 (left), CV = 0.2 (middle) and CV = 0.1 (right). Different symbols identify different EEW algorithms. The RMSEs are also provided.

2.2.4.2.3 Propagation of uncertainties into the ground motion estimation

We finally investigated the impact of the algorithms' magnitude and location estimation precision on the quality of resulting ground shaking predictions for the Southern Italy testbed, using the epicentral distance version of the Akkar et al. (2014) GMM (see Section 2.2.3.3 for model details). Ground shaking prediction accuracy was quantified with the *MD* metric for sensitivity analyses (Chun et al. 2000), which has already been leveraged to examine the performance of GMMs (Cremen et al. 2020). *MD* was used to measure the difference between the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of PGA

produced when the true source parameters were used in the GMM (considering model uncertainty), and the CDF obtained when an algorithm's estimated source parameters were input to the model (considering both model and propagated source parameter uncertainty, where relevant). We used Monte Carlo sampling of the underlying distributions to capture all uncertainties, and calculated MD according to the following equation:

$$MD = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N [y_{n/N}^i - y_{n/N}^o]^2}}{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N y_n^o}, \quad (2-5)$$

where N is the number of Monte Carlo samples used, and n is the sample index, $y_{n/N}^o$ is the (n/N) quantile of the true GMM CDF ($0 < n < N$), and $y_{n/N}^i$ is the equivalent quantile for the predicted GMM distribution. A lower value indicates a higher similarity between the predicted and true GMM distributions. This type of comparison is useful, as discrepancies in the CDFs indicate the potential for erroneous decisions on the part of the stakeholder, if EEW alerts are issued based on a given probability of exceeding a prescribed value of PGA (Figure 25). For example, a false alert may occur if the predicted PGA is greater than the actual PGA value at the exceedance threshold. On the other hand, an alert may be missed if this prediction is less than the true value. A further benefit of this evaluation procedure is its ability to simultaneously account for uncertainties in the GMM and the EEW source parameter estimates.

We specifically examined the best performing algorithms from the previous analyses, i.e., PRESTo (CV = 0.1), ElarmS, and the *scanloc* module. We first tested the algorithms individually, and then combined the predictions from the best-performing algorithms for location and magnitude estimation (i.e. *scanloc* for location and both PRESTo and ElarmS for magnitude). The results for Southern Italy are presented in Figure 26; each CDF represents the predicted or true values across all seven Italian earthquakes, for 2,000 Monte Carlo samples per event. It can be seen that the PRESTo+*scanloc* combination yields a 40% lower MD value compared to the original version of the PRESTo algorithm, and the ElarmS+*scanloc* combination results in a 50% lower MD value relative to ElarmS. The best MD estimate is obtained using the PRESTo+*scanloc* combination. These findings indicate that optimal combinations of different algorithms (in terms of location and magnitude estimation) could substantially improve the EEW decision-making process.

Figure 26: Demonstration of the GMM evaluation procedure, which measures the difference between the true and estimated GMM CDF for a given set of location and magnitude predictions. The light grey shading indicates PGA exceedance thresholds for which the predicted ground shaking is greater than the true value, which may lead to a false alert. The dark grey shading indicates exceedance thresholds for which the predicted shaking is less than the true value, which may lead to a missed alert.

Figure 27: Evaluation of ground shaking prediction estimates obtained using the best-performing algorithms identified for magnitude and location prediction.

2.2.5 Concluding Remarks

The goal of this analysis was to quantitatively compare the performance of different regional EEW algorithms in order to identify the best algorithms for location and magnitude estimations to be included in the TURNkey platform. A two-step comparison was performed to evaluate:

- 1) the operational performance of the SC3 (including *scanloc* and VS(SC3)) and PRESTo platforms (in terms of timeliness and accuracy); and

- 2) the theoretical isolated performance of the magnitude and location components from the PRESTo, ElarmS and VS (original) algorithms, as well as the *scanloc* location estimation module (in terms of accuracy, and also accounting for relevant uncertainties).

VS was confirmed to be the worst-performing algorithm in terms of both timeliness and accuracy. We found that the best algorithm for location estimation was *scanloc*, which is capable of providing fast and correct earthquake origins. In the case of magnitude, there was not a unique best performing algorithm for all the situations analysed in this study. Instead, the optimal choice for magnitude estimation is a function of the tolerable uncertainty level, which should be defined according to end-user needs by evaluating the acceptable trade-off between fast (but more uncertain) and accurate (but slower) estimates. For the case in which faster estimates are desired, ElarmS is recommended; conversely, if expected lead times are sufficient to allow more accurate estimates, PRESTo is the best choice for magnitude estimation. Therefore, we recommend that both algorithms are included in the TURNkey platform as independent modules for magnitude evaluation. In fact, the modular structure of SC3, on which the TURNkey platform will rely, enables the flexible replacement of modules (i.e. by selecting the most appropriate module for each situation), and the simultaneous running of different algorithms receiving the same input.

We also illustrated the performance improvement that the best algorithmic combinations for location and magnitude estimation (i.e. *scanloc* + PRESTo magnitude component and *scanloc* + ElarmS magnitude component) could offer at the ground motion prediction (decision-making) stage of EEW, relative to the original versions of the algorithms. We used a technique leveraged from sensitivity analysis to quantify the quality of GMM predictions for a given set of location and magnitude estimates, and specifically focused on events in Southern Italy. We found that the *scanloc*+PRESTo combination provides a 40% improvement in ground-shaking predictions over the PRESTo algorithm, and the *scanloc*+ElarmS combination ground shaking predictions are 50% more accurate than those of the ElarmS algorithm, at least for the testbed examined. This implies that optimal algorithmic combinations (in terms of location and magnitude estimation) may notably enhance a decision-making process for EEW triggering that depends on ground motion thresholds, leading to less false alerts and missed events.

The results of this study were obtained through offline playbacks of the seismic waveforms and EEW parameters associated with 27 historic or simulated earthquakes representative of different tectonic environments. This also translated in different station distributions and densities across Europe. For Southern Italy and the Pyrenees, for which synthetic seismograms were computed, the actual network configurations were used, while for Greece, Romania and Iceland, for which real recordings were used, the considered stations were constrained by the availability of recordings. The outcome of the study should therefore be interpreted as an average performance of the examined algorithms across different seismicity and network geometries in Europe. For target- or region-specific studies, a more detailed feasibility study is recommended.

It should also be highlighted that phase detection and association are difficult and error-prone tasks, especially during intense aftershock sequences (Meier et al. 2020). The parameters governing phase

detection and association must be carefully calibrated for each area of interest, evaluating the overall seismicity and network geometry. Therefore, the most appropriate tuning for a certain area could be different from that used in this study, which was calibrated using only the small sample of events analysed. Moreover, we did not explore the sensitivity of the Bayesian priors for PRESTo and VS (original version) algorithms. For example, magnitude priors retrieved from regional hazard studies (instead of the European ESHM13 model) may have resulted in better performance of a given algorithm. Finally, it should be noted that the empirical scaling relationships that use EEW parameters (i.e. ground motion peak values and predominant periods) for magnitude and location computation in the different algorithms may not be optimal for the regions considered in this study, especially for the deep events in the Vrancea region (for example, VS magnitude estimation relationships were calibrated for Californian events by assuming a depth of 3 km). The necessity to conduct region-specific recalibration of the relationship coefficients should be investigated when implementing an EEW system. Otherwise, it may be most practical to simply evaluate and add empirically derived offsets (if any) to the magnitudes estimated for particular regions (Cua, 2020, pers. comm.).

To overcome the aforementioned limitations, which primarily affect the choice of the best magnitude algorithm (i.e. PRESTo or ElarmS) to be implemented in SC3, the procedure outlined in Minson et al. (2017) could be adopted. This methodology combines real-time independent prediction models into one unified ground-motion prediction by evaluating the probability that each EEW algorithm is correct.

3 FEASIBILITY STUDY FOR RRE SYSTEMS

3.1 Introduction

RRE systems aim at providing an accurate picture of an earthquake's impact in the shortest time possible after the event. Most current RRE systems rely on the derivation of shake-maps and on the application of rapid damage and loss assessment tools. Shake-maps refer to updated ground-motion maps that make the most of the available post-earthquake information (i.e., earthquake parameters, ground-motion records, macroseismic testimonies), in order to constrain uncertainties of expected ground-motion levels (i.e., to be published a few minutes following the event). For the generation of shake-maps, it is foreseen to use either the multivariate normal (MVN) distribution procedure (Worden et al. 2018) or the Bayesian updating approach for the inference of ground-motion fields (Gehl et al. 2017): both approaches have proven to be mathematically sound, with an accurate treatment of the uncertainty field. They are also able to integrate multiple types of observations and to treat different intensity measures while accounting for their cross-correlation. Uncertainties related to hazard assessment may then be propagated to the damage and loss assessment step in order to obtain a distribution of expected losses.

In order to assess the feasibility of RREs in Europe, we focused on two areas from the testbeds: Luchon valley in the Pyrénées and Hveragerði in the south of Iceland.

- For Luchon valley, a virtual earthquake scenario is used (Mw 6.0; epicentre longitude/latitude: $0.65^{\circ}/42.7^{\circ}$), with a chosen intensity sufficiently high to induce damage to the buildings in the risk assessment. We analysed the ground-motion uncertainties and their impact on the damage distribution.
- Concerning Iceland, we investigated the 2008 Mw 6.3 Ölfus earthquake, and we evaluated the strong ground motions felt in the nearby city of Hveragerði. We used the earthquake data from the dense seismic array, which provide accelerations at a wide range of spectral periods.

Thanks to the availability of building exposure data for dozens of towns in Luchon valley, it is possible to test the connection of shake-maps with damage assessment tools in order to provide a rapid loss assessment at the regional scale. Uncertainties in the estimated hazard input are propagated thanks to the generation of stochastic ground-motion fields and the aggregation of damage statistics in the end. Various cases are studied, such as the absence of any field observations (prediction earthquake scenario only), the presence of a sparse seismic network (current situation in Luchon), and the prospective case where more seismic stations could be deployed in the area. The effects on the damage distributions can then be quantified in order to assess the benefit of setting up *ad hoc* RRE systems.

In the Iceland test-bed, the town of Hveragerði is covered by a dense seismic array, whose effect on the shake-map is investigated. Moreover, various GMPEs specifically developed for this area are also tested, as well as different spatial correlation models. Finally, the site terms of the array stations are described through probability distributions: this source of uncertainty (i.e., conversion of the stations' measurements from soil to rock conditions) is integrated into the shake-map algorithm as well. In the end, this sensitivity study on the modelling assumptions related to shake-maps will provide valuable insights on where subsequent modelling efforts are needed.

3.2 Methods

This part provides an overview of the shake-map methods used in order to estimate the ground motions and felt intensities following an earthquake rupture (USGS shakemap and the Bayesian method). It also introduces briefly the Armageddon tool developed at BRGM (Sedan et al. 2013) and how damage scenarios are computed.

3.2.1 Shake-map algorithms

We present here the two algorithms used for the computation of shake-maps: ShakeMap[®] version 4 (Worden et al. 2018) and the Bayesian network approach (Gehl et al. 2017). While the ShakeMap[®] approach has been improved in its version 4, in particular for the treatment of uncertainties, and is a fast and efficient method to compute shake-maps, the Bayesian approach remains interesting as additional uncertainties may be taken into account and propagated more naturally through Bayesian inference. Moreover, the Bayesian approach has the ability of building additional layers of variables (e.g., damage data, uncertain observations) on top of the shake-map, in order to create a more heuristic framework. Below, we present the mathematical base for each of these two algorithms. Both algorithms will be used in the Applications section later.

3.2.1.1 USGS Shakemap version 4

The USGS system ShakeMap[®] version 4 (Worden et al., 2018), is based on the MVN distribution (Vanmarcke 1983; Stafford 2012). The vector of ground-motion parameters \mathbf{Y} (assumed to be normally distributed) is divided into \mathbf{Y}_1 (m prediction sites, or grid points) and \mathbf{Y}_2 (n observations sites), with the following expressions for the mean and variance:

$$\mu_{\mathbf{Y}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{\mathbf{Y}_1} \\ \mu_{\mathbf{Y}_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \Sigma_{\mathbf{Y}} = \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{\mathbf{Y}_1\mathbf{Y}_1} & \Sigma_{\mathbf{Y}_1\mathbf{Y}_2} \\ \Sigma_{\mathbf{Y}_2\mathbf{Y}_1} & \Sigma_{\mathbf{Y}_2\mathbf{Y}_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3-1)$$

Then, given a set of observations $\mathbf{Y}_2 = \mathbf{y}_2$, a vector of residuals is defined as $\zeta = \mathbf{y}_2 - \mu_{\mathbf{Y}_2}$. Thanks to the MVN, it is possible to express the mean and variance of the set of predictions \mathbf{Y}_1 as follows:

$$\mu_{\mathbf{Y}_1|\mathbf{y}_2} = \mu_{\mathbf{Y}_1} + \Sigma_{\mathbf{Y}_1\mathbf{Y}_2} \cdot \Sigma_{\mathbf{Y}_2\mathbf{Y}_2}^{-1} \cdot \zeta \quad (3-2)$$

$$\Sigma_{\mathbf{Y}_1\mathbf{Y}_2|\mathbf{y}_2} = \Sigma_{\mathbf{Y}_1\mathbf{Y}_1} - \Sigma_{\mathbf{Y}_1\mathbf{Y}_2} \cdot \Sigma_{\mathbf{Y}_2\mathbf{Y}_2}^{-1} \cdot \Sigma_{\mathbf{Y}_2\mathbf{Y}_1} \quad (3-3)$$

The initial mean values of \mathbf{Y}_1 are obtained from a GMPE, and the variance-covariance matrix is assembled from the standard-deviations associated with the GMPE and from the spatial correlation structure of the ground-motion parameter(s) of interest. Therefore, the results from the equations above may be directly used as the updated ground-motion distribution for the generation of the shake-map. Worden et al. (2018) showed that this approach enables the consideration of multiple types of ground-motion parameters (e.g., PGA, SA at different periods) simultaneously: thanks to the cross-correlation structure between some ground-motion parameters (especially spectral responses), it is possible to gain knowledge and constrain shake-maps when only parameters of a given type have been recorded, for instance.

3.2.1.2 Bayesian network

The approach proposed by Gehl et al. (2017) is based on the Bayesian updating of correlated Gaussian fields: the prior distribution of the ground-motion field, consisting of a simple predictive scenario of the earthquake event with a GMPE, is updated with the observations in order to generate a posterior distribution of the ground motion at each grid point. To this end, a Gaussian Bayesian Network (BN) models the distribution of a given ground-motion parameter Y at each grid point i . Thanks to the lognormal assumption used in most GMPEs, a lognormal-normal conversion is able to express the conditional probability of Y_i as a normal distribution, with the mean expressed as:

$$\mu(Y_i|\mathbf{U}, W) = X_i + \sigma_\zeta \cdot \sum_{j=i}^n t_{ij} \cdot U_j + \sigma_\eta \cdot W \quad , \quad (3-4)$$

where X_i is the mean estimate of the ground-motion parameter from the GMPE, σ_ζ is the standard deviation of the intra-event term, and σ_η is the standard deviation of the inter-event term. The matrix of elements t_{ij} results from the Cholesky decomposition of the correlation matrix between the intra-event terms: spatial correlation models such as the one from Jayaram & Baker (2009) may be used to compute this correlation, based on the distances between all grid points and observations. The variables U_j and W follow a standard normal distribution, and they are essential to model the statistical dependence between the Y_i , and consequently, the updating process.

Observations, either in the form of ground-motion measurements or macroseismic intensities (with the associated uncertainties), are added to the BN as evidence, and subsequently the posterior distribution of the ground-motion parameters is collected at the variables representing the grid points. This approach is able to generate updated maps for the usual ground-motion parameters (e.g. PGA, PGV, SA) as well as macroseismic intensity.

3.2.2 Damage and loss estimates

Structural damage and loss assessment software in a rapid response context needs to be quick enough to deliver first estimates, which should be able to cover potentially large built areas. These tools enable the use of ground motion estimates and of exposure and vulnerability maps in order to assess the level of damage and loss at different levels of resolution. They have originally been developed for the computation of prospective damage scenarios at city, regional or national scale in preparedness and mitigation phases.

Here we use the Armagedom software developed at BRGM (Sedan et al. 2013), which can produce an analysis of loss estimation at different levels of resolution: level 0, level 1 and level 2:

- Level 0 analyses rely on empirical methods and basic exposure data (e.g. national census data). Vulnerability classes are described in terms of the A-F classification defined in EMS-98 (Grunthal 1998). Therefore, the seismic action has to be expressed as macroseismic intensity values. This level is well suited for results that aggregated at the scale of a city or municipality.
- Level 1 analyses are based on empirical macroseismic methods as well. However, they use a more detailed description of the buildings. A vulnerability index V_i is estimated based on various building features, and the semi-empirical method by Giovinazzi and Lagomarsino

(2004) is used in order to generate damage distributions. Results may be rendered at the scale of a municipality or a city district.

- Level 2 analyses are based on mechanical methods, namely the N2 approach (Fajfar 2000) that estimates the spectral displacement corresponding to the “Performance Point”. Then, the spectral displacement is either associated with a mean damage grade (and a damage distribution is generated like in level 1 analyses) or to pre-computed fragility curves. Results may be rendered at the scale of a city district or a single building.

An overview of the software architecture is illustrated in Figure 28 below.

Figure 28: Organization of Armageddom software [adapted from Sedan et al. (2013)]. The green rectangle represents the hazard assessment part, which is replaced by a shake-map in an RRE context. The blue rectangle represents data and models that are gathered before the event (i.e., “cold data”). The red rectangle represents the data and models that are computed in near-real-time after the event (“hot data”).

In this study, we run the analysis at level 1, where the results consist in the proportion of buildings falling in each of the 5 damage states D1 to D5 as defined in EMS-98. D1 corresponds to light or negligible damage, D2 to moderate damage, D3 major damage, D4 very major damage, and D5 represents collapsed buildings. A D0 category is allocated, when no damage is present.

3.2.3 A sampling of stochastic damage scenarios

In addition, the shake-map uncertainties are estimated, σ_{inter} and σ_{intra} , the inter-event and intra-event errors, respectively. In order to estimate uncertainties of the damage scenarios, we use the shake-map uncertainties to generate a large number of ground motion scenarios (1000 in this case). For each scenario, we generate a random value of σ_{inter} from its distribution (trimmed at the 5th and 95th percentiles), which is combined with a random vector of σ_{intra} (also using its distribution trimmed at the 5th and 95th percentiles), containing different values at each grid point (accounting for the spatial correlation between the grid points). The stochastic simulations are then used as input into Armagedom. Gathering and ordering the 1000 Armagedom results provides us with a distribution of damage scenarios, from which we can extract percentiles, therefore indicating how uncertainties are propagated from the shake-map to damage estimates.

Figure 29: Illustration of the procedure used to compute the statistical distribution of damages in Luchon valley from a synthetic earthquake event.

3.3 Applications

This section investigates the applicability and accuracy of the aforementioned RRE methods. To this end, two areas in TB-2 and TB-3 are considered, respectively Luchon (Pyrénées) and Hveragerði (Iceland).

3.3.1 TB-2 (Pyrenees) – area of Luchon

3.3.1.1 Presentation of the test-bed and seismic network

The Luchon valley, situated in the central Pyrenees (French side), has been chosen as a first site to test the RRE systems in place. The Pyrenees are one of the most seismically active zones in France; it is important to establish efficient rapid response systems in order to mitigate seismic risk in the area. This is also the reason why the vulnerability assessment is well detailed (Figure 30, left), with building classes readily available at the district scale, and site effects have already been determined using geophysical and geological on-site investigations during previous European projects (e.g. SISPYR). Another interesting feature of the site is the presence of several seismic stations nearby, two of which are within the area of interest itself (roughly 30 by 30 km). All the stations belonging to four networks (BRGM, ICGC, IGN or OMP) provide accessible data in order to compute shake-maps (Figure 30, right). Therefore, the detailed data and the relatively high risk for the region make it a suitable area for a feasibility study.

Figure 30: Luchon Valley and exposure data locations (left) and surrounding seismic stations (right).

The feasibility study will be conducted in two steps. First, a shake-map is calculated given a potentially damaging virtual scenario (Mw 6.0 in the vicinity of the valley) as well as the corresponding uncertainties. Subsequently, from the estimated ground-motion field and its uncertainties, we simulate stochastic scenarios of damage given building vulnerability and ground motion intensity using the Armagedom tool as described in the section above.

3.3.1.2 Shake-maps and associated uncertainties

Due to the lack of strong motion data recorded in Luchon valley that would induce significant damage to the buildings, we choose to compute an arbitrary virtual earthquake scenario of Mw 6.0 near the valley (longitude/latitude of the epicentre: 0.65°/42.7°). We also simulate PGA records at the station locations. A shake-map is computed using the BN approach.

In terms of PGA distribution, we obtain values up to $\sim 2.9 \text{ m/s}^2$ in the valley after applying site amplification factors (Figure 31, left). The uncertainties on the \log_{10} PGA values have a maximum value around 0.4 and are close to 0 at observations points (Figure 31, right), as we do not consider the possible uncertainty due to site effect coefficients or PGA measurements.

Figure 31: Shake-map for an Mw 6.0 scenario near Luchon (left) and corresponding uncertainties (right). Square dots indicate the seismic station locations, and the star corresponds to the epicentre location.

The PGA values are converted into macroseismic intensities using the ground-motion-intensity conversion equation (GMICE) by Souriau (2006) for this region, which has the following form:

$$\text{Intensity} = 4.8108 + 2.70257 \cdot \log_{10}(\text{PGA}) + 1.2162 \cdot \log_{10}(22.8) \quad (3-5)$$

The uncertainties are propagated using the relation:

$$\sigma_{\text{Intensity}}^2 = \sigma_{\text{GMICE}}^2 + (2.70257 \cdot \sigma_{\log_{10}\text{PGA}})^2, \text{ where } \sigma_{\text{GMICE}} = 0.484 \quad (3-6)$$

We obtain macroseismic intensities around VII in the valley and a maximum value of uncertainty $\sigma_{\text{Intensity}}$ around 1.2. $\sigma_{\text{Intensity}}$ never decreases to zero as the uncertainty from the GMICE conversion remains (Figure 32). An intensity of VII is enough to induce damage to buildings; we can, therefore, assess how ground motion uncertainties are propagated to the damage scenarios.

Figure 32: Simulated macroseismic intensity for Mw 6.0 scenario calculated via the BN shake-map method (left) and corresponding uncertainties (right).

3.3.1.3 Damage scenarios

The second part of the analysis consists in crossing the vulnerability information with the intensities determined in the previous step. For Luchon, the territory is segmented in several polygonal areas of homogeneous vulnerability types (i.e., the combination of EMS98 classes A to F). There are in general 1 to 3 different polygons for a single municipality (in total, 101 polygons are assessed in the Luchon area): a vulnerability index V_i is then assigned to each polygon. Combined with the macroseismic intensity, we calculate for each of the polygonal areas the proportion of EMS98 damage states induced (D0 or no damage, to D5 or collapsed building) by using a beta distribution. We run 1000 stochastic scenarios taking into account the uncertainties on ground motions in order to obtain a distribution of damage in each class. We choose not to use the uncertainty from the GMICE, as unlike in Armagedom, some damage estimation algorithms are based directly on PGA values and adding σ_{GMICE} hides the benefit of adding seismic stations in order to improve the damage scenarios of this study.

Figure 33 represents the percentages of buildings falling into the D2, D3 or D4&D5 (combined) categories, for the median values, but also 16th and 84th percentiles. These percentages are given for each homogeneous area represented by circles centred on the polygons' centroids, whose diameters are proportional to the total number of buildings within the areas.

For a Mw 6.0 earthquake, evaluating the median value, we note that around 8% of the buildings would experience moderate damage (D2). However, considering the 16th and 84th percentiles, there is a large discrepancy as the percentage may vary between 6% and 10%. It varies between 2.1 and 5.4% in the level D3 and between 0.5 and 2.3% in level D4&D5 (D4 and D5 are grouped as the percentages are relatively low).

Figure 33: Percentages of buildings falling into the D2, D3 or D4&D5 categories (for the median values, 16th and 84th percentiles). The percentages are given for each homogeneous area represented by circles centred on the polygons' centroids. The circles' diameters are proportional to the total number of buildings within the areas.

Although the results are detailed in Figure 33, they are grouped for the whole Luchon valley and summarized in Table 10. It is clear that the large uncertainties on the ground motions have a significant impact on the damage distribution. This is particularly obvious, when analysing the total proportion of non-damaged buildings in the valley: it varies between 61.7% (16th percentile) and 75.4% (84th percentile).

Table 10: Percentages of buildings in different damage state for the simulated damage scenarios. δ 84th - 16th refers to the difference between the 84th and the 16th percentiles of damage percentage.

damage state	16 th percentile	median value	84 th percentile	mean value	δ 84 th - 16 th
D0	61.7	68.4	75.4	68.3	13.7
D1	15.7	18.0	20.1	17.9	4.4

D2	6.2	8.7	10.9	8.6	4.7
D3	2.1	3.6	5.4	3.8	3.3
D4 and more	0.5	1.1	2.3	1.4	1.7

For comparison, we compute 1000 stochastic scenarios more, using the same virtual earthquake, but setting the uncertainty on the ground motion as if we did not have any observation (i.e., simple predictive scenario using only the GMPE) to observe the effect of adding stations on the damage results. The latter are displayed in Figure 34 and summarized in Table 11.

Comparing the two cases, we see that the mean values are very similar (e.g. 68.3% with observations, 67.9% without observation, for damage state D0), but that the uncertainties are reduced when using observations (for damages over D4, it ranges from 0.52% to 2.25% with observations, and from 0.57% to 4.22% without). This demonstrates that for this scenario, having the two stations within the Luchon valley improves the shake-map and the damage estimates by reducing uncertainties. However, the uncertainties on the damage estimates remain relatively high with or without observations, as they are reduced only very locally in the case of a sparse seismic network.

Figure 34: Percentages of buildings falling into the D2, D3 or D4&D5 (combined) categories (for the median values, 16th and 84th percentiles) in the case without any observations.

Table 11: Percentages of buildings per damage state for the simulated damage scenarios, with no decrease of uncertainties at observation points. δ 84th - 16th refers to the difference between the 84th and the 16th percentiles of damage percentage.

damage state	16 th percentile	median value	84 th percentile	mean value	δ 84 th - 16 th
D0	58.8	68.3	77.1	67.9	18.3
D1	13.9	17.0	19.5	16.8	5.6
D2	5.7	8.6	11.3	8.6	5.6
D3	2.0	4.1	6.7	4.4	4.7
D4 and more	0.6	1.7	4.2	2.4	3.7

Finally, we test a third case, where 15 virtual stations have been added at the locations of the largest towns of the valley (see Figure 35): this number represents a realistic estimate of the number of Raspberry-4D stations that will be deployed in this test-bed within the TURNkey project. The results of this simulation (see Table 12) show a small decrease in uncertainties. The slight variations of mean and median values are due to the small modifications of ground motions due to the added (virtual) observations.

Figure 35: Shake-map for a Mw 6.0 scenario near Luchon (left) and corresponding uncertainties (right). Square dots indicate the seismic stations, and the star corresponds to the epicentre location. In this case, 15 virtual stations at the locations of the largest towns have been added.

Table 12: Percentages of buildings per damage state for the simulated damage scenarios, adding 15 virtual stations.

damage state	16 th percentile	median value	84 th percentile	mean value	δ 84 th - 16 th
D0	69.4	75.5	80.9	75.2	11.5
D1	13.2	15.9	18.5	15.8	5.2
D2	4.3	6.2	8.1	6.2	3.8
D3	1.1	2.0	3.2	2.2	2.0
D4 and more	0.2	0.4	0.9	0.6	0.7

In order to provide better visualisation of the effect of seismic network density on the damage estimates, we analyse the difference of percentage values at the 84th and 16th percentiles, called δ 84th - 16th in the document. These values representing the spread of the distribution are calculated in Table 10, Table 11 and Table 12 and are gathered in Figure 36.

We can clearly see a decrease of the uncertainty on damage assessment. It is particularly visible for categories D0 where δ 84th - 16th drops from 18.3 without observations to 11.5 assuming a network with 15 additional stations distributed in the largest towns. For category D4&D5 (combined), it also drops significantly, from 3.7 to 0.7. Although this effect is less obvious in category D1, adding stations clearly improves the overall results.

Figure 36: Difference of percentages at 84th and 16th percentiles, in each of the damage states D0 to D4&D5 (combined), and for 3 different cases: without observations (blue), using the stations currently available (orange), and adding 15 virtual stations in large towns of the valley (grey).

3.3.2 TB-3 (Iceland) – Area of Hveragerði

In the following, we apply the Bayesian approach to generate shake-maps for the Mw 6.3 earthquake that occurred on 29 May 2008 in the westernmost part of the South Iceland Seismic Zone. The event took place on two parallel faults that ruptured nearly simultaneously. The earthquake strong ground motion used in this study was recorded at 20 stations, 10 of which were a part of a small-aperture urban array covering an area of 1.23 km² at 1-2 km distance from the causative fault. The recordings, thus being in the extreme near-fault region of the earthquake exhibit high-intensity ground motion of short-duration (4-5 s) and large PGAs (38-88% g) (Halldórsson and Sigbjörnsson 2009).

Pending the availability of exposure and damage models for the town of Hveragerði, this application focuses on the shake-map part of the RRE framework. We perform a sensitivity study on the outcomes of the shake-map by considering several parameters and modelling assumptions:

- influence of the array observations;
- influence of different GMPEs;
- influence of uncertainties related to observations (i.e., uncertain site terms identified at the array stations); and
- influence of different spatial correlation models.

3.3.2.1 Tectonics and seismicity of Iceland

Iceland is the most seismically active region in northern Europe. It is situated in the North Atlantic Ocean where the Icelandic hotspot, a broad, localized upwelling of magma from deep within the mantle, elevates the seafloor so that it is partly exposed and forms land (see Figure 37). The Icelandic hotspot drives the volcanism and seismicity of Iceland along with the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, a plate margin of active tectonic horizontal extension that runs along the entire length of the Atlantic Ocean between the Arctic and the Antarctica and approaches Iceland from the southwest and central north. The presence of the Icelandic hotspot, the centre of which is located approximately under the northwest part of the largest glacier in Iceland, causes an eastward ridge-jump on land in Iceland, forming the eastern and northern volcanic zones. As a result, two fracture zones characterized by transform motion have been formed in the south and north of Iceland, respectively. These zones are the South Iceland Seismic Zone (SISZ) and Reykjanes Peninsula Oblique Rift in southwest Iceland (RPOR), and the Tjörnes Fracture Zone (TFZ) in northern Iceland. The potential for large destructive earthquakes is largest in these zones, which is confirmed by historical annals spanning 1000 years.

Figure 37. Map of Iceland's topography and bathymetry, outlining the transform fault systems of Iceland, the SISZ+RPOR in the south and the TFZ in the north.

The SISZ and the RPOR take up the transform motion of the eastward jump of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge in southwest Iceland. Instead of a sinistral transform fault system linear and parallel to the direction of plate spreading, a “bookshelf” faulting system of near-vertical dextral transform faults perpendicular to the direction of plate spreading takes up the transform motion across the SISZ and RPOR (Einarsson et al. 1981; Einarsson 1991; 2008; 2015; Steigerwald et al. 2020).

The volcanic earthquakes in the four volcanic systems in the RPOR (shaded regions in Figure 38) are assumed to be maximum Mw 4.5-5 and thus have a minimum contributing role in the assessment of seismic hazard. Moreover, volcanic seismicity occurs episodically, and the release of tectonic deformation is thus taken up by transform motion on the bookshelf system in between volcanic episodes (Hreinsdóttir et al. 2001). As a result, earthquakes associated with volcanic activity are not modelled. The bookshelf system long known to characterize the occurrence of strong earthquakes in the SISZ has been shown to be continuous across the Hengill Triple Junction and along the RPOR (Steigerwald et al. 2020). The system is characterized by an array of parallel north-south near-vertical dextral strike-slip faults. The distance between the faults is assumed to be on the order of $d \sim 1-5$ km in the SISZ and the RPOR. There is, however, evidence that the distances between faults decrease towards the west in the RPOR, even down to a few hundred meters (P.Einarsson, 2020, pers.comm.).

Figure 38. Mapped fault traces of transform faults in the RPOR (Einarsson et al. 2020; Steigerwald et al. 2020) and hypothetical vertical fault plane projections of strong historical earthquakes in the SISZ (red lines; Roth 2004; Stefánsson et al. 2006) along with approximate epicentral locations (stars; see, e.g., Einarsson 2015) along the approximate central axis of deformation and seismicity (thin red line) and hypothetical earthquake zones that facilitates the classification of seismicity and seismogenic depth (cyan).

3.3.2.2 The 29 May 2008 Ölfus earthquake

At 15:45 UTC on 29 May 2008, a Mw 6.3 earthquake occurred in the western part of the South Iceland Seismic Zone (SISZ). The first motion originated approximately 6.5 km east–southeast of the town of Hveragerði on what aftershocks appear to identify as an almost 10 km long north-south trending fault. However, most aftershocks outlined another almost 20 km long north-south trending fault less than 2 km from the town of Hveragerði, which happens to be the location of the ICEARRAY, the first small-aperture strong-motion array in Iceland. The ICEARRAY produced high-quality recordings on 11 stations over an aperture of 1.9 km and 50 m minimum interstation distance. The recordings are characterized by strong motion of short duration and high intensity, manifested by the geometric mean of horizontal peak ground acceleration ranging between 0.44 and 0.87 g. Moreover, a prominent long-period near-fault velocity pulse is observed both along the strike-normal and strike-parallel directions. Its apparently repetitive behaviour may reflect the complex source effects of the two-fault systems. The linear response spectra of the ICEARRAY data indicate

that the long-period energy of the velocity pulse seen along the strike-normal direction is not present in the strike-parallel direction. However, the long-period spectral energy seen along the strike-parallel direction is caused by permanent tectonic displacement. The earthquake action during this earthquake exceeded the seismic design requirements of the vast majority of the structures in the town by a factor of 2-5. Nevertheless, the vast majority of the structures did not suffer significant structural damage (Sigbjörnsson et al. 2009; Halldórsson and Sigbjörnsson 2009).

Figure 39: North-south trending alignment of the seismicity distribution for the period of 29 May to 29 June, 2008 in south-west Iceland indicates the location of the causative faults (approximated by the dashed lines) of the 15:45 UTC 29 May 2008 earthquake. The triangles are the closest recording sites of the Icelandic strong-motion network. The inset picture on the bottom right shows Iceland with respect to the rift axis of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (black line), the TFZ in the north and SISZ in the south indicated by the shaded areas. The solid rectangle within the shaded area indicates the region shown in the main picture. The solid rectangle in the main picture indicates the area of the town of Hveragerði shown at the top left, depicting the locations of the recording stations of the ICEARRAY (dots) against the town's street layout (Halldórsson and Sigbjörnsson 2009).

3.3.2.3 Procedure

In the following, we generate shake-maps of the ground motion acceleration for rock conditions at the surface using different GMPEs applicable for Iceland, as well as different spatial correlation models at different periods. The output is in terms of mean and standard deviation (in a logarithmic scale).

Herein, we used a set of five empirical GMPEs developed by Kowsari et al. (2020) based on Bayesian inference using Icelandic strong-motion data and informative prior distributions of empirical parameters from other regions and physical parameters. The ground motion models all have different functional forms, referred to as KSea20 A, B, C, D and E, the attenuation of which is shown in Figure

40 and Figure 41 with respect to Joyner-Boore distance and peak acceleration and spectral response parameters.

- KSea20 A : Y1_np3 (functional form from Akkar & Bommer 2010);
- KSea20 B: Y1_np35 (functional form from Akkar & Bommer 2010);
- KSea20 C: Y2_np4 (functional form from Ambraseys et al. 2005);
- KSea20 D: Y3_np45 (functional form from Lin & Lee 2008);
- KSea20 E: Y4_np45 (functional form from Zhao et al. 2006);
- KSea20 F: Y5_np456 (based on magnitude-dependent depth in the SISZ).

Figure 40: The attenuation of the recalibrated ground motion models when information prior is used for PGA and PSA at various periods. The models are evaluated at Mw 5.2 (dash-dotted line), 6.4 (solid line) and 7.2 (dashed line). The Mw 6.4 is the weighted average magnitude of the three largest earthquakes that account for the majority of the data. The observed data are shown as diamonds colour-coded by magnitude. The dotted lines represent the range of model uncertainties ($\pm 1\sigma$ around the median predictions for Mw 5.2).

The GMPEs show a discrepancy in the predictions at short distances (Figure 41).

Figure 41: The estimated value of the median of PGA in (m/s^2) for an Mw of 6.3 predicted using the different GMPEs for a range of Rjb distances between 0 and 10 km, represented in linear scale.

The structural periods tested are: $T=0$ s ($S_a = PGA$); $T=0.1$ s; $T=0.15$ s; $T=0.2$ s; $T=0.25$ s; $T=0.3$ s. These periods have been selected as they correspond to periods of large differences between the site terms of the array stations (see Figure 58).

With the Bayesian framework, we are able to generate the shake-maps considering the uncertainties of the site effects at the stations recording the earthquake ground motion at different periods (Figure 42), from Rahpeyma et al. (2020) (unpublished).

Figure 42: Standard deviation of the site effect at the stations recording the acceleration spectra at different periods.

Finally, different spatial correlation models described in Table 13 and illustrated in Figure 43 are tested.

Table 13: Description of the spatial correlation functions evaluated in this work

References	Database	Spatial Correlation Model for PGA
Jayaram and Baker (2009) PGA and SA for T up to 10 s	Dataset used in Campbell and Bozorgnia (2008)	$\rho = \exp(-3 * h(x) / 8.5)$
Goda and Atkinson (2010) PGA and SA	SK-NET, K-NET and KiK NET database: 20 earthquakes with $5.6 \leq M_w \leq 6.8$ and $7 \text{ km} \leq \text{depth} \leq 70 \text{ km}$	$\rho = 5 * \exp(-(0.06 * h(x)^{0.283}) - 5 + 1)$
Esposito and Iervolino (2011) PGA and PGV	Subset of ESM (M_w 5–7.6 and Rjb 0-100 km) and ITACA (M_w 4–6.9 and Rjb 0-196 km)	$\rho = \exp(-3 * h(x) / 13.5)$
Heresi and Miranda (2019) PGA and SA for T up to 10 s	39 well-recorded global earthquakes	$\rho = \exp(-(h(x)/13.10)^{0.55})$

Figure 43: The models of the spatial correlation of PGA as a function of the interstation distance.

3.3.2.4 Results

This section details the shake-maps that have been computed using various sets of models and assumptions.

3.3.2.4.1 Shake-maps using different GMPEs: effect of the arrays of recordings

Figure 44 shows the estimated ground motion (PGA) using the 6 GMPEs for this region, while Figure 45 shows the estimated ground motions updated by the values of accelerations recorded at the seismic stations around the fault. The recorded accelerations are corrected using the site effect, and thus the ground motion estimated is for a rock site (pending the application of a specific soil amplification map of the area). The updated maps are generated using the Bayesian approach, considering the spatial correlation model by Jayaram and Baker (2009). Figure 46 and Figure 47 show the standard deviation of the estimated ground motion without and with the updates due to the recordings, respectively. The standard deviation is equal to zero at the observation points, and it increases with distance from the observation.

Figure 44: PGA (mean) shake-map estimated using different GMPEs. The spatial correlation function is from Jayaram and Baker (2009).

Figure 45: PGA (mean) shake-map estimated using different GMPEs considering the recordings at the stations. The spatial correlation function is from Jayaram and Baker (2009).

Figure 46: PGA (standard deviation in logarithmic scale) shake-map estimated using different GMPEs. The spatial correlation function is from Jayaram and Baker (2009).

Figure 47: PGA (standard deviation in logarithmic scale) shake-map estimated using different GMPEs considering the recordings at the stations. The spatial correlation function is from Jayaram and Baker (2009).

The existence of different empirical Bayesian GMMs allows us to compute the coefficient of variation (CV), which consists of computing the standard deviation of the six predictions and normalizing it by the mean using the arithmetic values for both the standard deviation and the mean. Figure 49 (left) shows the CV from the 6 GMPEs (Figure 44) and Figure 49 (right) shows the CV resulting from the six shake-maps considering the observations at the stations (Figure 45). This coefficient demonstrates that the Bayesian network generates robust results to predict the ground motion close to the observations (CV tends to zero meaning less variation of the prediction in terms of the GMPE model used.) The shake-maps predicts the ground motion close to the observations in a consistent way, regardless of the GMPE used. It appears that there is a local minima in the CV at a constant distance of about 1-2 km (r_{JB}) from the causative faults (blue band) indicating that the GMMs all tend to agree in their prediction at these distances (see insert figure below). Their disagreement, however, increases at smaller distances (red region at distances less than ~ 1 km) for this magnitude. At distances of ~ 2 -10 km their predictions deviate slightly (green broad region), while for distances beyond and this magnitude, there is very good agreement between the GMMs (broad blue region).

Figure 48: Average shake-maps computed using the 6 GMPEs (left) without considering the PGA recorded at the stations and (right) taking into account the recordings at the stations.

Figure 49: The arithmetic coefficient of variation CV computed as the standard deviation of the PGA, computed using the 6 different GMPEs, normalized by the average of the PGA of the 6 GMPEs. The left CV is computed using the mean PGA maps estimated from GMPEs, without considering the recordings at the stations (from Figure 44). The plot on the right is computed using the mean PGA maps estimated using the 6 GMPEs, considering the recordings at the stations (Figure 45). The spatial correlation function is from Jayaram and Baker (2009).

3.3.2.4.2 Shake-maps using different GMPEs: effect of the array recordings considered as one point

Now we consider replacing the array of 12 stations by one representative point; its coordinates are the average coordinates of the 12 stations, and its value of PGA is also the average value of the recorded PGA at those stations. We generate the shake-maps considering this average observation using the different GMPEs in Figure 50. Notice that the average value of the PGA is slightly higher

than the one predicted by the GMPEs at this location. The location of the stations' array is shown in Figure 51 (left) as dots.

Figure 50: PGA (mean) shake-map estimated using different GMPEs considering one observation as an average for the dense array of 12 stations west of the fault. The spatial correlation function is from Jayaram and Baker (2009).

The average shake-map resulting from those 6 GMPEs is represented in Figure 51 (right), while the shake-map on the left shows the GMPE predictions without taking into account this representative station.

Figure 51: Average shake-maps computed using the 6 GMPEs (left) without considering the PGA recorded at the stations and (right) taking into account the recordings at the station represented as a square. The dots on the left plot represent the 12 stations that are averaged (in coordinates and value of PGA) and used in the right plot as the average observation station of the array.

3.3.2.4.3 Shake-maps at different periods: effect of the uncertainties at the recordings

Figure 52 shows the shake-maps of the ground motion acceleration spectra at different periods, using GMPE1 (KSea20A) and JB2009 for spatial correlation. It illustrates the difference in acceleration spectra behaviour at different periods. Figure 54 shows the corresponding standard deviation values. The same maps are generated in Figure 53 (for the mean) and Figure 55 (for standard deviation), this time, the uncertainties at the site are included. Figure 56 and Figure 57 present a more detailed picture of the standard deviation maps for a range of $[-21.23; -21.17]$ in longitude and $[63.98; 64.02]$ in latitude, corresponding roughly to the extent of the array. Large discrepancies are observed at periods 0.1 s and 0.15 s. This is in accordance with Rahpeyma et al. (2020), who illustrated the relative differences between the posterior distribution of station terms for ICEARRAY I strong-motion stations located on lava-rock with respect to the posterior distribution of the reference station term, for PGA and PSA at different periods (Figure 58).

Figure 52: The mean value of the acceleration spectrum computed at different periods. The shake-maps take into account the observations recorded at the stations. The ground motion is predicted using GMPE1 and JB2009 for modelling the spatial correlation.

Figure 53: Same as Figure 52 considering site uncertainties at the stations.

Figure 54: The standard deviation of the acceleration response spectrum computed at different periods. The shake-maps take into account the observations recorded at the stations. The ground motion is predicted using GMPE1 and JB2009 for modelling the spatial correlation.

Figure 55: Same as Figure 54 considering site uncertainties at the stations.

Figure 56: Same as Figure 54, computed for a smaller area (as a zoom on the set of the stations).

Figure 57: Same as Figure 55, computed for a smaller area (as a zoom on the set of the stations).

Figure 58: Relative differences between the posterior distribution of station terms for ICEARRAY I strong-motion stations located on lava-rock (colour-coded) with respect to the posterior distribution of the reference station term (black dashed curve), estimated for PGA and PSA at different periods ($T = 0.05 \text{ s} - 0.4 \text{ s}$). The reference station term is defined as the average of the posterior distribution of stations IS609, IS611, and IS612, which are not characterized as typical lava-rock stations. From Rahpeyma et al. (2020).

3.3.2.4.4 Effect of the spatial correlation function

The Bayesian approach allows testing of various spatial correlation models and their impact on predicting the ground motion acceleration maps. In general, the similarity of ground-motion IMs at two different sites depends on (Schiappapietra and Douglas 2020):

- (1) the earthquake source. It is accounted for by the inter-event residual provided by the GMPE;
- (2) the propagation path from the source to the sites and local-site effects. The intra-event correlation between all pairs of sites during an earthquake due to the similarity of travel path and local-site effects depends on the inter-site separation distance. Typically, it is modelled as an exponential function and this is tested hereafter;
- (3) the position of closely spaced sites in near-source conditions with respect to the main fault asperities.

In the following, we test 4 intra-event spatial correlation models, listed in Table 13 and illustrated in Figure 43.

The computation of the PGA shake-maps (mean and standard deviation) are shown in Figure 59 and Figure 60, respectively for the range of $[-21.23; -21.17]$ in longitude and $[63.98; 64.02]$ in latitude. Their CVs (using the 4 correlation models) are shown in Figure 61.

Figure 59: Shake-map of PGA (mean value) computed using GMPE1 for different spatial correlation models listed in Table 13.

Figure 60: Shake-map of PGA (standard deviation) computed using GMPE1 for different spatial correlation models listed in Table 13.

Figure 61: Coefficient of variation evaluated when generating shake-maps with different models of spatial correlation (shown in Figure 59 and Figure 60, respectively, for the mean and the standard deviation).

3.3.2.5 Discussion, next steps and future directions

This feasibility and sensitivity study highlights the following:

- The generation of shake-maps for each of the multiple empirical Bayesian ground motion models shows how the resulting mean shake-map accounts partially for the epistemic uncertainty captured by the median ground motion predictions by the GMMs.
- The coefficient of variation for the mean shake-map highlights the spatial confidence of the overall shake-map. As expected, confidence is the least in the extreme near-fault region as the GMMs typically predict considerably different values at such small distances. This is in line with the literature on near-fault simulated motions from dynamic and kinematic rupture models showing that the variability increases in the near-fault region relative to the far-field (Dalguer and Mai 2011).
- The disparity between the large-scale earthquake fault dimensions and the small-scale array aperture where a large number of recordings exist (i.e., dense recordings) appears to disproportionately affect the shake-map estimates relative to those of sparse station recordings. As a result, the generation of the Bayesian shake-map estimate for the region is more feasible.
- A regional Bayesian shake-map will thus provide the constraints required in the overall location of the array to allow for a more realistic array-specific shake-map where all array recordings are used. In other words, a Bayesian shake-map for the town would then exclusively be generated.
- The availability of the site factors for the array station locations allows for a more robust estimate of the shake-map and highlights the effects that such prior information has on the final shake-map estimate.
- Regional shake-maps for the last three strong earthquakes in the SISZ, the 17 and 21 June 2000 and 29 May 2008 events, respectively, need to be generated. The strong-motion data and the finite-fault information has been collected and is to be analysed and implemented in the shake-map generator.
- Similar to the posterior estimates of site factors of the array stations, the site factors for the recording sites of the strong-motion network in Iceland are currently being estimated.
- A new geological map for strong-motion research in southern Iceland is under development.
- The correlation between the site factors at recording sites and their geology allows the site factors to be interpolated regionally across different geological units, thus informing the Bayesian shake-map to provide a more realistic view of the wavefield.
- The Bayesian inferred empirical ground motion models eBGMMs used in this study are symmetric with respect to r_{JB} around the fault. In other words, they do not take into account:
 - the near-fault directivity effects towards the north and south ends of the causative faults, or
 - the general bilateral rupture of SISZ earthquakes.
- As a result, we expect that regional shake-maps will fail to capture this distribution of intense near-fault motions, while at the same time informed (by data) shake-maps would indicate that motions towards the fault-ends are generally larger. Therefore, the eBGMMs need to be updated with specific near-fault terms that take into account the fault geometry, the hypocentral location, and the source-site geometry in a simplified manner.

3.4 Recommendations and conclusions

This feasibility study of RRE systems has been applied to two TB areas, which led to the investigation of two complementary aspects:

- The sensitivity of shake-map outcomes with respect to various hypotheses and modelling assumptions: the influence of a dense seismic array, the influence of different GMPEs, the influence of different spatial correlation models, the influence of considering the uncertainty on observations (i.e., uncertainty of the site terms of the stations). Further developments of GMPEs accounting for area-specific near-fault terms, along with a posterior estimation of site terms for seismic stations, appear to be crucial for the successful implementation of a robust and accurate shake-map system (refer to the study on TB Iceland).
- Coupling of shake-maps with damage assessment tools, especially from the point of view of the propagation of uncertainties related to the hazard input (refer to the study on TB Pyrenees).

In the Pyrenees test-bed, using a virtual earthquake scenario, the resulting shake-map has been successfully coupled to the Armagedom damage assessment software. Moreover, the stochastic generation of ground-motion maps from the shake-map distribution (mean and standard-deviation of the intensity measure at each grid point) has allowed the generation of stochastic damage scenarios, from which damage statistics can be assembled. Such an exercise, while often overlooked in current RRE systems, has the potential to deliver robust loss estimates rapidly (e.g. in the Luchon valley example, damage statistics may be generated within 10 minutes of the earthquake occurrence): providing probabilistic losses instead of deterministic metrics may appear as less accurate. However, it constitutes the only way to consistently account for the multi-sensor capabilities of the TURNkey product and to quantify the gradual reduction of uncertainties as more and more observations are obtained from the field.

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